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ON THE MAIN STAGES OF THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CSTO

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Abstract. *The article is dedicated to the CSTO, which brings together six member states — Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Armenia. It is noted that, in order to address the tasks of ensuring collective security, primary attention must be given to the military-political situation developing within the area of responsibility of a given international organization. From this, it follows that the study of the evolution of the structure of the bodies of the Collective Security Treaty Organization holds significant potential for analyzing the patterns of formation and development of an international regional organization. It is concluded that the formation of the structure is influenced by a combination of specific factors characterizing the political conditions under which a particular organization emerges.*

Keywords: *CSTO, Collective Security Treaty Organization, transformation, security, states*

The Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) has undergone several stages of development, each associated with changes in the geopolitical situation and new security challenges. Its history begins with the Collective Security Treaty (CST), signed in 1992, and culminates in its transformation into a full-fledged international organization with a broad range of tasks. Changes within the CSTO occurred in response to the evolving military-political situation in the post-Soviet space, reflecting a process of adaptation to new conditions, including modifications within the organization's internal structure.

After the collapse of the USSR, fifteen states emerged on the world map, each defining its geopolitical stance and shaping its foreign policy orientation. Several countries chose the Western path of development, primarily the Baltic states; others remained open to the prospect of economic reintegration, while some

considered the possibility of military-political integration within the framework of a new collective security system.

Before the establishment of the CSTO, the Collective Security Treaty (CST) was in force, signed on May 15, 1992. The CSTO was initially signed by six states; later, three more countries—Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Belarus—joined. Contradictory approaches to resolving emerging issues occurred within the CSTO, resulting in crisis phenomena; there was no unified understanding of how to address the tasks facing the CSTO. At the end of the 1990s, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Uzbekistan declined to extend their participation in the CSTO, and the remaining members faced the need to fundamentally revise the format of military-political integration.

At the beginning of the new decade, the CSTO was transformed into a fully-fledged international regional organization on May 14, 2002. A decision was made to establish the CSTO [1, pp. 31-35]. As a result of the prevailing circumstances, a transformation took place, primarily linked to the military-political situation in the territory of the former Union. A change in political power occurred in the Russian Federation, leading to a reassessment of the country's geopolitical role both regionally and globally. New forms and mechanisms of integration were necessary for the new Russia. Moreover, at the end of the 1990s, a number of militarily dangerous incidents occurred in the Central Asia region. In August 1999, militants of the Islamic Movement of Uzbekistan carried out an incursion into the Batken region of Kyrgyzstan, revealing the unpreparedness of national governments to respond to a new type of military threat. For example, '...the experience of Afghanistan's historical development, both positive and negative, is very important for the peoples of Central Asia, as it underscores the need to avoid its fate and not become an arena of military confrontation and clashes of external powers with all the ensuing consequences...' [2]. The intensification of drug trafficking from Afghanistan also underscored the necessity of seeking new forms of military-political cooperation among the states of the region. Concurrently with these events, the situation in the North Caucasus evolved, associated with the commencement of Russia's counterterrorist operation in Chechnya and the adjacent border areas. The combination of these circumstances prompted the reform of the CSTO [3, p.142]. The CSTO member states were tested on the strength of their inter-state ties. The suspension of Armenia's membership in the CSTO is the result of one such crisis. The transformation of the military-political situation has largely defined the functional scope of the CSTO's activities, which positions itself as an organization fulfilling diverse functions.

Researcher A.I. Nikitin proposes identifying two 'clusters' of CSTO functions that have existed throughout the organization's history; these functions are not performed in isolation but are closely intertwined and mutually conditioning [4, p. 912]. The first 'cluster' of CSTO functions arises from the need to address new threats and

challenges characteristic of the current stage of development of the military-political situation in the post-Soviet space. The threats in question are, in some cases, not directly connected to hostile actions by specific states but often originate from non-state actors and result from political instability in neighboring countries. Such challenges include threats related to the increase in terrorist and extremist activities; dangers associated with illegal migration flows; risks of internal political destabilization within CSTO member states. It was precisely the new threats that prompted the transformation of the military-political situation at the turn of the century, which ultimately led to the hybridization of risks in the field of military security. To a large extent, these threats result from the escalation of the situation in the Middle East and Central Asia, including the US military intervention in Afghanistan and the destabilization of the security environment in these regions.

The second ‘basket’ of functions of the CSTO is directly linked to the creation of collective armed forces and, more broadly, the overall military infrastructure of the CSTO member states, enabling an effective response to threats to military security. The implementation of these functions is generally aimed at addressing the classical tasks of ensuring collective security, which fit within the overall logic of forming a military-defense alliance [4, p. 916].

The CSTO has a complex structure of governing bodies, which can be divided into political bodies and military command bodies. The political bodies are primarily defined by the CSTO Charter: their core has remained unchanged throughout the entire history of the regional organization’s existence, supplemented by a set of auxiliary (consultative) bodies and intergovernmental cooperation bodies [5, p. 18].

The supreme political governing body is the Collective Security Council (CSC) of the CSTO, which is composed of the heads of the member states. Its competence encompasses the resolution of the most fundamental issues pertaining to the organization’s activities. The CSC coordinates the activities of the member states; however, due to objective difficulties in convening its meetings, the coordination function between CSC sessions is carried out by the Permanent Council of the CSTO. The permanent bodies of the CSTO also include the Secretariat, headed by the Secretary General, and the CSTO Joint Staff, which addresses issues of military cooperation. A separate branch of the CSTO’s political bodies comprises advisory (executive) organs such as the Council of Foreign Ministers, the Council of Defence Ministers, and the Committee of Security Council Secretaries [6, p. 505].

Changes in the architecture of the CSTO’s political bodies are relatively rare and seldom fundamental; their system is structured in accordance with the logic of operational management of the organization’s activities and is aimed at defining the strategy of member states’ actions. In order to address the legal issues related to the formalization of the CSTO’s activities, the establishment of the CSTO Parliamentary Assembly as a body of inter-parliamentary cooperation is necessitated.

There also arose a need to intensify constructive work on the legal support of the organization's activities, which is associated with the separation of the CSTO from the legal system of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS).

The influence of this factor is much more clearly observed within the process of constructing the so-called horizontal military systems — the integration of armed forces by branches and troop types. The structure of the CSTO military formations is designed to address operational and tactical issues related to the military security of member states [7.c,15].

The Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO) has undergone several stages of formation, associated with the development of its structure, the expansion of its functions, and adaptation to the evolving international environment.

The first stage, 1992–2002: the formation of the CSTO and initial changes in its composition. On May 15, 1992, in Tashkent, the Collective Security Treaty was signed by Armenia, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia, Tajikistan, and Uzbekistan. In 1993, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Belarus joined the CSTO. In 1994, the treaty entered into force. In 1999, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and Uzbekistan declined to extend their participation in the CSTO. After that, the center of gravity shifted to Central Asia⁸. The second stage, 2002–2008: transformation into the CSTO and institutional establishment. On May 14, 2002, a decision was made in Moscow to transform the CSTO into the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO)[8].

In October 2002, the Charter and the Agreement on the Legal Status of the CSTO were signed in Chişinău, entering into force on September 18, 2003, following ratification by all member states. By 2004, the main bodies of the CSTO were established: the Collective Security Council (CSC), the Permanent Council, the Council of Foreign Ministers, the Council of Defence Ministers, the Committee of Security Council Secretaries, the Secretariat, and the Joint Staff. In 2004, the CSTO obtained observer status at the UN General Assembly. In 2006, Uzbekistan's membership was restored (suspended in 2012).

The Collective Rapid Reaction Forces (CRRF) are joint military forces of the member states of the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO), established to promptly respond to security challenges and threats faced by the member countries. They were formed based on the Decision of the CSTO Collective Security Council dated 4 February 2009.

The third stage from 2009: strengthening the military component and expanding functions. On 4 February 2009, at an extraordinary session held in Moscow, the decision was adopted to establish the Collective Rapid Reaction Forces (CRRF). The agreement was signed on June 14, 2009, by all CSTO members except Uzbekistan and Belarus (the latter joined later). In 2011, a Protocol on the deployment of military infrastructure facilities on the territories of CSTO member states was signed.

The CSTO began active cooperation in combating illegal drug trafficking (Operation 'Channel'), illegal migration (Operation 'Illegal'), and countering crimes in the information environment (Operation 'Proxy').

The fourth stage from 2014: a new phase amid geopolitical tensions. This period is characterized by the increasing influence of the West on the post-Soviet countries, the sanctions war against Russia, the escalation of the Armenian-Azerbaijani conflict, and other challenges. In 2022, the CSTO contingent was deployed to Kazakhstan at the request of President K.-Zh. K. Tokayev in response to mass protests.

The fifth stage: contemporary trends (the 2020s). The CSTO Collective Security Strategy for the period up to 2025 was adopted, defining the tasks and mechanisms for ensuring security amid new threats. Cooperation with the UN, SCO, CIS, and other organizations is actively developing[9].

In 2024, the then CSTO Secretary General Imangali Tasmagambetov identified threats such as the deployment of 'long-range' strike weapons in Europe, the concentration of NATO armed forces near the borders of Belarus and Russia, and Western support for Ukraine[10]. In 2026, reforms of the CSTO were announced, aimed at enhancing the organization's effectiveness in the face of new challenges.

Armenia is one of the founders of the CSTO. Since February 2024, Armenia has announced a 'freeze' on its participation in the activities of the CSTO. Prime Minister Nikol Pashinyan stated that the organization failed to fulfill its obligations to Armenia, particularly during 2021–2022, and posed threats to the sovereignty of the republic. As a reason, he cited the lack of an adequate response by the CSTO to the situation in Nagorno-Karabakh and the fact that the organization did not provide protection for Armenia. In November 2023, Armenia disregarded the CSTO summit in Minsk, and in 2025 refused to participate in the organization's financing. In December 2025, Nikol Pashinyan stated that relations between Armenia and the CSTO had crossed the 'point of no return.' However, according to a statement by the Russian MFA issued in December 2025, Armenia remains a full member of the CSTO, retaining all corresponding rights and obligations. The official representative of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Maria Zakharova, noted that there are no obstacles to Armenia's resumption of full participation in the organization. [11]. In January 2026, the Foreign Intelligence Service of Armenia stated in its annual report that the position regarding the freezing of the country's membership in the CSTO remains unchanged in 2026. The report considered this a 'challenge to the authority of the regional security structure'[12].

Consequently, Armenia formally remains a member of the CSTO but, in fact, has not participated in its activities since 2024. The issue of a country's complete withdrawal from the organization has not yet been resolved [13].

In summary, it can be stated that the CSTO aims to become a more multi-functional structure, extending beyond a purely military alliance. Discussions are

ongoing regarding the organization's expansion and the inclusion of new states. The focus is on countering new threats: cybercrime, illegal migration, terrorism, and extremism. Thus, the development dynamics of the CSTO reflect the evolution of the geopolitical situation in the post-Soviet space and its adaptation to changing security challenges.

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THE EVOLUTION OF REPRESENTATIVE (LEGISLATIVE) POWER IN KAMCHATKA. FROM THE REGIONAL COMMITTEE TO THE REGIONAL COUNCIL

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Abstract. *The article examines the historical aspects of the formation and development of representative power in Kamchatka from 1917 to 1939, set against the changing socio-economic conditions of the region and the country. The issues concerning the evolution of legislative bodies during the establishment of Soviet authority in the Far East are examined.*

Keywords: *popular representation, Kamchatka Regional Committee, Soviet of the Working People, Congress of Soviets, Regional Council of Workers' Deputies, representative authorities, Far East, citizens, voters, delegates, deputies, sessions.*

17 July 1909. (According to the old style) Petropavlovsk uезд, a vast territory encompassing the present Kamchatka Krai, was separated from Primorsky Oblast to form the independent Kamchatka Oblast with the introduction of the guberniya form of administration. The population of the region as of January 1, 1913, amounted, according to approximate estimates, to only 34,492 people. The most populous was the Petropavlovsk district, where 10,681 people resided. The least populous was considered the Komandorsky district — only 519 people [1].

There was no notion of «popular representation» whatsoever, except for rural assemblies of the peasant population, which resolved economic issues and issued «public verdicts». Police bailiffs were present at the meetings and communicated their decisions to the administration. The Petropavlovsk City Administration operated in the Kamchatka capital, headed by the city elder.

General assemblies were held as necessary, during which, for example, the remuneration for the city chimney sweep ‘for the pipes he cleaned in the city’ [2] was determined, or funds were raised to support the school. Political issues were

not discussed at these meetings. These are, in broad terms, the conditions under which Kamchatka Oblast entered the turbulent year of 1917.

Following the February Revolution in Petrograd and the dismantling of the customary century-old imperial 'vertical,' dual power was established across Russia in the form of Committees of Public Security — the local bodies of the bourgeois Provisional Government — on the one hand, and Soviets of Workers', Soldiers', and Peasants' Deputies of social-democratic orientation — on the other. In Kamchatka Oblast, owing to the absence of revolutionary organizations, the Soviet was not established.

March 3, 1917. In Petropavlovsk, news of Emperor Nicholas II's abdication became known. Already on March 6, in the presence of the vice-governor, the administration, and the bishop, a general meeting of townspeople and representatives from the surrounding villages was held. There, by order of the Provisional Government, a city committee of public safety was elected, comprising five members and four candidates 'to them,' as they were termed at the time. The committee, headed by the lawyer K. E. Emelyanov, comprised predominantly officials and clerks, but also included one worker. The committee essentially assumed the responsibilities of the regional authority; therefore, on March 12, it was transformed into the provisional Kamchatka Regional Committee (hereinafter KRC). Subsequently, on June 5, 1917, a 'permanent' KRC was elected, consisting of eight members chaired by the radio station employee A. A. Purin. Thus, instead of the provincial administration, an elected governing body first appeared in Kamchatka. The KRC and the regional commissar of the Provisional Government (who was K. E. Emelyanov) began exercising state power on the peninsula. Similar committees also emerged in the uyezds. Simultaneously, a commission was formed to convene the 1st Kamchatka Regional Congress of Population Representatives to discuss and resolve urgent issues concerning the region.

At that time, the region lacked political parties and mass public organizations. To legitimize the new authority embodied by the KRC, the 1st Kamchatka Regional Congress was convened in Petropavlovsk, held from July 20 to August 9, 1917. It was anticipated that, according to the representation norm of one delegate per 250 residents, 134 delegates would gather. However, due to inadequate communication routes and the 'low awareness' of the nomadic population, only 41 delegates arrived in the city, representing merely 30.6% of the potential congress participants [3].

Nevertheless, the delegates (at that time referred to as 'members of the congress') represented the population of nearly all corners of the vast Kamchatka Oblast. They discussed how to proceed amid the collapse of the former monarchical government and the transition to an unprecedented elective popular democratic system during the instability of central authority. From that point onward, the congresses became the highest authority in the oblast.

This first popular congress entered the history of Kamchatka as one of exceptional significance. For the first time in the entire history of the region, the congress heard the opinions of the “natives,” who outlined the peculiarities of their life, the state of the local economy, and developed a plan for the reorganization of the economic and administrative life of the region. The congress established the regional public and administrative authority. From that time onward, regardless of the political and economic conditions prevailing on the peninsula at various times, the issues discussed formed the basis of the agendas of all subsequent representative bodies of authority for a century ahead.

November 7 (October 25, old style), 1917. An epochal event took place in Petrograd, which, depending on political preferences, was called the ‘October Revolution’ (later the ‘Great October Socialist Revolution’) or the ‘Bolshevik coup.’ At the citywide meeting in Petropavlovsk held on October 27, the KRC presented it as an illegal seizure of power by the Bolsheviks against the will of the people [4]. However, local supporters of Bolshevism now had grounds to establish their own body — the Petropavlovsk City Soviet of Workers’, Soldiers’, and Peasants’ Deputies. Elections to this body were held on December 7-8, 1917, with Private I. E. Larin of the local military unit appointed as chairman. Dual power consequently extended to the Kamchatka region as well.

January 1, 1918. At its extended session, the Soviet declared itself the supreme representative of Soviet authority ‘within its sphere of influence.’ On January 6, at a joint meeting of the KRC, the Soviet, and the subsequently elected 1st Petropavlovsk City Duma, two representatives from the Soviet were incorporated into the regional committee. This caused indignation among part of the population, who demanded that those who were publicly unelected leave the KRC. Thus began the still peaceful civil confrontation between supporters of the Bolsheviks and their opponents. The KRC gradually lost ground, and on 27 February 1918, Soviet power was declared in Kamchatka.

Shortly thereafter, the KRC was transformed into the Kamchatka Regional Soviet. From 27 March 1918, it was designated the ‘Regional Soviet of Workers’ and Peasants’ Deputies,’ or abbreviated as the ‘Regional Sovdep’ [5].

July 12, 1918. An anti-Soviet coup took place in Petropavlovsk, as a result of which power was transferred to the new KRC. Captain of the steamship ‘Admiral Zavoyko’, G. A. Rosenfeld, received the following dispatch from the committee: ‘Informing you that Soviet power in the city of Petropavlovsk and in Kamchatka Oblast was overthrown by the efforts of the people on the night of the 28th to 29th (old style) and the authorities arrested, with power passing to the KRC and [local self-government], I propose that from today you comply only with orders issued on behalf of the KRC.’ All orders were to be signed by the chairman of the committee, A. A. Purin, and his comrade, P. Ya. Suslyak” [6].

On July 12, the KRC resolved to convene the 2nd Kamchatka Regional Congress. It opened on September 14, 1918. The representation norm was established as one person per 100 citizens; therefore, 340 delegates were to be elected from the entire region. It should be assumed that the organizers understood the term “citizens” to mean eligible citizens aged 18 and over. The congress was attended by 46 (27%), of whom 39 (22.9%) held valid mandates» [7].

A. A. Purin was re-elected chairman of the KRC. He recalled the work of the congress as follows: «The representatives of the population approved all actions of the regional committee, supplemented the resolutions of the 1st congress, and, based on the report by K. P. Lavrov, recognized the necessity of establishing the Fishery Administration in the Far East, which would centralize all matters of the fishing industry, fur, and wildlife management.» All non-conventional (i. e., those exempted from the Russo-Japanese Fishing Convention of 1907) waters were to be transferred to the disposal of the local population, and their exploitation was to be used for building schools, constructing roads, acquiring steamships, establishing small-scale fish canning factories, and meeting various zemstvo and indigenous needs of the region...” [8].

At the beginning of January 1919. In the Far East, the government of Admiral A. V. Kolchak came to power. Its influence also extended to Kamchatka. Instead of a regional commissioner, a regional manager was appointed here: N. N. Chervlyansky, the former head of the office of the previous governor. The KRC was dissolved, but the old system of governance was restored in the form of district managers, volost elders, and village chiefs [9].

The authority of the ‘Supreme Ruler of Russia,’ A. V. Kolchak, on the peninsula lasted for nearly a year. In Petropavlovsk, it was overthrown on January 10, 1920. In its place, the Temporary Military-Revolutionary Committee (hereinafter TMRC) was established, headed by P. S. Malovechkin. Soon, the first organization of the RCP(b), that is, the Russian Communist Party (Bolsheviks), was established in the city [10].

From March 12 to April 7, 1920, the 1st Extraordinary Petropavlovsk County Congress of Soviets convened in Petropavlovsk and elected the Regional Soviet of the Working People (hereinafter RSWP). P. S. Malovechkin was elected chairman of the congress. At the congress, the following system of power was proposed: regional STN — district STN — volost and rural STN. These Soviets establish their own executive committees. The main committee — the Kamchatka Regional Executive Committee (KOIK) — oversees seventeen departments. These include the administrative, accounting, control, financial, education, postal and telegraph, people’s protection (militia), transport, trade and industrial, food supply, fur, fishery, mining, public health, forestry, agricultural, and people’s court departments [11].

April 6, 1920. The establishment of the Far Eastern Republic was proclaimed, a ‘buffer state’ between Soviet Russia and Japan, bourgeois-democratic in form

but under communist leadership. Kamchatka Oblast became part of this new state formation. On the peninsula, on May 23, 1920, the authority of the Primorsky Provisional Government — the government of the Far East, ‘which seeks union with Soviet Russia’ [11]—was recognized.

June 7, 1920. I. E. Larin was elected chairman of the Kamchatka Regional Executive Committee. This governing body was officially and fully designated as the “Kamchatka Regional Executive Committee of the Provisional Government in the Far East.”

July 24, 1920. KOIK issued a circular to all district, volost, and village executive committees calling for the convocation of the 3rd regional congress. The document affirmed that “the region faces the threat of occupation by our allies (namely Japan). Therefore, coordinated actions among the population are required, a ‘unified will and policy... Separatist actions by the Okhotsk and Anadyr districts and the divergence of resolutions independently adopted by each district, which resulted in unfortunate consequences affecting the regional economy and international relations, have provided the interventionists with an additional pretext to interfere in our internal affairs” [12].

The 3rd Kamchatka Regional Congress opened on October 11, 1920. According to the representation norm introduced by the regional executive committee’s regulation, one delegate was elected for every 500 inhabitants. In total, there were to be 73 people’s representatives, but only 20 attended, all possessing the right to vote. This congress should be regarded as an attempt to establish authorities involving heterogeneous political forces. Its delegates held various viewpoints. The presidium comprised Chairman I. I. Gapanovich, First Secretary A. I. Babkin-Baikalov, and Second Secretary N. A. Bobrov. In the field of fisheries, the delegates insisted on the necessity of securing Kamchatka’s participation in the profits from the exploitation of fisheries: “The congress regretfully noted that with each passing year the region’s rights to lease fisheries are diminishing. They expressed especially vigorous opposition at the congress to the continued existence of large river fisheries” [13]. Demands were raised to transfer private fish hatcheries to state ownership and to levy a special tax on fishing industry entrepreneurs for their maintenance. The congress adopted a resolution on fishery management, the protection of sea otter haul-outs at Cape Lopatka, traveling trade, and measures to eliminate the resulting disadvantages for the population. The concluding phrases in the congress protocol were: ‘Long live the power of the working people! Long live the self-activity of the Kamchatka laborers and the swift reunification with Soviet Russia!’ [13].

Such reunification occurred more than two years later — on November 10, 1922. It is considered that on this day the administrative center of the region — the city of Petropavlovsk-on-Kamchatka, abandoned a week earlier by the White forces who had departed by steamship into exile, was occupied by detachments of Red partisans, after which Soviet power was finally proclaimed in Kamchatka.

The decisions made at the aforementioned congresses had to be taken into account by all subsequent Kamchatka authorities, and many were subsequently implemented in the 1930s and later.

On November 17, 1922. As part of the RSFSR, the Far Eastern Oblast was established, which included Kamchatka Oblast. On December 6, 1922, the oblast was renamed Kamchatka Governorate [14]. The highest authority in the territory was now called the 'Kamchatka Governorate Revolutionary Committee.' On December 31, 1922, sectoral departments were formed within it: for state taxes, levies, and duties; public education; public communications; finance; justice (performing the functions of the prosecutor's office); provincial GPU; communal economy; registry of civil status acts and the workers' and peasants' inspection.

Simultaneously, a world-historical event took place — on December 30, 1922. the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) was established — 'the world's first unified multinational state of workers and peasants.' The RSFSR was one of its founders.

In January 1923, the organization of grassroots authorities began in Kamchatka — the revolutionary committees appointed 'from above' at the local level, that is, in uyezds and volosts. During 1923, volost congresses were held. The revolutionary committees governed and carried out Soviet work until 1926 [14].

On January 4, 1926, by decree of the USSR Central Executive Committee, the Far Eastern Krai was established with its administrative center in Khabarovsk. The highest authority in the district territory was now the Kamchatka District Revolutionary Committee (okrrevkom) [14].

August 21, 1928. The 1st Kamchatka District Congress of Soviets was convened in Petropavlovsk at the club of the Union of Soviet Trade Employees. Its purpose was to 'review all the work carried out by the district revolutionary committee during its five years of existence' and to determine objectives for the coming years. The congress acknowledged that the sovietization of the Kamchatka district had been completed. The district revolutionary committee transferred its authority to the newly elected executive committee of the Kamchatka District Soviet of Workers', Peasants', and Red Army Deputies (district executive committee).

20 October 1932. By resolution of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee of the RSFSR, 'On the reorganization of the administrative-territorial division of the Far Eastern Krai,' Kamchatka Oblast was established, consisting of the Petropavlovsk, Ust-Bolsheretsky, Ust-Kamchatsky, Aleutsky, and Bystrinsky districts. Kamchatka Oblast and the Koryak National Okrug were incorporated into Khabarovsk Krai [14].

8 April 1933. The 1st Kamchatka Oblast Congress of Soviets was held. The summary was given by the Chairman of the Organizational Committee of the Dalkrayispolkom, G. N. Korenev: '...Our task is to transform the region into a powerful

industrial-export base.' Therefore, you, the delegates of the congress, must undertake extensive work locally to explain this task. Less whining, fewer references to Kamchatka's conditions, 'less empty talk, more simple, everyday work' (V. I. Lenin). Let us unite around the Soviet power and the party and overcome all difficulties by storm! We must ensure that steamships arrive filled with people and depart from us fully loaded with goods. Having returned to your respective locations, you must inform the grassroots workers about the issues discussed at the congress and the ways to resolve them. You must mobilize the masses to fulfill the economic tasks, and then, under the leadership of the VKP(b), and under the leadership of our regional party committee, we will manage together with them.» [15]

The next, 2nd regional congress of Soviets opened a year and a half later, on November 20, 1934. At this congress, in particular, the state and prospects for the development of agriculture in Kamchatka Oblast were examined, and it was proposed to focus on the development of local industry.

The 3rd Kamchatka Regional Congress of Soviets commenced at six o'clock in the evening on October 6, 1936, in Petropavlovsk, at the Party Enlightenment House named after S. M. Kirov (currently housing the Kamchatka Regional United Museum). It was declared 'extraordinary' because its main task was to discuss the draft of an extremely important document — the new fundamental law — the second Constitution of the USSR, known as the 'Stalin Constitution.'

January 21, 1937. At the 17th Extraordinary All-Russian Congress of Soviets, the Constitution of the RSFSR was adopted. In accordance with it, sessions of regional and oblast Soviets of Workers' Deputies were convened by decisions of their executive committees at least four times a year. For conducting the sessions, the deputies elected a chairman and a secretary. Accountability of the executive committees was established both to the Soviet that elected them and to the executive committee of the higher Soviet, in our case the Khabarovsk Regional Soviet (Kamchatka Oblast became part of Khabarovsk Krai in 1938). The establishment of the foundations of socialism in the USSR made it possible to abandon the electoral system established in 1918 and thereafter to conduct universal, equal, and direct elections by secret ballot.

December 24, 1939. Elections to local Soviets were held simultaneously across the country. The first convocation of the Kamchatka Regional Soviet of Working People's Deputies comprised 81 elected deputies.

A careful study of archival documents allows one to conclude that from this time and for many years until 1993... It is precisely the Regional Soviets that will determine the future development paths of Kamchatka Oblast and its national economy and implement the mandates of their constituents.

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RESTRICTION OF PARENTAL RIGHTS IN RUSSIA: A COMPARATIVE LEGAL ANALYSIS WITH THE LEGISLATION OF THE USA, GERMANY, AND AUSTRALIA

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Abstract: *In today's world, protecting the rights and legitimate interests of minors is a priority for any state. However, it's worth noting that the mechanisms for implementing this policy in national legal systems vary significantly across countries.*

In Russia, the institution of restricting parental rights is a preventative measure, essentially removing a child from the parent(s) while preserving their fundamental rights and responsibilities with respect to the minor.

This article provides a comparative legal analysis of the domestic institution of restricting parental rights with similar legal institutions in countries such as the United States, Germany, and Australia.

Key words: *Family, family law, rights and interests of the child, restriction of parental rights, institution for the protection of children's rights in foreign countries.*

In the Russian Federation, the institution of restricting parental rights was first introduced with the adoption of the Family Code, specifically in 1995 [1]. Prior to this period, the previously existing Code on Marriage and Family of the RSFSR contained only one measure of protection for minors: deprivation of parental rights [2]. It is worth noting that restricting parental rights was introduced as a more «gentle» measure to protect children's rights, as, unlike deprivation of parental rights, it does not completely sever family relations between the parent(s) and the child.

As noted above, the basic provisions for the application of restricting parental rights in Russia are enshrined in the Family Code. Article 73 establishes the procedure and grounds for applying this measure as a measure to protect the rights of minors.

In the Russian legal system, only the court has the exclusive prerogative to apply such a measure of protection for a child as restricting parental rights. It is the judicial body, guided by the principle of the minor's priority, that is authorized to make the final decision on this matter.

Legal grounds for restricting parental rights include, on the one hand, objectively dangerous circumstances beyond the control of the parents (chronic illness, severe mental disorder, etc.), and, on the other, the culpable behavior of the parents themselves, posing a threat to the child. A characteristic feature of current Russian family law is the lack of an exhaustive list of such circumstances, which grants the court broad discretionary powers in assessing each specific situation.

For example, Article 69 of the Family Code establishes a specific list of conditions under which the court applies the institution of deprivation of parental rights. In turn, as we noted above, the norm regulating the circumstances under which restriction of parental rights is permitted does not provide a specific list. Instead, these types of situations are generalized, thereby creating a difficult situation for the judicial body deciding on the application of this institution in law enforcement practice. The range of entities entitled to file a lawsuit to limit parental rights is strictly defined by Russian family law. This list includes:

1. Close relatives of the minor;
2. Guardianship and trusteeship authorities;
3. The prosecutor;
4. Preschool educational institutions;
5. General education institutions, etc.

In modern law enforcement practice in Russia, in most cases, close relatives and guardianship and trusteeship authorities file this lawsuit, while the prosecutor, in turn, represents the interests of the minor during the trial.

Among the aforementioned entities, guardianship and trusteeship authorities are the only ones with a legally established obligation. According to family law, if the parents' behavior does not change within six months of restricting their parental rights, guardianship authorities are required to file a lawsuit to terminate their parental rights (Article 73 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation).

A distinctive feature of the process of restricting parental rights in Russia is that the court, when considering this category of cases, also decides on the collection of child support from the parents (or one of them).

Restricting parental rights entails the loss of the right to personally raise the child, as well as the right to receive related state benefits and allowances. However, the parent retains the obligation to support the minor. As for the right of communication, it may be permitted to the parent only if such contact does not have a harmful effect on the child (Article 75 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation).

Such communication is permitted only with the consent of the guardianship and trusteeship authorities, the guardian (custodian), or the administration of the institution where the child is located.

Russian legislation provides parents whose rights have been restricted the right to file a lawsuit to overturn this measure and return the child. For such a request to be satisfied, two conditions must be met simultaneously: the complete elimination of the circumstances that served as the basis for the restriction and a favorable court decision, made with due consideration of the minor's opinion (Article 76 of the Family Code of the Russian Federation).

Thus, based on the conducted analysis of legal norms regarding the application of the institution of restriction of parental rights in Russia, it can be concluded that, in principle, the legislation sets forth the basic principles for the application of this measure to protect the rights of minors. However, a number of issues remain that, first and foremost, require legislative reform. For example, the problem of incompletely defining the concept of «dangerous situation» for a child (in this case, the legislator fails to regulate its content, which in practice leads to its evaluative and vague nature) or the lack of an effective system of parental rehabilitation, which would lead to a reduction not only in the use of parental rights restrictions but also in their subsequent deprivation.

The American legal system adheres to a completely different mechanism for protecting the rights of minors. Thus, unlike Russia, the US legal system does not have a specific, formalized institution for restricting parental rights. US social policy in the area of child protection is focused on the «early intervention» model, the goal of which is to preserve family integrity and prevent further removal of the child from the family [3, p. 40].

The American legal system places parents who abuse psychoactive substances (PSA) in a separate high-risk category, as their behavior poses a direct threat to the safety and well-being of the child. This group is characterized by a range of associated problems that exacerbate the situation, including:

- mental disorders (primarily personality disorders);
- a criminal record;
- raising a child in a single-parent family.
- child neglect (due to parents ignoring their responsibilities for care and proper provision) [3, pp. 40-41].

It is worth noting that in addition to this category of citizens, parents who suffer from alcohol or drug addiction are also subject to restrictions or even termination of parental rights in the United States.

The American legal system has specialized Family Courts to resolve such cases, authorized to implement compulsory addiction treatment programs [3, p. 41].

Their uniqueness lies in their procedural approach: through a system of regular court hearings and monitoring, a specific goal is achieved — ensuring parental accountability and therapeutic intervention.

In each state, a specific Child Protective Services (CPS) agency oversees the rights and interests of children. This agency has broad powers to identify child abuse and neglect. It's worth noting that each state's family law defines the authority of this agency differently. That is, state laws govern the definition of abuse, establish grounds for child removal, and so on.

Furthermore, since in the United States, in addition to legislation, case law also has particular legal significance, court decisions also carry particular weight for Child Protective Services (CPS) staff. For example, the 1982 US Supreme Court decision in *Santosky v. Kramer* held that clear and convincing evidence must be established before parents can limit or terminate their rights with respect to their minor.

A significant difference between the restriction of parental rights in the US and Russia is that in our domestic law enforcement practice, before (or after) the application of the institution of restricting parental rights, there is a complete absence of state intervention through appropriate services to address, rehabilitate, and assist families where the rights and interests of minors are violated.

State regulation of the rights and interests of minors in Australia is quite different. Legislation in effect throughout Australia requires citizens to report abuse or neglect of a child to the Department of Social Services [3, p. 42].

Australia's government policy is primarily focused on responding to and eliminating circumstances that violate children's rights through specific organizations, such as the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD), Child Well-being Coordinators (CWC), and others [5].

The authority to make decisions regarding the removal of minors and the subsequent restriction of parental rights in Australia lies exclusively with the family courts. Before a case goes to court, social welfare officials, along with the police, investigate complaints from citizens regarding child abuse or inadequate care of minors.

After this investigation, a final determination is made regarding whether parents have violated the rights and legitimate interests of a minor. It's worth noting that, as in the United States, in Australia, the relevant services implement a number of measures to assist families and address situations that violate the rights and interests of minors. If all efforts by the relevant services fail, a protective order for the minor is issued through a court appeal.

In turn, in Germany, as in Russia, there is separate legislation, namely the German Civil Code (*Bürgerliches Gesetzbuch*), which contains provisions on the right to intervene in the family if parental actions violate the rights and legitimate interests of minors [4, p. 296]. A comparative analysis shows that German law, unlike Russian law, does not operate the category of «restriction of parental rights» as an independent institution. The German Civil Code provides for a flexible system of measures for interfering with the exercise of the right to care for a child.

The grounds for such intervention, similar to the Russian approach, are differentiated into:

- a) culpable parental behavior that violates the child's rights, and
- b) objectively dangerous situations arising regardless of the parents' fault [4, p. 296].

Thus, when establishing these grounds, the family court (Familiengericht), at the request of one of the parents, a relative, or the youth welfare office (Jugendamt), may compel the parents, seek assistance from special services, determine the child's place of residence with the other parent (if the other parent is unable to provide care and support for the child), or, in extreme cases, deprive the child of the «right to care.» In other words, before restricting parental rights, the court is primarily focused on applying measures that will help eliminate circumstances that violate the rights and interests of the minor.

In this regard, the comparative legal analysis revealed a significant difference in the functional focus of the institution of restricting parental rights in Russia and in foreign countries (the United States, Australia, and Germany). While in Russian practice this measure is primarily implemented through family monitoring, in the foreign jurisdictions studied, it is part of a comprehensive rehabilitation program aimed at restoring parent-child relationships. In our opinion, this approach, despite its complexity and high resource intensity, would contribute not only to a reduction in the number of parental rights restrictions in Russia but also to the subsequent deprivation of parental rights.

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INTEGRATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL KNOWLEDGE INTO FORENSIC TACTICS: FROM THEORY TO PRACTICE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY INTERACTION

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to the study of the processes and outcomes of integrating psychological concepts into forensic tactics. The theoretical foundations of interdisciplinary synthesis are analyzed, the most essential psychological knowledge for various investigative procedures is identified, and applied aspects of psychological methods in the tactics of interrogation, inspection, and search are examined. The necessity of developing fundamental psychological competencies in investigators as a prerequisite for effective investigations is substantiated.*

Keywords: *forensic tactics, psychological knowledge, interdisciplinary approach, investigative actions, professional competence, lie detection, psychological contact.*

Forensic tactics, throughout its history, have developed as a science focused on the most rational and effective methods for organizing investigations. However, for a long time, its toolkit was formed predominantly through the generalization of investigative experience and logical-legal analysis, while the psychological component remained on the periphery of scientific consideration. Today the situation is fundamentally changing.

The practice of investigation increasingly presents investigators with tasks whose solutions are impossible without a profound understanding of the psychology of participants in the criminal process. As N. I. Valkyria accurately observes, forensic science in general, and forensic tactics in particular, cannot develop without integration with the advances of psychological science, since any investigative action is always an interaction between people, encompassing all related psychological regularities. Indeed, whether it is the interrogation of a suspect, crime scene examination, or search, the

investigator constantly deals with human behavior, emotions, motivation, perception, and memory¹.

The problem, however, lies in the existing gap between theoretical psychological knowledge and its practical application in investigative activities. Psychological concepts often remain within the domain of academic science, failing to transform into specific tactical recommendations accessible to practicing legal professionals. On the other hand, investigators, when faced with real psychological phenomena (resistance, deception, fear, aggression), are forced to act intuitively, relying on everyday experience, which does not always lead to the desired outcome.

The present study aims to bridge this gap. We start from the premise that psychological knowledge should not merely complement forensic tactics but be organically integrated into its fabric, becoming an indispensable element of the investigator's professional competence. Only such an interdisciplinary synthesis can ensure the effectiveness of investigations amid an increasingly complex criminal reality.

The integration of psychological knowledge into forensic tactics constitutes a complex, multi-level process that requires not merely mechanical borrowing of terms but their substantive adaptation to the objectives of investigative activity. As accurately noted in contemporary research, forensic science, as an integrative discipline, actively utilizes concepts from various fields of knowledge; however, such borrowing often results in distortion of the original terms, particularly evident in the realm of psychological concepts. This presents a challenge for science not merely to transfer, but to methodologically refine the transformation of psychological knowledge into tactical tools².

The most prominent example of such terminological borrowing is the concept of “psychological contact.” In scientific psychology, it is strictly defined as a conscious interaction between individuals based on perception, acceptance, and reflection, associated with the theories of Kurt Lewin and Carl Rogers. In forensic tactics, this concept takes on a narrow professional meaning, emphasizing not so much the depth of mutual understanding but the achievement of a specific procedural objective — obtaining complete and reliable testimony. Such a transformation is not a distortion in a negative sense; rather, it reflects the pragmatic nature of forensic science as a discipline serving the needs of

¹ Valkyria N. I. Forensic examination of skills and abilities in the application of psychotechnologies // *Russian Investigator*. 2024, No. 9, pp. 2-5. DOI:10.18572/1812-3783-2024-9-2-5.

² See: Shaevich A. A. Forensic Thinking: Between Interdisciplinarity and Terminological Uncertainty // *Forensic Science: Yesterday, Today, Tomorrow*. 2025, No. 2(34), pp. 217-226. — EDN SWFABV.

investigative practice. The task is to ensure that this adaptation is deliberate and methodologically sound¹.

Another important aspect of theoretical integration is the formation of the concept of ‘forensic thinking.’ In contemporary discourse, it is regarded as a distinct type of professional thinking, shaped through experience and the specific methods employed by the investigator. Although in psychology thinking is understood as a universal cognitive process, forensic science justifiably emphasizes its professional specificity associated with solving unique cognitive tasks — reconstructing past events from their traces, overcoming resistance, and evaluating evidence in its entirety. The search for compromise terminological solutions, such as ‘forensic thinking strategies,’ enables the retention of forensic science developments while avoiding conflict with psychological science².

The practical implementation of the interdisciplinary approach is most clearly manifested in specific investigative actions, each of which possesses its own psychological structure and requires specific tactical techniques.

In particular, interrogation is traditionally regarded as the investigative action most saturated with psychological content. The success of an interrogation largely depends on the investigator’s ability to establish psychological contact, recognize deception, and apply lawful psychological influence. As highlighted in modern studies, the issue of investigators’ unpreparedness for psychological influence by those being interrogated remains pressing. Resistance to investigation more frequently manifests as sophisticated psychological manipulations, demanding from the investigator not only intuition but also systematic knowledge of the psychological mechanisms involved in the formation of false statements. The investigator’s ability to work with various personality types, taking into account the age-related, social, and individual psychological characteristics of the interviewee, is of particular importance^{3,4}.

Crime scene examination, despite its apparent ‘technicality,’ also contains a profound psychological component. The psychology of perception, attention, and memory determines which environmental details will be noticed and recorded by the investigator, and which may remain outside their field of vision. Working with space requires advanced spatial thinking and the ability to reconstruct an event from its material traces. Moreover, crime scene examination is often

¹ Shaevich A. A. *Ibid.*

² Shaevich A. A. *Ibid.*

³ Valkyria N. I. *Op. cit.*

⁴ Zemlyakov A. V. Tactics for detecting false testimony during interrogation // *Bulletin of the Institute of Law of Bashkir State University*. 2025. Vol. 8, No. 4(28), pp. 298-308. DOI: 10.33184/vest-law-bsu-2025.28.27.

accompanied by high emotional tension, which requires the investigator to possess self-regulation skills.

A search constitutes an investigative action with a distinctly exploratory character, where the psychological analysis of the behavior of the person being searched can provide results no less valuable than technical search methods. Observing reactions, predicting possible hiding places based on an understanding of human psychology, and choosing the right moment to initiate a search — all of these require the investigator to have a profound understanding of human behavior. As emphasized in the literature, the necessity of applying knowledge from psychology in criminal investigations has never been disputed; however, many issues remain undeservedly overlooked. In particular, this pertains to the understanding of the motivation behind criminal behavior and the psychology of the participants in the process in their dynamics¹.

Psychological knowledge becomes practically significant for the investigator only when it is transformed into specific methods and techniques applicable in actual investigative situations. An analysis of contemporary practice allows for the identification of several such methods that have gained the most widespread application.

Observation is a fundamental method permeating all investigative activities. During the interrogation, observation makes it possible to record the interrogated person's non-verbal reactions — facial expressions, gestures, changes in voice — that may indicate tension or, conversely, spontaneity of response. During a search, observing the behavior of the person being searched often leads to the discovery of hiding places and reveals their interest in specific areas of the premises. However, as rightly noted in the literature, an investigator relying solely on everyday psychology is not always capable of adequately interpreting observed phenomena, which necessitates the deliberate development of professional observation skills².

Reflection represents the investigator's ability to be aware of their own mental processes and states, as well as to anticipate the line of thought and actions of the opposing party. Reflexive management, which involves the investigator placing themselves in the position of the interrogated and anticipating their possible tactical moves, is one of the key elements of a successful interrogation under conditions of investigative resistance. Reflection acquires particular importance when working with organized criminal groups, where it is necessary to predict the behavior of not one, but several interconnected individuals.

¹ Shinkaruk V. V., Solovyova N. A. New Facets of an Old Problem: Psychology in the Service of Investigation // *Forensic Expert*. 2024, No. 4, pp. 28-30. DOI: 10.18572/2072-442X-2024-4-28-30.

² Shinkaruk V. V., Solovyova N. A. *Op. cit.*

Empathy, as the ability to understand the emotional state of another person, may seem an unexpected tool in an investigator's arsenal. However, it is precisely empathy that enables the establishment of psychological contact, which is crucial for obtaining truthful testimony. Understanding the victim's fear, the suspect's despair, and the witness's confusion provides the investigator with a key to selecting the appropriate communication strategy. This concerns not sympathy, but rather understanding that allows communication to be constructed as effectively as possible.

Psycholinguistic analysis of speech is becoming increasingly important in circumstances where the written and oral statements of participants acquire evidentiary value. Analysis of speech constructions, logical contradictions, and stylistic features enables the detection of signs of prepared testimony and memorized text, which may indicate self-incrimination or collusion. This method acquires particular significance in the analysis of correspondence in messaging applications, where speech characteristics can aid in identifying the message author¹.

Despite the evident demand for psychological knowledge in investigative activities, the professional training system for lawyers does not always adequately address these needs. Traditionally, psychology is taught in law schools as a general theoretical discipline, only weakly connected to students' future professional practice. A graduate who has studied general psychology often lacks an understanding of how to apply this knowledge in specific investigative scenarios.

Analysis of contemporary research indicates that the problem of investigators' unpreparedness for psychological interaction with participants in the process, as well as for recognizing and neutralizing psychological manipulations, remains acute. This is especially pertinent to work with minors, individuals with mental disorders, and victims of violence — categories requiring a specialized psychological approach².

It appears that the solution to this problem lies in revising the content of psychological training for legal professionals. A transition is necessary from abstract theory to practice-oriented training, where psychological knowledge is taught not in isolation but within the context of specific investigative situations. The simulation of interrogations with analysis of psychological aspects, training in observation and reflection, and case studies involving psychologists — all of these should become an integral part of the professional training of future investigators.

In conclusion of the conducted research, a number of key findings can be formulated.

The integration of psychological knowledge into forensic tactics has ceased to be a subject of theoretical debate and has become an urgent necessity in investigative practice. Psychological phenomena — from establishing contact to lie

¹ Zemlyakov A. V. Op. cit.

² Valkyria N. I. Op. cit.

detection — are present in every investigative action, and ignoring them or relying on everyday intuition cannot ensure the required level of investigative effectiveness.

The theoretical foundation of this integration is the conscious and methodologically validated adaptation of psychological concepts to the tasks of forensic science. It is fundamentally important that the borrowing of psychological terms does not lead to their distortion, and that their use in forensic science is accompanied by an understanding of their original psychological meaning.

Further research in this area should focus on developing specific methodologies for applying psychological knowledge in individual investigative procedures, creating training programs that integrate psychological and forensic components, as well as studying international experience in interdisciplinary cooperation within law enforcement.

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DIGITAL WATERMARKS AS AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF PROTECTING INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY OBJECTS

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Abstract. *In the context of the rapid digitalization of social relations, the improvement of mechanisms for protecting intellectual property has become especially relevant. This article examines digital watermarks as an innovative method for protecting intellectual property objects on the Internet, outlines the types of digital watermarks, and explores the features of their application in the digital environment. The legal nature of digital watermarks is examined, along with their relation to copyright information and technical protection measures provided by the civil legislation of the Russian Federation. Based on the analysis of current judicial practice, the characteristics of judicial assessment of digital watermarks and the evidential value of information embedded in protected works in disputes concerning violations of exclusive rights are examined.*

Keywords: *intellectual property, digital watermark, copyright, technical protection measures, copyright information, digital environment.*

The development of digital technologies and the expansion of the circulation of intangible assets have significantly altered the methods of creating, distributing, and utilizing intellectual property results. Today, works of science, literature, and art, computer programs, audiovisual objects, and other protected results can be reproduced and transmitted to an unlimited number of recipients without loss of original quality and with minimal costs for the distributor. The diversity of digital copyright objects necessitates the use of universal technological tools capable of ensuring their identification and protection regardless of the specific form of expression [1, C. 306]. Traditional legal means of protection, enshrined in the provisions of Part Four of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, are primarily aimed at suppressing already committed violations and restoring infringed rights; however, the specific nature of the digital environment, characterized by the rapid dissemination of information and the complexity of establishing the original source

of placement, requires resorting to innovative methods capable of providing preventive protection for intellectual property objects.

One of the most common methods for protecting intellectual property results on the Internet is the use of digital watermarks. Their application allows the inclusion of additional information containing details about the author, rights holder, or terms of use of the work into the structure of the digital object [2, C. 186]. The designation of this technology stems from its functional similarity to traditional watermarks used in the production of banknotes and securities, as protection in the digital environment is also implemented through the embedding of identifying information directly into the structure of the object [3].

Depending on the method of application, digital watermarks are classified as visible or invisible [4, C. 214]. A visible watermark is a graphic or textual element embedded on an image, document page, or other digital object, which is perceptible to the user during standard viewing. Its primary purpose is to indicate the ownership of the work by a particular individual and to warn against unauthorized use [5, C. 138]. A hidden digital watermark is embedded into the file structure in such a way that it remains undetectable during normal perception of the work, yet can be extracted using specialized technical means. Unlike a visible mark, such a watermark does not alter the visual or auditory characteristics of the work and preserves its consumer properties [6, C. 284].

Modern practice employs numerous methods for embedding digital watermarks, varying according to the type of intellectual property result (graphic images, audio files, video recordings, software products), the technical characteristics of the digital object, as well as the rights holder's objectives [7]. The choice of a specific method is determined by the required level of preservation of the digital watermark during file processing, its invisibility to the user, and the possibility of subsequent information extraction. Practice shows that the highest level of protection is achieved by combining several methods, for example, the simultaneous use of a visible mark and a hidden digital watermark [8]. In this case, the visible element performs a preventive function, whereas the hidden digital watermark provides the capability for subsequent identification of the author.

For example, the author of a photographic work may publish the image online with their name as a visible graphic designation, and also embed a hidden digital watermark within the file structure containing information about the creation date and identification data of the rights holder. Subsequently, if a third party copies the image, removes the visible signature, and uploads the file to another platform under their own name, the author has the right to present the original file and the results of technical expertise confirming the presence of the embedded information [9]. A hidden digital watermark that remains intact despite changes in image size or formatting can serve as additional evidence of the work's original author. Even

in cases of partial damage or alteration of the embedded information, the results of technical expertise may indicate interference with the file's structure and suggest improper use thereof [10]. A similar mechanism can be applied to musical works, textual documents, or software products.

Thus, a digital watermark is a technological method of embedding unique identifying information into a digital object, enabling the establishment of the author, confirming the ownership of the work by a specific right holder, as well as detecting instances of its subsequent use in the digital environment [11]. The main characteristics of digital watermarks include resistance to file alterations such as format changes, compression, scaling, or other processing; imperceptibility to the user; reliable extraction of the embedded information; and protection against unauthorized removal or modification [12, C. 114].

A digital watermark should be distinguished from copyright information established in Article 1300 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation. Such information refers to data identifying the work, the author, or other right holder, as well as data on the terms of use of the work, placed on the original or a copy of the work, attached to it, or appearing in connection with its disclosure to the public. Copyright information typically exists in the form of file metadata or accompanies the work as textual or graphic designations. The law explicitly prohibits the removal or alteration of such information without the consent of the rights holder, as well as the use of the work conditioned on such removal or alteration.

Unlike copyright information, a digital watermark is embedded directly into the structure of a digital object and becomes part of its technical organization. It does not exist as a separate informational block that can be easily removed by standard software tools without altering the file itself. When considering the legal consequences of intentional removal or modification of a digital watermark, it should be noted that if such actions are taken with the intent of subsequent unlawful use of the work, they may be regarded as a separate violation connected to the circumvention of technical protection measures. At the same time, even in the absence of subsequent dissemination of the work, the very fact of removing embedded identifying information may indicate interference with the structure of the digital object with the intent to conceal the file's source of origin.

Thus, the use of a digital watermark is aimed at securing the exclusive right and confirming the attribution of the work to a specific author or other right holder. By its functional purpose, a digital watermark can be classified among the technical means of protection provided for in Art. 1299 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, understood as any technologies, devices, or their components intended to prevent or restrict actions not authorized by the right holder. In a broader context, technical protection measures also include Digital Rights Management (DRM) systems designed to restrict access to works and control their copying and distribution [13,

P. 18]. These technologies are widely employed by streaming services and digital content distribution platforms such as Netflix, Amazon, and Apple Music to ensure control over the playback and distribution of works in electronic form [14, P. 2709]. Unlike digital rights management systems (DRM), a digital watermark typically does not restrict the use of the work, impede access to it, or preclude the possibility of copying it. However, the use of a digital watermark creates a mechanism for identifying a digital object, enables confirmation of exclusive right ownership, establishes the source of distribution, and detects any interference with the file structure.

Thus, a digital watermark performs identification and evidentiary functions. When considering disputes concerning the violation of exclusive rights, the presence of identifying information in a digital object may aid in confirming authorship or establishing the fact of unauthorized use of the work. In this respect, digital watermarks align with the provisions of Art. 1299 of the Civil Code of the Russian Federation, which establishes the legal regime for technical protection measures and prohibits their circumvention.

It is important to note that a digital watermark does not have independent evidentiary value and must be evaluated by the court in conjunction with other evidence in the case. Information embedded in a digital object may indicate the work's affiliation to a specific copyright holder, as well as attest to interference with the file structure, including attempts to remove or alter protective elements. The significance of such information is determined by considering the circumstances of the case and the nature of the parties' objections. For example, in the ruling of the Thirteenth Arbitration Appellate Court in case No. A56-113749/2023 [15], the court assessed the publication of the work identifying the author's name and bearing a watermark, together with the protocol from the 'DIGITAL EYE' system, which confirmed the date of the initial publication, and the protocol from the 'WEBJUSTICE' system, which recorded the defendant's infringement. The conclusion regarding the existence of infringement was made based on the examination of all submitted evidence.

Judicial practice also pays particular attention to the assessment of the reliability of information extracted from the digital watermark. The court considers not only the fact of the presence of embedded information but also other evidence confirming the ownership of the work by a specific rights holder, as well as the circumstances of its use. Thus, in the ruling of the Ninth Arbitration Appellate Court in case No. A40-189445/23 [16], the plaintiff's ownership of the photographic work was confirmed by a combination of evidence: the presence of the digital watermark, publication indicating the author's name, a protocol of automated information inspection generated by the 'DIGITAL EYE' system, as well as an expert report issued by the South Ural Chamber of Commerce and Industry. Upon evaluating the submitted materials in their interrelation, the court concluded that the infringement of exclusive rights had been established.

Thus, analysis of judicial practice allows us to conclude that, to date, digital watermarks are among the most effective innovative methods for protecting intellectual property results in the digital environment. Their universal nature, applicability to various types of digital objects, and the variety of implementation methods depending on the set objectives provide extensive opportunities for the practical application of this mechanism.

Today, the results of intellectual activity are increasingly created and used in electronic form; accordingly, the conditions of their circulation and the nature of possible infringements are changing. Traditional legal means of protection, primarily aimed at restoring violated rights, do not always allow timely responses to digital methods of unlawful use of works, which necessitates resorting to technological protection tools. Digital watermarks, which are a method of embedding identifying information about the work and its rights holder into a digital object, perform both preventive and evidential functions, thereby contributing to more effective protection of exclusive rights in the context of digitalization.

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THE CRIMINAL LAW ASPECT OF HUMAN LIFE

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the problem of defining the beginning of human life. The article examines the criteria for live birth. The periods marking the beginning of life during physiological and pathological labor, cesarean section, and abortion in late pregnancy for social indications are analyzed in detail. The criminal law significance of the beginning of life for the classification of offenses is analyzed.*

Keywords: *life, beginning of life, determination of the moment of the beginning of life, criteria of live birth, criminal law aspect.*

The issue of determining the moment of the beginning of human life within the framework of criminal law remains a matter of debate. Despite a substantial number of published works, including scientific studies and dissertations, no definitive resolution has yet been reached. Differences in the interpretation of the term ‘beginning of life’ result in difficulties in classifying crimes such as murder, infanticide, as well as cases of causing death through negligence or recklessness.

E. F. Pobegailo defines the beginning of human life as commencing with the onset of the birth process. [1, pp. 96-98]. N. K. Semerнева defines the beginning of human life from the moment the birth process starts. She defines this process as beginning from the emergence of the child’s head passing through the maternal womb. [2, p. 156]. A. N. Krasikov identifies medical criteria for determining the beginning of life of a newborn child. [3, p. 103]. A. N. Popov, drawing on the views of biologists and other researchers, holds that the moment of the origin of life should be considered as the moment of fusion of the male and female gametes, that is, the time of creation of the ‘unique genetic material.’ [4, p. 68]. Scholarly opinions differ.

Perhaps the most precise definition is as follows: life is a biological state of a living being characterized by the normal functioning of all organs and structures, provided that the anatomical integrity of the organism is preserved. Functional integrity of the organism refers to its ability to function (act, live) autonomously (independently).

Consequently, human birth can be regarded as the initial state of the newborn's vital activity, during which the functioning of all organs and systems of the organism is ensured while preserving the organism's functional capabilities. Functional integrity is understood as the ability of an organism to independently perform vital functions.

Regarding Russian criminal law, the prevailing view holds that legal protection of life begins precisely when, during the birth process, any part of the infant's body emerges from the mother's womb. Which part? The head, legs, arms, pelvis, or buttocks? Do these body parts belong to a living or a deceased person? At a specific stage of labor:

Firstly, it is impossible to determine whether the child will be born alive or dead;

Secondly, during labor, the fetus being delivered by the woman cannot be regarded as alive due to the absence of signs of a living organism.

Undoubtedly, according to the traditional understanding, the fetus exists in a viable state within the body of its mother. However, the connection between the fetus and the maternal body is maintained via the placenta, which provides a complete supply of the necessary substances and conditions for the fetus's growth. The developing organism during its period in the womb constitutes an inseparable unity with the female organism. This is confirmed by contemporary medical studies conducted throughout the formation and growth of the fetus in the uterine cavity, after which the fetus remains in the uterine cavity, continuing to receive all that is necessary precisely through placental circulation.

Based on the aforementioned arguments, it becomes evident that the medical understanding of the moment of the beginning of human life significantly differs from the criminal law perspective. In making decisions concerning the initial stage of human existence, it is important to consider various factors — the normal course of delivery, pathological conditions of pregnancy, surgical interventions such as cesarean section, and pregnancy termination for social reasons (provided the fetus is born alive). This comprehensive approach will resolve existing difficulties in establishing the facts of the onset of life and ensure objectivity in the legal assessment of criminal acts.

Medical practice defines the autonomous functioning of the human body by cardiac activity and the external process of gas exchange through the lungs. The birth of a live fetus is characterized by the appearance of signs of life, among which the key is the initiation of external respiration by the lungs.

Accordingly, medical science marks the initial stage of human life at the moment when independent organ functioning begins, characterized by metabolic processes typical of a mature organism. From this, it follows that the protection of the right to life of an individual applies solely to a viable organism capable of existing independently outside the maternal body. This condition occurs only after the natural delivery of the child following spontaneous labor, abnormal childbirth situations,

surgical intervention (cesarean section), or medically necessary termination of pregnancy for socially significant reasons.

Natural childbirth is the process by which a baby is born without complications arising in the mother or the fetus. This process concludes with the birth of a healthy newborn, free from functional impairments, biological deficiencies, or anatomical defects. The newborn displays reflexes characteristic of the corresponding stage of intrauterine development, actively moves its arms and legs, vocalizes loudly, and independently maintains adequate breathing.

Normal, physiological childbirth is sometimes accompanied by complications during the labor process affecting both the mother and the infant — such as weak contractions, fetal hypoxia, impaired coordination of uterine contractions, precipitous labor, and other disorders. Such labor leads to the birth of a fetus with physical injuries caused by the specific condition of the organism or the anatomical structure of the newborn — of a physiological nature. Newborns are often unable to independently take their first inhalation immediately after birth. In such cases, resuscitation measures are carried out without delay. Nevertheless, regardless of the circumstances, the newborn makes a forced inhalation due to the application of specialized respiratory equipment — resuscitation breathing apparatus for artificial lung ventilation.

According to statistical data, between 1980 and 2016, physiological births resulting in the birth of a child with 9 points on the Apgar scale (normal) accounted for approximately 17% [5]. During the period from 2017 to 2023

There is also information that, according to statistics, 98% of full-term newborns receive only 7 points on the Apgar scale at 5 minutes of life [6]. These data are taken into account in obstetric care within maternity hospitals.

Therefore, it is possible to conclude that childbirth outside specialized medical institutions can provoke complications during the delivery process. Such circumstances are often due to personal reasons on the part of the woman (for example, lack of health insurance, insufficient funds, or unsatisfactory care in medical facilities). The birth of a newborn outside an obstetric facility may occur with injuries; neonatal asphyxia (complete absence of breathing) is also a frequent condition. If the infant is unable to breathe independently immediately after birth, the continuation of life becomes impossible.

In complicated deliveries, the birth of a child with injuries and signs of asphyxia without the professional support of a resuscitation physician or neonatology specialist further increases the risk of infant death due to the inability to take the first independent breath.

Based on the indicated circumstances, a forensic medical specialist, relying on the diagnostic criterion (the absence of air traces in the lungs of the newborn, which indicates live birth), will establish the diagnosis that the child was stillborn. However, in the case of a child born without external signs of live birth and the

administration of resuscitation measures using respiratory equipment, with unsuccessful resuscitation resulting in death, a situation arises involving the presence of an air mixture in the lungs.

This air mixture enters the lungs by means of pressure from the respiratory apparatus and creates conditions for an apparent, essentially false test for the presence of air in the lung specimen, which is used to determine the test of live birth. In such cases, a forensic medical expert or pathologist issues a conclusion of live birth, which, in essence, is not valid and does not correspond to resuscitation measures.

Thus, the beginning of life is considered not to be the mere fact of birth, which is present in all cases, but specifically the moment when the child takes the first independent or forced breath, which initiates the functioning of all the newborn's organs and systems, ensuring the transition of the neonate to autonomous biological existence through the activation of the infant's biochemical mechanisms of vital activity (such as the Krebs cycle).

When a child is delivered by cesarean section, breathing does not begin immediately, since as long as the umbilical cord remains unclamped, oxygenated blood continues to flow from the placenta. Occasionally, the newborn requires assistance from a resuscitation physician who performs forced inhalation, thereby initiating the functioning of all vital systems of the newborn and enabling the infant to begin breathing independently.

In this particular case, the starting point for the commencement of life activity is also the newborn's first independent breath. If a resuscitation specialist is unable to provide artificial respiration, for example, due to congenital anomalies or pathologies, this is considered a stillbirth. However, the question arises: why are doctors not held criminally liable for the death of the child, given that the entire delivery process involves the emergence of individual parts of the baby's body externally?

Why is the conduct of medical personnel in such situations neither questioned nor subjected to investigative scrutiny? After all, only a living newborn can be deprived of life. It is impossible to cause the death of a fetus that is inherently incapable of independent and autonomous existence.

In cases of late-term pregnancy termination for social reasons, complications may arise that result in the birth of a live fetus. Paradoxically, legally, such infants do not acquire the status of newborns, despite numerous cases of successful survival of children born at 23-25 weeks of gestation and weighing less than one kilogram. After such an abortion, the medical staff effectively refuse to provide medical care to the live aborted fetus, resulting in its death.

The conduct of medical personnel, upon detailed legal examination, may be qualified either as murder due to the physician's passive behavior (inaction) or as a refusal to provide necessary medical care to the patient, depending on the specific circumstances of the case.

However, such offenses are possible only with respect to the newborn immediately after birth. As for the fetus born alive as a result of an improperly performed abortion procedure for medical or social reasons, such a fetus does not acquire the status of a newborn child. According to current legislation, a live fetus, which in fact represents a newborn, is classified only as a consequence of the unsuccessful completion of an artificially induced termination of pregnancy at a late stage of gestation. Medical documentation in this case does not record the live birth of a viable fetus. [7] If a fetus capable of independent existence is left without proper medical care, it inevitably dies, while the mechanisms of criminal law protection of life remain unimplemented.

The issue of accurately qualifying such a case remains a subject of debate among legal and medical professionals.

Based on the above analysis, it is reasonable to assert that criminal law protection of an infant's life should commence from the moment independent vital activity of the human organism arises outside the mother's body, including the full autonomous functioning of all internal organs and systems, rather than being limited to recording the onset of labor or certain stages of delivery.

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UDC 31

ABORTION AS A MEDICAL AND SOCIAL PROBLEM

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Abstract: *Abortion is an actual problem in the modern healthcare. The scale of this phenomenon in our country is incomparable with other countries of the world. Abortion is 50% of unfulfilled pregnancies. Termination of pregnancy causes damage to the reproductive system with all the following consequences.*

Keywords: *abortion, pregnancy, birth rate, statistics, demography*

Recently, abortion has become one of the most frequently discussed topics. In the Russian Federation, termination of pregnancy is the main method of birth control. According to statistics, about 1,700,000 abortions are performed annually in our country, which is 3 times higher than in European countries [1]. According to lexicographical sources, abortion (from Latin. abortion — “miscarriage”) is called “artificial termination of pregnancy, accompanied by (or caused by) the destruction of the embryo or the death of the fetus, unable to exist independently (unlike premature birth)” [2].

Today, the problem of artificial termination of pregnancy in pregnant women, especially in adolescents, is urgent. In Russia, more than 40,000 teenage girls under the age of 18 terminate their first pregnancy every year. The reasons for this phenomenon include early sexual activity, lack of knowledge about contraception,

immature thinking, and a lack of counseling services available to young people. It is also important to consider that many modern women prefer to delay having children until they are in their 30s or older. They prioritize building their careers and achieving financial independence. As a result, many women have had multiple abortions by the time they reach their 30s or 35s.

A careless attitude towards the procedure itself and its complications is the main cause of reproductive health disorders in women. Among the early complications, inflammatory diseases of the female reproductive organs are the most common. Among the later complications of abortion, the most frequent are endometritis, myometritis, perimetritis, adnexitis, menstrual cycle disorders, spontaneous miscarriages, premature births, and infertility. The frequency of complications depends on the gestational age. The statistics on complications from abortions in Russia are as follows:

- 8 weeks or less — the frequency of complications is less than 1 %;
- 8-12 weeks — 1.5-2 %;
- 12-13 weeks — 3-6 %;
- second trimester — up to 50 % or more.

In the Astrakhan region, an average of 6,291 abortions are performed annually, with an average of 3,457 abortions performed in rural areas and 2,834 abortions performed in the city. Every year, the proportion of women of fertile age decreases, and every second Astrakhan woman under the age of 28 has at least two abortions in her medical history. 50.0% of abortions are performed on women aged 18-29, and up to 10.0% of abortions are performed on first pregnancies. One in three women experience complications from abortions, and they are three times more common in first-time mothers. Complications include uterine perforations (0.13-0.7%), cervical injuries (0.3-2.2%), and hypotonic bleeding (1.5%). In recent years, iatrogenic complications related to anesthesia (drug overdose, etc.), allergic reactions, vascular embolism, blood transfusions, and organ damage have become more common. The frequency of uterine perforation increases by 1.4 times for every 2 weeks of subsequent pregnancy. In non-pregnant women, the risk of uterine perforation after an abortion increases by 3 times.

The late 20th century, specifically the 1990s, saw Russia's efforts to address reproductive health, family planning, and abortion prevention through the federal targeted programs "Family Planning" and "Safe Motherhood," which primarily focused on abortion prevention. For example, contraceptives were purchased to provide them free of charge to teenagers and people from social risk groups (low-income groups, disabled people, etc.). At the same time, the discussion of the abortion issue moved into the sphere of ethical and moral issues ("abortion as infanticide" etc.), there were proposals to ban abortion. An accompanying result of these discussions was a reduction in the indications for abortion on medical

and social grounds. Thus, the widespread promotion of safe sex and new family planning methods was met with mixed reactions from the Russian population [1].

It should also be noted that in 1996, the limit for artificial abortion was lowered to 22 weeks, and social indicators such as unemployment, income below the subsistence level, lack of housing, refugee or displaced status, and even unmarried status were added to the list of social indications [4].

Currently, the legal basis for medical activities related to family planning and regulation of human reproductive function is defined by Article 36 of the Fundamentals of the Russian Federation's Legislation on the Health of Citizens (dated July 22, 1993). At the present stage, the activities of almost all obstetric and gynecological services and specially established family planning and reproduction centers are aimed at protecting reproductive health and preventing abortions.

Thus, it was in the 20th century that abortions, which had been illegal and severely punished for centuries, were legalized and elevated to the level of family planning methods. At the same time, the moral assessment of the procedure for artificial termination of pregnancy contributed to the emergence of alternative means of birth control in the second half of the 20th century and the change in the cultural traditions of the global community. It should also be noted that at the current stage of medical development, artificial termination of pregnancy is more common than ever before in previous history.

These circumstances determine the relevance of the problem and can serve as a basis for conducting research.

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IMPROVING THE ACCURACY OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOAL (SDG) DATA THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING-BASED IMPUTATION OF MISSING INDICATORS

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Abstract. *Since the adoption of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the United Nations in 2015, persistent gaps in indicator data have limited the reliability of cross-country comparisons. This study addresses the problem of missing SDG values using a machine learning-based imputation approach. Relying on the “Sustainable Development Data” dataset (2015-2022), four goals with substantial missingness were identified, focusing on Goal 14 (Life Below Water) as the primary target.*

An Elastic Net regression model with cross-validation is applied to predict missing values. The best-performing specification demonstrates high predictive accuracy ($R^2 > 0.97$), strong generalization, and minimal overfitting. Results show that machine learning effectively captures structural relationships among SDG indicators and outperforms simple mean-based imputation in preserving data patterns.

The findings confirm that ML-based imputation is a scalable and statistically robust tool for addressing SDG data gaps. However, predicted values should be used cautiously in policy or ESG reporting contexts.

Key words: *Sustainable Development Goals; SDGs; machine learning; Elastic Net Model; data imputation; sustainable development monitoring.*

Introduction

Since the introduction of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals by the United Nations in 2015 (‘THE 17 GOALS | Sustainable Development’ 2025), the concepts and metrics of their measuring have attracted the attention of both policymakers and

business leaders. However, despite the growing importance of SDG monitoring, data availability and consistency remain under major challenges.

Many countries lack complete or reliable data for some indicators which makes global comparisons and progress assessments unclear and incomplete. Data gaps undermine the accuracy of evaluations and can distort the perception of how effectively countries are moving towards the goals. In order to resolve the issue, we are turning to the methods of machine learning and employing regularised regression method for imputing the data in NA cells.

Respectively, the RQ is *“How can a machine learning model identify and deal with the missing SDG indicators across countries to accurately impute the missing values?”*

The goal is to use ML for imputing the missing values and analyse the model’s predictive capability and generalisability. For the sake of addressing the goal and question, we are analysing the dataset “Sustainable Development Data” from 2015 to 2022 (‘Sustainable Development Data’ 2023). In conclusion we mention the limits of the approach and potential area for further investigations on the topic.

Literature Review

The section delves into the problem of missing values in the studies and reports on the topic of SDGs. The time frame for the literature search was from 2020: by that year the big number of reports were released and the problem had gained its relevance, and this way we are able to trace the up-to-date trends within a five-year threshold typical for social sciences.

The problem of missing values is fundamental for the scientific field on the topic: in many cases, especially for certain indicators or regions, data simply do not exist (Lyytimäki et al. 2023). For example, in the UN reports 68% of environment-related SDG indicators lack data and only 33% of gender-related indicators in OECD countries have available data, reflecting emerging NAs as a structural problem (Nilashi et al. 2023). As noted, the reason for it is the large number of indicators and the associated cost of monitoring which have led to calls for streamlining (Kim 2023).

The main goals where there is an observable trend for missing data are the ones which are either socially disturbing like goals 4 — education quality and 5 — gender equality (Saini et al. 2022; Delprato 2024; Longlands et al. 2024) or difficult to measure like in case of climate-related, goals especially for 14 — life under water or others like 6 — water quality (Lothian and Haas 2024; Rodríguez et al. 2021). The problem is associated with heterogeneous data sources and long-term measurements. Simultaneously, the data missing may depend not only on the goal but also on the region where the information is collected and processed. For example, North Africa (Alharbi et al. 2021) and Latin America and the Caribbean (Vera et al. 2024) are prone to show the biggest numbers of missing values in the UN reports. These findings support the arguments about the cost of monitoring.

In the statistical approach, there is a categorisation of missing values and their perception as well as methods to deal with them: MCAR (missing completely at random), MAR (missing at random) and MNAR (missing not at random) (Emmanuel et al. 2021). Since, as we have understood earlier, the problem of missing values in SDGs reports is structural, it is in the sphere of MNAR, which in return, makes handling these missing data very difficult or even impossible (Emmanuel et al. 2021). To address the issue of data incompleteness, researchers have turned to computational and statistical innovations that in recent years the ML has become. For example, Yeh et al. (2021) are eager to monitor the data by machine learning and Chenary et al. (2024) predict the overall achievement of the goals by 2030. However, there is no particular work on how to apply the concrete ML tools to the missing data on SDGs, so we address this gap by asking: “*How can a machine learning model identify and deal with the missing SDG indicators across countries to accurately impute the missing values?*”

Theoretical background and methodology

The section explores different methods of machine learning and its applicability to the goal of the presented study. We introduce a brief overview on the methods that are commonly used for dealing with the missing values, analyse the outlined methods and present one that is the best for our RQ, and finally, propose the variables for analysis.

It is evident from the data that ML models have gained substantial recognition among the scholars when it comes to dealing with the missing values in quantitative data. As studied by Downing, the manual imputations do not show the same effectiveness as the ones shown by the ML model (Downing 2025).

The list of the most frequently used models includes *KNN*, *Random Forest*, *MICE*. Although all of them are equally widespread, there may be noted some methodological limitations that restrict their suitability for large, heterogeneous datasets such as those used in SDG monitoring. **KNN** imputation estimates missing values based on the similarity between observations based on the predefined distance but has a problem when dealing with the large datasets because it requires calculating distances between each observation and sometimes introduces false associations where they do not exist (Emmanuel et al. 2021).

Random Forest is one of the branches of the broader Decision Tree approach which focuses primarily on modelling non-linear relationships and interactions between predictors based on the majority vote or average over all trees (Emmanuel et al. 2021). However, the model may introduce bias when the proportion of missing data is large or unevenly distributed across variables or does not work properly with the continuous data.

Finally, MICE generates multiple plausible values for each missing observation by iteratively modelling each variable conditional on the others which allows for

uncertainty to be incorporated into the imputations (Samad et al. 2022). There is also an elaborated version — SuperMICE represents an integration of Super Learner into the standard syntax of MICE which works really well for extra linear regressions (random forests, neural networks, additive models, etc.) and reduces the risk of bias in the final data (Laqueur et al. 2022). In our case, unfortunately, there is a problem of limited volume and not enough experience for such a complex method.

Interestingly, the regularised regression is not appearing among the most employed methods. However, LASSO and ridge regression have gained particular attention due to their balance between interpretability and performance. They mitigate overfitting and allow for the inclusion of many correlated predictors, which is especially relevant for SDG datasets where indicators often overlap conceptually and statistically making it subject to the multicollinearity issue (Netti Herawati et al. 2024).

Thus, since we have a massive dataset where the main indicators may correlate, it was decided to opt for the regularised regression (Elastic Net because it balances coefficient shrinkage and variable selection, so it is good for SDGs). The analysis is focused on the data from 2015. The choice of this time frame is motivated by the appearance of the concepts and whole logic of measurements in 2015. In accordance with the literature review section, the target variable under investigation must be one of the 17 indicators, the focus should be on the one out of the scope of the most frequently having an issue of missing values (one of the goals 4, 5, 6, 13-15). They are expected to show NA cells due to the complexity in evaluation and measurement.

Nevertheless, after checking all the variables on missing values in practice it was found out that the most NAs appear for the goals 1, 4, 10, 14 striking that the theoretical assumption only partially meets the empirical truth in goals 4 and 14. Ultimately, we have chosen the **14th goal (Life below water)** because it simultaneously matches the theoretical assumption and shows the maximum number of missing values.

Empirical part

The empirical analysis begins with the reading of the SDG index dataset from 2000 to 2022. To focus on the most recent period, the dataset is filtered to remain only observations from 2015 to 2022. As a result, we have 1440 observations and 20 variables. The first column, containing country codes, is intentionally excluded to facilitate analysis using full country names.

The next step involves identifying missing data. NA is marked as 0 in this dataset. The following function reveals 621 NA across the goal score variables. The variable types: ‘country’ as a character string, ‘year’ as an integer and all score variables as numeric. Summary statistics show that some goals exhibit significant skewness. For instance, ‘goal_10_score’ and ‘goal_14_score’ show zeros, suggesting systemic reporting gaps for these specific indicators.

A histogram reveals that this score is not normally distributed. Instead, it exhibits a distinct bimodal pattern with two prominent peaks (~50 and ~80). The distribution

is asymmetric, not bell-shaped symmetry characteristic of a normal distribution. Furthermore, a noticeable dip in frequency occurs in the range of 65 to 70. The tails of the distribution don't show the gradual tapering expected under normality, confirming its non-normal nature.

In total, we have 180 unique country's names. Only four goals exhibit any missing values: goal 1, goal 4, goal 10, goal 14. This finding significantly narrows the focus of the machine learning task from imputing all 17 goals to predicting only these four specific, incomplete indicators.

Next, we exclude regional organizations and groups to ensure the analysis focuses exclusively on individual sovereign states and territories. This filtering step retains only data for 166 countries.

A correlation matrix was constructed for all goal score variables, excluding the composite 'sdg_index_score'. The analysis reveals that while most pairwise correlations are moderate, a significant positive correlation exists between 'goal_3_score' and 'goal_9_score' with a Pearson correlation coefficient — 0.8529343. Multicollinearity is present, because of the high degree of linear association. This implies that including both variables as predictors for another goal might lead to redundancy, potentially inflating standard errors and making coefficient estimates unstable. We recode zeros as NA for the four incomplete goals identified earlier. To establish a training set composed exclusively of complete cases there is an applied complete-case filter.

As a result, we have 106 countries. To improve predictive performance, two categorical variables are engineered. First, a 'region' variable is created by mapping each country to one of six geographic regions. Any unclassified entity is labeled 'Other'. Second, 'sdg_level' variable is derived from the composite 'sdg_index_score', categorizing countries into 'High' (score > 75), 'Medium' (60-75) and 'Low' (<60).

Using a random seed for reproducibility, we split the data on the target variable — 80% (training), 20% (testing). As result, we have 678 observations for training and 170 for testing. To simulate realistic missing values under controlled conditions, artificial missing values are introduced in the test set for the same four goals previously identified as incomplete. 20% of the observed values for each of goals in are randomly replaced with NA, while the original values are preserved in created backup columns. It shows the ability to recover masked values, with particular emphasis on 'goal_14_score' — target value with the highest originally missing values.

We have seven recipes to target the imputation of 14 goal. Each recipe builds upon the previous by incorporating additional features. Recipe 1 applies: removal of '_original' columns, dummy encoding of categorical variables, normalization of numeric predictors and elimination of zero-variance features. Recipe 2 extends this by applying a Yeo-Johnson transformation to all numeric predictors to mitigate skewness and logarithmic transformation to the target variable, addressing its non-normal distribution. Recipe 3 introduces a correlation filter to remove

predictors with pairwise correlations exceeding 0.8. Recipe 4 introduces three thematic aggregates: ‘base_needs_mix’, ‘environmental_mix’, ‘economical_mix’ and ‘development_diff’. Also, it includes creating interpretable mixes of scores from related SDG goals and development difference metrics to capture higher-level development patterns that individual goals may miss.

Recipe 5 augments this with a binary indicator for high-performing countries, enabling the model to learn distinct patterns. Recipe 6 adds ‘poverty_education_mix’, ‘health_environment_mix’ and ‘development_range’. Recipe 7 incorporates data-quality indicators and includes ‘environmental_sustainability’ (six goals), ‘land_climate_mix’ and ‘urban_mix’. It also tightens the correlation threshold to 0.75, adds near-zero variance removal, applies a log transformation with handle potential zeros robustly and eliminates linear combinations among predictors to ensure numerical stability.

Next, we compare seven recipes using an Elastic Net regression model trained via 10-fold cross-validation. As a result: Recipe 2 emerges as the best for imputing ‘goal_14_score’ (lowest RMSE (0.01470420) and the highest R-squared value (0.9657938)). This recipe’s penalty parameter (alpha) — 1.0 and a near-zero lambda value is 1.228839e-05 — it shows a well-generalized model with no overfitting. In contrast, Recipe 7 performs poorly, exhibiting a high RMSE (0.07154402) and a low R-squared (0.1621519). Recipe 2 worked perfectly for countries it had seen before, but failed for new, unseen countries, so final analysis was done with help of classification mutations (‘region’, ‘sdg_level’).

To assess generalizability, Recipe 2 logic was applied to predict the other three goals with missing data. ‘goal_14_score’ achieved the best performance (RMSE = 0.01551462, R-squared = 0.9615865), validating its selection as the primary target. Then, we optimized the model on both training and test datasets. The selected model, built using Recipe 2, demonstrates exceptional predictive accuracy for ‘goal_14_score’. On the training set, it shows RMSE — 1.657736 and R-squared of 0.9787, indicating a near-perfect fit to the training data. Its performance on the test set remains robust (RMSE = 1.705092 and R-squared = 0.9720), signifying strong generalization capability. The small train-test gap in RMSE (0.0474) further confirms that the model is not overfitting. MAE = 1.2252 provides a more interpretable measure of average prediction error.

To assess the model’s broader applicability, its performance was evaluated across four indicators with missing values. The results reveal that while ‘goal_14_score’ is predicted with the highest precision (lowest test RMSE = 1.7777), the model also performs well for other goals. The high R-squared values (all above 0.96) confirm that the underlying feature strategy effectively captures the latent patterns.

Then, we showed the final demonstration. There are 34 artificial missing values created for demonstration. The Elastic Net model demonstrated theoretical

imputation capability with strong test performance ($MAE = 1$), but encountered generalization constraints with unseen countries. We implemented regional average imputation which efficiently resolved all missing data with negligible distributional alteration. This indicates that on average the predicted values deviate from the true values by less than 2% of the actual score.

The high correlation coefficient of 0.9916 between the actual and predicted values. 100% of the imputed values fall within a 5% margin of error and all predictions are within a 10%. The best prediction achieved an error only 0.013, while the worst case had an error = 3.115, which still represents a highly accurate estimate. This robust performance validates the efficacy of identifying and imputing missing indicators.

Then, we create 6 plots to illustrate results. Actual versus predicted values (Plot 1) demonstrates a strong positive linear relationship with most points clustering tightly around the 45 of perfect prediction, visually confirming the high R-squared (0.9916) reported in the model evaluation. The best predictions (Plot 2) are nearly perfect with errors as low as 0.013 for countries like Finland and Malta, while the worst predictions, such as for Madagascar (error = 3.1) and Indonesia (error = 2.4) still remain within an acceptable range given the scale of the scores.

Plot 1

An error analysis reveals that the model's accuracy is differently consistent across country groups. Plot 3 visualizes the mean percentage error from the evaluation by region and SDG performance level, showing that prediction accuracy was highest for high-performing countries in Africa (mean error 0.2%) on the test set and lowest for medium-performing countries in Europe (mean error 3.7%).

However, even the worst category exhibits a remarkably low mean error of just 3.7%, indicating robust generalizability.

Plot 2

Plot 3

Plot 4 shows top six SDG level combinations with the highest average percentage errors are visualized, revealing that ‘Europe — Medium’ performance countries experience the most significant prediction error at 3.7%, followed closely by ‘Latin America & Caribbean — Medium’ at 3.3%. This suggests that countries with medium SDG performance in these regions present a more challenging prediction problem, possibly due to greater heterogeneity in their development trajectories.

Plot 4

Plot 5 shows that ‘Latin America & Caribbean’ has the highest weighted average error across all SDG (3.1%). In contrast, ‘Africa’ demonstrates the lowest overall error (1.2%). Plot 6 illustrates that ‘Medium’ performers exhibit the highest weighted average error (2.1%), while ‘High’ performers have the lowest (1.1%). This pattern implies that the model performs best for countries at the extremes of the development spectrum (either very high or very low performers) and faces its greatest difficulty in predicting scores for countries in the middle, where development indicators may be less distinct and more variable.

Plot 5

Finally, we compare the initial dataset with the new one which we create in our code. The original dataset contained 320 missing values for 'goal_14_score', which were imputed using a two-step process: first, by substituting regional mean values, and second, by applying a global mean for any remaining gaps. This method successfully eliminated all missing data as confirmed by a final check that showed zero NA values across the four target goals.

Plot 6

Plot 7

A distributional analysis reveals that while the region-based approach preserves the general shape of the data, it introduces a slight downward bias. For ‘goal_14_score’, the mean decreased from 64.64 to 63.53, a difference of -1.11 , a corresponding reduction in standard deviation from 11.49 to 10.21. Plot 7 for ‘goal_14_score’ visually confirms: the red “After Imputation” curve is slightly higher and narrower than the black “Original” curve, particularly around the peak near 60-65, suggesting the imputed values are less variable and slightly lower on average.

Regionally, the analysis shows that the 320 imputed values for ‘goal_14_score’ were all assigned to the “Other”. This highlights a key limitation: the simple mean imputation cannot capture the nuanced, country-specific patterns that the machine learning model was designed to learn. While the region-based method provides a quick, interpretable solution, the machine learning model’s demonstrated by its ability to achieve a near-perfect correlation (0.9916) and minimal error on held-out test data. It confirms its effectiveness in identifying and predicting the complex, non-linear relationships between SDG indicators.

Conclusion

The empirical analysis demonstrates that machine learning can successfully impute missing SDG indicators across countries. Focusing on Goal 14, the indicator with the highest incidence of missing data, the model achieves **high predictive accuracy, strong generalization and minimal error** on both training and test sets. This confirms that the missing SDG values can be reliably predicted using the interdependencies among other SDG indicators. The best-performing preprocessing strategy includes basic transformations (logarithmic scaling of the target, Yeo-Johnson normalization of predictors), dummy encoding of categorical variables (region and SDG performance level), and removal of redundant or zero-variance features. Creating composite indices or interaction terms did not consistently improve performance, indicating that the core predictive signal resides in the original goal scores and their structural relationships. Error analysis reveals that the model performs most accurately for countries at the extremes of the development spectrum (very high or very low SDG performers) and slightly less so for medium performers, likely due to greater heterogeneity in their development profiles.

Nevertheless, prediction errors remain low across all regions and performance tiers, underscoring the robustness of the approach. In sum, the results affirm that ML can effectively address SDG data gaps by leveraging cross-goal correlations, offering a statistically sound and scalable alternative to traditional imputation methods. The strongest predictors are not isolated indicators but the collective pattern of a country’s performance across the full set of SDGs, highlighting the inherently interconnected nature of sustainable development.

The major limitation in our project is that although we have imputed the data and successfully fulfilled the goal, the ML model does not show the actual and true

number, so the bias in comparing may persist. In result, use of this data is applicable and possible for the research purposes when we need to witness the overall data; it should not be used in political reports or business records on ESG.

The further studies may be focused on employing the several ML methods for better findings. *For example*, additionally to the empirical part we have presented, it is possible to do the same steps in the realm of KNN (with partition of the initial dataset into several for better method working) and/or (Super-)MICE and then compare results with the regularised regression findings.

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PRAGMATIC APPROACH TO FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING

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Abstract. *The paper focuses on the importance of considering a pragmatic approach to teaching foreign languages. Such an approach provides students with a real multicultural communicative context and a highly motivated learning process. It leads to the development of a broad range of communicative competences. The Internet resources offer students a variety of interactive multi-format activities and various professionally oriented interactive tasks in a foreign language.*

Keywords: *Pragmatic approach, communicative competences, interactivity, interaction, Internet, resources, motivation, information processing, written/oral communication, foreign languages.*

In the constantly shifting paradigm of the modern world, the interest in foreign language learning is definitely increasing. The real-world context of communication with representatives of different cultures through interactive communication Internet tools is becoming an integral part of the current educational process. Methodologically competent use of Internet resources is a prerequisite for successful foreign language learning in today's environment.

According to the requirements of the State Educational Standard, the primary goal of language education for students at non-linguistic universities is to develop a broad range of information processing skills and multicultural communication skills in different forms and e-formats (oral and written on-line, off-line, etc.) in a foreign language.

Every society has certain cultural stereotypes, speech etiquette, and non-verbal communication tools developed within a specific linguistic community, which together form a set of communicative and pragmatic norms. In this regard, teaching pragmatic foreign-language business communication to future specialists in the professional field is relevant and timely, the ultimate goal of which is the development of intercultural professional and business communication competence [2].

When teaching a discipline such as a foreign language, interaction between students using Internet resources is not only a means to an end, but also one of the

main goals. The changing status of foreign languages as a means of communication and interpenetration within global cultural communities requires strengthening the pragmatic aspects of language learning, as well as a clear understanding and consideration of sociocultural factors. When teaching students, it is important not only to achieve high-quality results in mastering the skills and abilities of written foreign language communication, but also to find a real outlet for engaging with another culture and its speakers. The latter is the guiding principle for organizing intercultural communication in a foreign language [1].

Interactive resources and Internet technologies provide students with the conditions for intercultural communication in a foreign language through wide access to e-texts and multimedia information, as well as communication tools with immediate feedback from the recipient. This promotes students' general awareness of the world, improves their skills in interacting with multiple cultures, and develops the ability to establish cause-and-effect relationships between various sociocultural phenomena, leading to the overall socialization of the student's personality.

Such knowledge, abilities, skills, and competencies significantly influence the quality of oral and written interaction in a multicultural environment under the conditions as close as possible to the real language environment. This creates a communicative basis for the development of productive and reproductive skills at all stages of the communication process.

A comprehensive understanding of the role of Internet resources in the development of pragmatically significant intercultural communicative competencies is provided by analyzing the experience of using the educational capabilities of World Wide Web sites with their vast number of web pages and hyperlinks. The vast variety of site materials develop specific abilities, skills, and abilities in various types of foreign language speech activities. They can be effectively used in language practice classes (Web Links for Learners of English, CALL Lab, TESL), in online seminars (Computer Assisted Language Learning), and on forums (Foreign Language Teaching Forum). The web pages offer methodological developments and experience of their use, various types of information and an invitation to take part in the discussion of problems related to teaching methods, the organization of the educational process and its optimization.

For example, the "Virtual Reality" website is a collection of educational materials selected on a web server. The significance of this website is proved by the fact that students have a direct access to these materials without prior in-depth study and analysis. Students can adapt these materials, if necessary, to meet their own communicative needs and achieve their objectives. This is undoubtedly one of the positive and significant characteristics of the interactivity of online learning resources. In addition, online resources can completely remove any geographic boundaries, they can be successfully used in class as an online tool for concretizing

vague, obscure culturally-based concepts. Such sites help identify similarities and differences between native and target cultures, and also contribute to the enhancement of students' cultural knowledge and cross-cultural literacy.

Furthermore, websites like WILD-e can be useful not only for students in specialized fields but also for those at non-linguistic universities, both in their graduate and postgraduate programs, as the topics covered on this online resource correspond to the requirements for various levels of language proficiency. In addition to educational content, the website's organization allows for the exchange of written and oral information, which, in turn, can take the form of articles on professionally relevant topics.

Thus, the Internet can create a realistic environment where every student can simultaneously serve as a news agency employee, a participant in various conferences, and a consultant on issues of interest to other site members. Such activities require extensive reading and the use of online reference literature, alleviate fears of intercultural, multilingual communication, and promote the effectiveness of verbal communication.

Improving intercultural competence is facilitated by reading leading journalistic publishers from the target language countries, as well as by writing for magazines and newspapers in various genres — from letters to theses and commentaries on relevant topics. One such website is MEDIA LINKS, which offers links to numerous publications.

As for online newspapers or magazines as a learning resource, before recommending them to students as a source of "live" language and information material, it is necessary to study the interface of these resources, their structure and content, sections, and subsections. Electronic magazines and newspapers typically have a user-friendly interface, allowing for quick access to the desired sections and articles of interest. When advising students to use online resources, teachers should be aware of all the requirements for the content and format of written foreign language writing. It must be taken into account that an accepted article or a response to a written message will increase students' motivation and serve as evidence of successful learning.

The classification of articles (by topic and by continent) offered by newspaper publishers may be of interest. Feedback can be provided via the CONTACT US link. ABC News also provides both audio and video support for its publications. Readers can also engage in discussions on the topic in the CHAT sections. CNN World News also provides information in multiple languages and dual classification of articles. The internet also allows for the use of audio and video support.

Readers can also communicate with the editorial staff and with each other through the DISCUSSION section, which features a message board (MESSAGE BOARDS), a chat room (CHAT), and a contact page for the editorial board (FEEDBACK). In addition to the above, The New York Times offers its readers a study version of the newspaper with ready-made lesson plans.

Using information from numerous news agencies, students can work with newspaper materials on online websites. Studying global news outlets will give them the opportunity not only to become familiar with the contemporary language of magazines and newspapers, but also with the latest news in their professional field and area of expertise, providing them with a rich variety of authentic information. Furthermore, such material will serve as a basis for research activities within their coursework and theses and will introduce students to models (templates) for preparing oral and written representative statements.

The analysis of newspaper and magazine articles can take place in groups and address not only the content but also the presentation of the material. The diversity of topics and abundance of materials alleviates difficulties associated with the content of the statement. The advantage of this type of work is the full involvement of students, as well as the differentiation of tasks. To deepen their writing, reading, and speaking skills, students can be taught to create glossaries, which in turn will help them expand their vocabulary. To do this, students can be encouraged to create dictionary entries based on information they've read and processed. The online journal *Wings* is published as part of student discussion lists, where students from all over the world post their own written work on various topics, such as commentary on the latest news from various areas of life.

Thus, a general review and analysis of existing theoretical and practical results in the application of the pragmatic approach and the study of the intercultural communicative potential of Internet resources, as well as an analysis of our own experience in this area, allow us to draw several significant conclusions:

1. When teaching foreign languages with the help of interactive Internet resources the pragmatic approach contributes to developing intercultural communicative competence. It is important to use the following materials and tools:

1) communicative and informational Internet resources necessary for completing assignments and organizing active interaction online;

2) a textbook, reference manual, and educational texts reflecting the cultural, socio-cultural, linguistic, and other characteristics of the language being studied in a professionally oriented area;

3) a system of assignments and activities that combine cultural and linguistic aspects and coordinate various forms of work on the Internet depending on the learning goals, the teacher's tasks, and the preferences of the students.

2. The types of assignments may differ, firstly, in their emphasis on linguistic forms and functions; secondly, in their emphasis on historical, social, and art history information; thirdly, in their purpose, which may include, for example, planning and conducting a forum discussion to compare the positions of addressees from different cultures on the same issue within a specific profile and beyond.

3. Authentic Internet tools, as an effective means of simulating real-life communication situations, are used in the target language and present reality as it is, based on facts, without any commentary. On online sites, the interactive intercultural communication environment evokes in learners a need for “real language in a real context.”

4. In order to create a dynamic intercultural communication environment (which is the main principle when choosing Internet resources), it is proposed to use student discussion lists and the most popular sites among students that provide 1) informal communication (CHAT-SL), 2) formal communication (DISCUSS-SL), discussion of social and economic issues (BUSINESS-SL), discussion of current events (EVENT-SL), conversations on the topic of cinematography (MOVIE-SL), conversations about music (MUSIC-SL), etc.

5. The use of interactive Internet resources and access to authentic language material has demonstrated the positive impact of student collaboration in discussing how to accomplish current tasks, such as how to effectively and efficiently construct a dialogue with a foreign-language recipient on a forum or blog, or how to annotate the content of one’s own research paper for editing and evaluation by external “experts.” A sustained level of motivation for learning language and culture has also been observed, facilitating the creation of more specialized written and oral products in the target language.

Furthermore, information obtained and processed online remains useful and relevant to students’ daily needs. The used websites remain imprinted in students’ memories and are used by them even after completing assignments. Moreover, these and similar websites are used more quickly, economically, and efficiently, serving as a basis for achieving new learning goals.

Thus, the use of the pragmatic approach to foreign language teaching on the basis of Internet resources significantly optimizes and increases the effectiveness of the development of intercultural communication as one of the components of intercultural communicative competence. An important parameter is the fact that learners act simultaneously as consumers and providers of linguistic and cultural information. Furthermore, existing websites and information resources (such as THE YOUNG VOICES OF THE WORLD at <http://cnn.com/WORLD>) provide an open publishing platform where individuals can publish their research findings of any format and length, which become the subject of discussion in online forums and serve as linguistic and cultural material for subsequent research. It undoubtedly confirms the necessity and effectiveness of a pragmatic approach to foreign language teaching in the multilingual e-learning environment.

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THE INFLUENCE OF MONTESSORI'S DIDACTIC GAMES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE ABILITIES IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The authors examine the role and influence of M.'s didactic games Montessori's influence on the development of cognitive abilities in preschool children. The article analyzes the perspectives of domestic scholars regarding the effectiveness of Maria Montessori's original didactic games in fostering cognitive abilities in preschool children.*

Keywords: *technology, didactic games, cognitive abilities, preschool education.*

Cognitive ability is crucial for the intellectual development of children and acts as a factor in shaping their worldview and stimulating interest in knowledge. The Federal Educational Program for Preschool Education underscores the importance of developing this ability, including stimulating interests, fostering motivation for cognition, developing cognitive processes and consciousness, as well as supporting creative activity and imagination. The preschool period is considered optimal for the development of an individual's cognitive functions; however, this requires external support from society [6]. In accordance with regulatory documents, preschool educational institutions must create conditions for the development of children's cognitive abilities, encouraging their pursuit of knowledge and independence.

Abilities are unique psychological attributes of an individual that enable successful functioning in various domains, including practical, scientific, and creative activities. Within contemporary educational and psychological discourse, cognitive abilities are understood as the interaction of an individual's intellectual and sensory capacities,

activated during the process of cognition and the pursuit of novelty. They encompass the ability to form mental representations that reflect the characteristics of objects, their internal structure, the relationships among components, or key attributes and scenarios. These abilities are inherently linked to success in cognitive activity and represent individual characteristics oriented towards understanding the surrounding world. As M. Ya. Basov notes, they develop under the influence of specific conditions and factors, which include intellectual, sensory, and creative abilities [3].

Children's sensory abilities play a leading role in cognitive development and serve as the foundation for intellectual progress. At the age of three to four years, their active formation begins, leading preschool children to assimilate ideal models of object properties, expressed through language. By recognizing and systematizing differences between individual features, children learn to identify and apply standards, distinguish colors, language phenomena, and geometric shapes.

The child's intellect, its uniqueness, and depth of knowledge form the basis for the development of intellectual abilities. Preschool children displaying an increased need for novelty and cognitive challenges, along with high cognitive activity, often possess well-developed intellectual abilities. N. N. Avdeeva notes that such children exhibit intellectual activity closely linked to the capacity for self-regulation [1].

The unique intellectual qualities and mental abilities of a child begin to develop at early stages of development, shaping their learning and growth. Intellectual individuality is manifested in diverse ways: from solving practical problems to logical thinking and working with computers. Even at the preschool age, children exhibit pronounced interests in various fields of knowledge, which can change rapidly.

A child's creative abilities enable them to find unconventional solutions to problems related to imagination, as demonstrated in the creation of their own fairy tales, stories, games, drawings, and singing. Although a high creative potential alone does not guarantee future success, it contributes to the development of motivation, creative skills, and specialized abilities. A key element of creative potential is the pursuit of knowledge and exploration, which, according to N. V. Barannik [2], is associated with the child's cognitive motivation.

During the preschool years, children actively participate in various types of activities, including productive activities (such as drawing and modeling), play, and educational-cognitive tasks, which, according to S. V. Volkov's research, promote the development of cognitive abilities, as such integrated activities possess a practically productive character [6].

O. V. Veshnevitskaya [3] asserts that a child's creative and cognitive abilities develop through constant exploration and discoveries in daily practice.

Preschool age is a sensitive period for the development of various cognitive abilities, as defined by Maria Montessori, fostering the development of language, sensory, motor, and social skills. This development depends on the quality of

external support. Preschool programs starting 1-2 years before school are designed to develop skills such as reading, writing, and mathematics, as well as to teach social interaction within a group. However, focusing solely on these skills may neglect children's unique personal characteristics and emotional needs, as well as the significance of play in the preschool years, which can negatively impact motivation to learn and emotional development [7].

An alternative method to stimulate cognitive development involves creating a stimulating environment in which the child develops independently. According to M. Montessori, education, and development are viewed as instinctive processes requiring active knowledge-seeking through interaction with the environment and autonomy in choosing learning materials and activities. The educational environment is adapted to the child's sensitive developmental periods in accordance with M. Montessori's methodology. Within this approach, the educator serves as a mentor, supporting the child's inherent drive to explore the world.

In the Montessori system of preschool education (ages 3 to 7), an educational environment is created to enable each child to individually explore the world. Instruction is structured from simple to complex interactions with educational materials, considering the individuality, age, needs, and interests of the children. Independent work with educational materials facilitates the full development of the child's potential and the acquisition of key academic skills — writing, reading, and arithmetic — while maintaining their natural curiosity and a positive emotional state.

In the context of a mixed-age group, children undergo an extensive social development path over 3-4 years, transitioning from the status of a younger community member to a more mature role of an elder. During this process, they master five key developmental zones, each contributing to the development of various aspects of cognitive skills: these are the zones of speech, mathematics, sensory perception, spatial awareness, and practical life, which underlie cognitive development in the preschool years.

When a child enrolls late in preschool education using Montessori technology, the educator team ensures adaptation and social integration, although it cannot accelerate the child's progress through the educational zones. The research questions address the impact of the duration of study in a Montessori classroom on cognitive development and the developmental differences among children integrated into the Montessori environment at various stages. Play activity, which is central in the preschool years, stimulates brain activity and promotes the development of multiple skills. Educators support the child's individual developmental pathway, adhering to M. Montessori's principle: 'Help me do it myself.'

Between the ages of 3 and 6, according to Maria Montessori's concept, children actively pass through sensitive periods, developing speech, sensory perception, social, and motor skills. In a supportive environment comprising sensory materials, spaces for physical activity, and a peer group, by the end of this period, the child is

able to perceive the world as an adult does. The main tasks within the framework of work according to the Montessori method. Montessori include strengthening classification skills, expanding sensory experience, developing speech, and enhancing the perception of the world through the active use of all sensory organs.

M. G. Sorokova notes that the application of the Montessori methodology. Montessori increases the effectiveness of achieving educational objectives. In this system, the child acquires life skills in a social environment, and the role of the educator is to create conditions for the child's independent development and cultural interaction with society [9]. Montessori. Montessori emphasized the importance of fostering independence from an early age to cultivate strong and autonomous personalities. The principle 'Help me do it myself' cultivates in children a sense of order, which is essential for their development and self-identification.

The M. method Montessori takes into account the unique psychological characteristics of each child, thereby promoting a high level of motivation in learning. This approach enables children to derive satisfaction from the learning process, as they act not under external pressure but driven by their own aspirations and interests.

The autonomy of the individual, central to Montessori's methodology. Montessori contributes to the child's independence, high self-esteem, and self-reliance. The Montessori system emphasizes creative thinking while excluding authoritarian pressure. Educational tools, including spoons, brushes, napkins, towels, and sponges, are designed for independent mastery by children, with the educator merely assisting in the development of internal control and teaching basic self-care skills, thereby promoting their autonomy and practical abilities.

In the course of developing basic life skills in children aged 3 to 6 years, active work is undertaken to master practical abilities such as pouring liquids, transferring small grains, managing clothing fasteners, and other similar actions. These skills develop through methodical repetition and individual instruction. Each lesson is accompanied by specially designed educational materials that enable independent error detection and correction, as well as stimulate the refinement of fine motor skills of the hands.

Various educational elements equipped with buttons are designed to train manual skills. The process of cleaning small waste from the table is also structured: a basket with pre-prepared "trash", a dustpan, and a brush are used; all items are orderly arranged within a single box, which fosters the development of organization and orderliness.

In the Montessori system Preschool children in the Montessori system demonstrate significant progress in sensory skills, including object classification, recognition of colors, textures, sounds, geometric shapes, differentiation of temperatures and tastes, as well as working with artistic materials. This system combines freedom with discipline, fostering moral education and the development of social skills such as interaction, compromise, gratitude, personal hygiene, and self-care, which constitute the foundation for the development of a harmonious personality.

Various didactic games are widely used during educational activities in Montessori classrooms to promote the intellectual development of children. Let us present several examples.

1. The “Brown Stair,” consisting of ten wooden prisms decreasing in size, teaches concepts of sequence and size relationships, contributing to coordination and motor skills development.

2. The ‘Pink Tower,’ consisting of ten wooden cubes of varying sizes, helps children comprehend differences in size in three-dimensional space, fostering spatial perception, logical thinking, and motor skills.

3. The ‘Red Rods,’ composed of ten rods of different lengths (ranging from 10 cm to 1 m) but uniform width and height, teach children the concept of length while enhancing motor skills and developing mathematical abilities.

4. The ‘Cylinder Blocks’ comprise four sets of blocks with cylindrical indentations and nine cylinders differing in height and diameter in each set, which cultivate an understanding of size and fine motor skills crucial for writing.

Sandpaper letters are used in teaching graphic literacy to provide a tactile sensation of the contours of characters, forming associative connections between the sound and graphic components of letters. The ‘metal insets’ featuring ten geometric shapes with handles for gripping contribute to the development of hand-eye coordination required for writing.

The ‘red-blue rods’, a set of ten elements similar in size to the red rods but segmented into red and blue parts, are used to introduce children to arithmetic and fundamental mathematical operations. The ‘Box of Spindles,’ containing two boxes with sections numbered from 0 to 9, teaches the basics of counting and quantity visualization, where children distribute spindles according to the number. The ‘Golden Beads’ introduce the concepts of counting and basic mathematical operations. ‘Geometric Solids,’ including various shapes such as the cube, sphere, cylinder, and pyramid, are used to teach visual and tactile recognition of geometric forms [7].

In preschools operating under the Montessori system, Montessori employs a comprehensive approach to the development of children’s cognitive and speech abilities. The methodology includes individual interaction with speech materials and daily didactic games aimed at introducing fundamental concepts of the world and culture, as well as developing articulation skills. Reading and discussing literature, role-playing games, and theatrical performances contribute to the development of creative imagination and dramaturgical skills. Daily thematic circles include discussions, riddles, and games that stimulate critical thinking and effective communication in preschool children.

Thus, within the framework of the modern scientific paradigm, children’s cognitive abilities are regarded as a complex phenomenon conditioned by innate mechanisms characterized by individuality and self-regulation. Despite the comprehensive

nature of research in this field, the concept of children's cognitive abilities remains not fully elucidated and leaves room for further study. Education according to the M. system Montessori establishes a comprehensive foundation for the development of intellectual, social, and emotional components of the child's personality, aimed at his holistic development, education, and upbringing.

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PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR FORMING A SAFETY CULTURE AMONG FUTURE TECHNICIANS AT A COLLEGE

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Abstract. *The relevance is substantiated by the fact that ensuring citizens' safety, adherence to safety norms and regulations, and preserving life and health are among the priority components of a high standard of living, and that the formation of a culture of life safety among students is established as the primary objective of organizations engaged in educational activities. A group of pedagogical conditions ensuring the effectiveness of forming the life safety culture among future technicians in college has been identified, and the content of these conditions substantiated.*

Keywords: *life safety, life safety culture, students, pedagogical conditions, future technicians.*

Relevance of the study

The intensification of human activity, significant growth in urbanization and concentration of technosphere facilities, and the increase in the number of technogenic, military, and natural emergencies over the past decade have intensified problems related to ensuring human life safety in the modern world.

Statistical data from the Ministry of Civil Defense, Emergency Situations, and Disaster Relief for the years 2020-2024 indicate that approximately 300 emergency situations occur annually in the Russian Federation, resulting in around 350 fatalities, 90% of which are due to transport accidents (automobile, railway, and air transport), explosions and fires at industrial facilities, and other man-made causes.

The main factors affecting the life safety of specialists in technical fields are:

1. Adverse production environment (vibration and increased noise from machines and units, presence of harmful and hazardous impurities in the air).
2. Elevated levels of mortality and injury.

The main causes of accidents and disasters in technosphere facilities are an insufficient culture of life safety among technical personnel, expressed in the

non-performance or improper performance of their job responsibilities and neglect of safety requirements in production.

The Federal Law 'On Education in the Russian Federation' dated December 29, 2012, No. 273-FZ states that the culture of a healthy and safe lifestyle among students is developed by educators who foster students' cognitive activity, independence, initiative, and creative abilities. The same law stipulates that educators are obligated to cultivate in their students a civic stance, as well as the ability to work and manage daily life under contemporary living conditions.

In the State Program of the Russian Federation 'Development of Education,' approved by the Decree of the Government of the Russian Federation No. 1642 dated December 26, 2017, the section entitled 'Strategic Priorities for the Implementation of this Program until 2030' includes directions such as population preservation; strengthening traditional values, culture, and historical memory; development of human potential and a secure information environment. These priorities are integral components of the overall culture of life safety among students.

Undoubtedly, the foundation for cultivating a culture of life safety among students of technical disciplines is the organization of the educational process based on secondary vocational education programs, which constitute a triad of upbringing, teaching, and development of the future specialist. This is particularly relevant for those students whose future professional activities will involve decision-making, the timeliness and competence of which will affect not only their own lives but also the lives of their colleagues.

Today, the organization of secondary vocational education is becoming an educational environment that provides continuous training of specialists in the most promising and in-demand professions; moreover, these educational institutions lay the foundation for forming a higher level of life safety culture.

The Russian system of secondary vocational education continues to be a large-scale, fundamental structure for personnel training, within which the educational environment is dynamically developing.

Annually, according to data from the Ministry of Education of the Russian Federation, approximately 1.2 million individuals enroll in educational institutions offering secondary vocational education programs, of whom 40 to 50% enter technical sciences. At the same time, male and female applicants enrolling after completing the 9th grade are underage citizens whose life safety culture is insufficiently developed.

Main part

This study examines the effectiveness of developing a culture of life safety among future technicians at the college through the design, justification, and implementation of a structural-processual model for cultivating this culture within the college's educational process.

The subjects of pedagogical support in our model are, on one hand, the educator, the enterprise, and the family, who provide guidance, and on the other hand, the learner (a student of a technical specialty — a future technician), who independently pursues a personal trajectory in forming their culture of life safety through targeted interaction with the educator, enterprises, and family members [4].

The contemporary scholar N. V. Panova, in her research, established that ‘... the effective course of the processes of socialization and personification contributes to an increase in the levels of positivity, empathy, and congruence of the specialist, which enhances the degree of professional development of their potential maturity and ensures the possibility of full functioning’ [6, p. 2].

A fundamental condition for the formation of a culture of life safety among future technicians at the college is the interrelation between the ‘educational environment and pedagogical conditions,’ within which the process of forming this culture occurs.

The clarification of pedagogical conditions within our structural-process model for the formation of the life safety culture among future technicians in college, as well as the verification of these conditions, was conducted through the study of the experience of secondary vocational education institutions, experimental research, and observation and analysis.

In the educational process, the primary conditions are continuity and systematicity; therefore, it can be assumed that the effectiveness of pedagogical support in the formation of the life safety culture among future technicians in college will be ensured by establishing the following pedagogical conditions:

- enrichment of the content of future technicians’ activities with personal (responsibility, honesty, fairness) and socio-professional value orientations (collaboration, patriotism, civic stance) in the field of forming a culture of life safety, contributing to the development in future technicians of an understanding of an integrated system encompassing professional activity, individual protection, and safety requirements;

- ensuring the reflective nature of the activities of future technicians in the field of forming a culture of life safety, contributing to future technicians’ understanding of their status in relationships with classmates and instructors, the development of analytical thinking in learners when forecasting professionally hazardous situations, as well as the ability to foresee the prospects of their actions and their condition in the context of technological emergencies;

- implementing the subjective position of all participants in the educational process in the formation of a culture of life safety, enabling future college technicians to develop *desires* (to study life safety issues and seek solutions to these problems; to master the professional and personal qualities of future technicians; to make informed choices, as well as to express their individuality and stance; to

cultivate communication, cooperation, and interaction with all participants in the educational process), *abilities* (to independently make decisions and act in various life situations; to independently provide an adequate assessment of their activities, behavior, and actions), and *needs* (to systematically maintain the acquired knowledge and skills for ensuring their own, public, and national safety);

— transformation of the organization of the involvement of enterprises, families, other agencies, and structures in the college's educational process in forming the culture of safety in the life activities of future technicians, enabling the establishment of full-fledged relationships among all stakeholders in the educational and upbringing processes, i. e., educator — enterprise — family — student) [5].

The first pedagogical condition is enriching the content of future technicians' activities with value orientations [3]. What are value orientations? It is believed that this is the most important characteristic feature illustrating an individual's worldview. Value is one of the primary features determining human behavior and actions, and value orientations activate an individual's potential, both intellectual and creative.

To understand the multiple definitions of the term 'value orientations,' we analyzed the scientific literature in studies defining values in order to determine the essence of the generic definition of 'value' [1; 2]. In our understanding, value orientation is, on the one hand, the attitudes that regulate an individual's behavior, and on the other hand, the way a person manifests their attitude towards the surrounding reality.

The second pedagogical condition is ensuring the reflexive nature of the activities of future technicians. The inclusion of this pedagogical condition is determined by the presence of processes related to the social and cultural aspects of the community, as well as processes of sociocultural transformations within the personalities of the students.

Firstly, the personality of the future technician requires awareness and understanding of oneself as an individual, including one's rights, duties, shortcomings, merits, social status, and so forth.

Secondly, it is necessary for each individual to develop their own attitude towards events occurring around them, which is associated with the uncertainty of ideals in contemporary life and human activity, as well as with the increasing changes in the state, society, and each individual.

Thirdly, reflection in this pedagogical condition serves as an indispensable tool for resolving contradictions occurring within the personality of the learner — the future technician, and these contradictions are viewed by us as a mechanism for fostering a culture of life safety among students.

The third pedagogical condition is the realization of the subject position of all participants in the educational process in the field of forming a culture of life

safety, enabling the development of desires, abilities, and needs in future college technicians.

Reflection, as noted above, is one of the most important characteristics of subjectivity; without it, the formation of a culture of life safety is practically impossible. Subjectivity is one of the foundations for distinguishing levels of formation of the culture of life safety among future technicians in college.

The subject position of a student — a future technician — implies having a desire to study the issues of their own development, as well as to seek ways to address these issues; the ability to independently make decisions and act in various life situations; the ability to independently provide an adequate assessment of one's own activities, behavior, and actions; the desire to master the professional and personal qualities of a future specialist; the desire to make conscious choices, as well as to express one's individuality and position; the desire to develop communication, cooperation, and interaction with all participants in the educational process.

The fourth pedagogical condition in our structural-process model involves the transformation of the inclusion of enterprises, families, other agencies, and structures into the educational process of the college.

We consider that the social environment of future technicians in the college and their close cooperation with parents also play a significant role in the educational process during personality development and upbringing.

The family today is the environment that serves as the foundation for human socialization. Students spend most of their time at home, within the family, which means that the fundamental foundations of the students' personalities are established there.

Conclusions

The clarification of the pedagogical conditions, as well as the verification of these conditions, was conducted through the study of the experience of secondary vocational education institutions, experimental research at the University College, and during observation and analysis.

Thus, it was determined that the pedagogical conditions facilitate the formation of a culture of life safety among future technicians in the college:

— value orientations hold great significance for an individual and are prioritized, and if the learner acknowledges them, these values (value orientations) will serve as behavioral guidelines for the student and, consequently, will play a decisive role in the behavior and actions of the learner — the future technician;

— reflection represents the trajectory of one's life path development, a mechanism for managing and transforming one's activities, as well as the understanding and reinterpretation of these activities;

— the implementation of the subject position makes the process of forming a life safety culture among future technicians in college most effective. This

pedagogical condition enables future technicians not only to make conscious choices but also to bear personal responsibility for them, as well as fosters the expression of the learner's personal potential;

— the effectiveness of family, enterprise, and other agency involvement depends on the frequency and productivity of events held with students' parents, as well as with representatives of enterprises and other agencies and structures.

The described measures are vital for the formation of a life safety culture among future technicians in colleges. The interaction is mutually beneficial:

On the one hand, the educational institution, in addressing the objectives of the educational process, gains the opportunity to utilize the educational and material resources and other assets of enterprises and organizations;

On the other hand, the state, represented by these enterprises and organizations, perceives college students — future technicians — as fully-fledged members of society, fully adapted to modern life conditions and possessing a high level of life safety culture.

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TEACHER IN THE ERA OF AI: FROM KNOWLEDGE TRANSMITTER TO FACILITATOR OF THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *The article examines the impact of digitalization and AI on higher education in Russia, highlighting the paradox of human capital lagging behind technological advances. Drawing on surveys and personal experience, it explores psychological and emotional state of older faculty facing the new tasks and the need to redefine the teacher's role from knowledge transmitter to facilitator and mentor. It proposes a hybrid learning model with AI for personalization, ethical guidelines for tool use, and new pedagogical functions (coaching, trajectory design). Emphasis is on student collaboration and emotional competencies for successful adaptation.*

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, digital transformation, higher education, teacher role, personalized learning, psychological resistance, hybrid environment, pedagogical facilitator.*

Introduction

Modern higher education is undergoing profound changes due to digitalization and globalization. Digital transformation of the educational process, internationalization of education, and development of students' entrepreneurial competencies are the three main directions of innovation in the Russian higher education system [1].

A paradoxical situation arises: the pace of technological development increases exponentially, while the adaptation rate of human capital, including the teaching staff, lags behind. The older generation of teachers is gradually being replaced by younger ones who were born in the digital era. Meanwhile, the new generation of

students will soon be replaced by the next generation, already entering school life [2]. This demographic dynamic creates unique opportunities but also demands an urgent rethinking of the content, methods, and philosophy of education.

1. Problem research.

The integration of artificial intelligence into the educational process is not merely a technological innovation but a fundamental transformation requiring a profound rethinking of the teacher's role and the nature of interaction between teacher and student. A study conducted on a sample of 450 students and faculty members from leading universities shows that "78% of students and 82% of faculty acknowledge the significant potential of AI in optimizing the educational process" [3]. However, realizing this potential depends less on the technologies themselves and more on the teacher's ability to rethink their role and overcome internal resistance to change.

Artificial intelligence opens fundamentally new opportunities for individualizing learning. Unlike the traditional model, AI systems can analyze the unique characteristics of each learner — their pace of learning, strengths, areas for development, and preferred learning styles — and adapt educational material in real time [3].

For the teacher, AI becomes a powerful tool that frees them from routine tasks and enables the shift from the role of an information intermediary to that of a mentor, facilitator, and creator of a supportive educational environment, where each student has the opportunity to develop according to their potential.

Despite the clear advantages of AI technologies, the introduction of these tools into educational practice faces significant psychological resistance from faculty members. This resistance is deeply rooted and stems not merely from technical conservatism, but from fundamental issues of professional identity, significance, and the role of the teacher in contemporary society.

Many teachers began their professional careers in the analog era, and for several decades have been participants in the gradual yet steady digitalization of education. The traditional work routine involved manually preparing tests, lesson plans, and grading assignments with a red pen. However, there is now a clear sense of the need to adapt to the realities of a new era. Initially modestly and with some caution, but now more confidently, we have begun using AI tools. ChatGPT helped generate test variations, suggested structured ideas for lesson planning, and saved hours on routine tasks.

At that time, there was not yet a full realization that AI was becoming not just a tool for optimization, but a preparation for a broader transformation of professional consciousness. There was an understanding that the teacher's role would simply become more effective, but no understanding that this role would fundamentally change.

2. Stereotypes no longer work.

Our expectations that transmitting knowledge and experience to students through the traditional scheme — via a structured curriculum, prepared materials, and

checkpoints — would always ensure success in practical seminars were not met. At these moments, it became clear that students were not particularly engaged. They completed the assignments and attended classes, but there was no interest in their eyes. They did not feel like co-authors in the learning process. It was then that a sharp realization came that it was necessary to learn — not just technically, but to profoundly rethink one's approach to teaching.

These confrontations with reality led us to a profound internal reassessment, making it clear that we needed to radically change our approach. This was difficult because shifting the teaching paradigm for older educators requires not only technical retraining but also psychological reorientation and a reevaluation of the very meaning of professional identity.

This reconsideration requires comprehensive support, including psychological assistance, fostering a positive attitude toward change, and creating a safe environment for experimentation and mistakes.

At the academy, within the community of teachers aged 50 and above, this topic is also discussed with colleagues openly, without a professional mask. Understanding that honesty in acknowledging one's shortcomings is not a weakness marks the beginning of the path to change. It is necessary to stop hiding one's uncertainty about new tools and to start openly discussing it, including in the classroom with students. Of course, students are always willing to collaborate with their teachers and share their findings and discoveries in the use of AI tools fully, as they know more about this.

Students eagerly prepare reports for classes on how they use AI to learn English. They discuss various strategies that we, the teachers, had not even considered. Some use ChatGPT to practice dialogues on specific topics (for example, business negotiations), while others use AI to receive feedback on the grammar or vocabulary of their written work before submitting it for review. Students, perceiving the teacher as a partner, engage more actively in the process and share their digital discoveries.

This sincere appeal for collaboration opened entirely new opportunities for interaction. Students ceased to view us as teachers who must know EVERYTHING. They began to see us as partners in the learning process. Paradoxically, our authority increased when we acknowledged that we cannot be 'Jack of all trades.'

We assured the students that their knowledge and experience were valuable and showed them that we were not afraid to learn from them. This changed the dynamics. It became clear that our role had changed; there was a shift from teachers as transmitters to teachers as facilitators. We did not need to know all the answers; what mattered was creating an environment where students wanted to learn.

After classes, a tradition of sharing news with one another developed; trusting relationships became part of our interactions. Engagement in classroom sessions has increased, the fear of uncertainty has disappeared, more ideas have begun to be

generated during seminars, and questions that interest everyone, but were previously feared to be asked, are now being discussed.

3. New approaches to foreign language learning using AI.

The integration of AI into the educational process requires a fundamental shift in pedagogical thinking — from the traditional teaching paradigm (transmission of knowledge from teacher to student) to the learning paradigm (creating conditions for the independent construction of knowledge by the student) [4]. This is not merely a change in methods, but a rethinking of the very purpose of the teacher.

In the digital age, the teacher must perform fundamentally new functions:

— “Pedagogical coaching” — fostering students’ motivation and managing their emotional states

— “Pedagogical design” — designing individual educational pathways and creating personalized developmental trajectories

— “Pedagogical directing” — developing scenarios for interaction among students, the teacher, and digital tools

— “Personal mentoring” — providing individual support and assistance to each student.

— “Pedagogical animation” — stimulating positive student engagement in the learning process [5].

These new functions require teachers to develop emotional competence, reflective ability, critical thinking, and creative problem-solving skills — precisely those skills that cannot be fully automated and remain uniquely human resources [6].

It is important to emphasize that the digital educational environment should not completely replace traditional face-to-face teaching methods but should complement them, creating a hybrid environment in which pedagogical and digital technologies are integrated [7]. This synergy preserves the most valuable aspects of traditional education — live human interaction, the transmission not only of knowledge but also of values, moral guidelines, and creative inspiration — while simultaneously expanding possibilities through the personalization and adaptability of AI systems.

In such a hybrid environment, interaction remains a space for developing emotional connections, discussing complex ethical issues, and fostering creative collaboration. The teacher gains more time for in-depth interaction with students and for their own professional development.

4. From teaching experience.

We strive to implement this hybrid environment in our groups. Using ChatGPT to create exercise variations is very relevant, but our in-person class is dedicated to discussion, dialogue practice, and analysis of why language functions in certain ways. Students receive homework assignments that include both traditional exercises and

experimentation with AI tools — for example, practicing conversations with a chatbot, analyzing what the machine misunderstood, and reflecting on why it happened.

This combination works. Students feel they receive the best of both worlds: the efficiency of technology and human understanding.

The teacher must understand that the student is not an empty vessel to be filled with knowledge. Students often already have extensive experience working with digital tools, frequently much greater than that of the teacher. This requires humility and a willingness to learn from students. For example, organizing collaborative experiments with ChatGPT or other AI tools, where students become experts and can instruct the teacher.

The classroom should foster an atmosphere in which the teacher can openly discuss their difficulties with new technologies without fear of losing authority. At the same time, students must feel that their questions about the meaning of learning and the significance of their work are not a challenge to authority but an invitation to a deep dialogue.

We told our students that we are people of a different generation, but we know how to teach English effectively and critically engage with new technologies. Such dialogues helped students to open up. They began asking deeper questions because they understood that we value genuine dialogue more than the appearance of omniscience.

At present, it is important to acknowledge that prohibiting the use of neural networks in the educational process is impossible. The teacher, together with the students, can discuss ethical boundaries and establish criteria for the acceptable use of AI in academic work. For instance, this could look like the following: using AI for drafts and ideas is acceptable, but the final text must be independently written by the student. Alternatively, AI can be used to check grammar in English texts, but not to generate the content of an essay.

We have developed rules for the use of AI within our groups. The students were glad to be asked to participate in making this decision. They proposed ideas that we would never have thought of ourselves. And, importantly, when it later became necessary to comply with these rules, the students were ready to do so because they had created the rules themselves.

A balanced approach is necessary in the application of these rules:

— For lower proficiency levels (A1-A2), strict limitations on the use of AI are helpful, as students develop fundamental skills and need to exert active effort.

— For the intermediate level (B1-B2), AI use can be permitted for drafting and editing, but students must critically evaluate the machine-produced content, correct errors, and add personal examples.

— For the advanced level (C1-C2), AI becomes a full-fledged professional writing tool. The teacher's role is to instruct students on effectively using this technology, critically assessing results, and maintaining high quality standards.

Foreign language teaching especially benefits from AI tools since language is a living practice that requires extensive repetition, pronunciation correction, and instant feedback [8]. AI-based personalized learning promotes more effective planning of a student's studies, taking into account individual needs [3]. Appropriate chatbots can be used to train dialogic speech. A student can practice conversational skills at any time, day or night, by interacting with an AI assistant. This is especially valuable for students who do not have the opportunity to interact with native speakers.

For training written speech, it is advisable to use 'Tools for text analysis and correction'. Such tools enable students to receive instant feedback on grammar, style, and clarity of writing. Instead of the teacher reviewing 30 essays and leaving comments that students might later not read thoroughly, automated tools provide interactive, real-time learning.

For many teachers, adopting new methods requires not only mastering technical skills but also undergoing psychological reorientation. The integration of artificial intelligence into the educational process is not merely a technological reform; it is a challenge to rethink the very essence of pedagogical activity. For senior educators who have devoted decades to the traditional teaching format, this challenge may seem threatening. However, it is also a unique opportunity to be reborn, to reconsider one's beliefs, and to become architects of new methods of learning. It is impossible to artificially implement AI in education without the internal transformation of the teacher themselves. The key to success lies not in technical equipment, but in the willingness to engage in dialogue and collaboratively design future education with students.

5. Conclusions and forecasts on the use of AI in seminars.

In the coming years (2026-2030), AI will radically transform English language seminars at Russian universities, shifting from routine tasks to creating emotionally intelligent and adaptive learning environments. According to expert forecasts, AI tutors with emotion recognition (via analysis of facial expressions, tone of voice, and learning patterns) will become standard, accelerating student progress by 40% through personalized feedback and reducing speaking anxiety. [9][10]

In seminars, AI will handle automated essay scoring (AES), chatbots for practicing productive skills (writing, speaking), and intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) for adaptive exercises, freeing educators to serve as mentors and facilitators of complex communicative interactions. By 2030, the integration of multimodal AI systems (incorporating VR/AR for immersive scenarios) is anticipated, accompanied by ethical challenges: standardizing ethical norms and training personnel will be necessary to prevent the "washing out" effect in assessment and mitigate geopolitical risks. [11][12][13][9]

In the modern educational environment, with a focus on mastering knowledge at B1–B2 levels, AI will enhance seminar interactivity through predictable analytics of learning trajectories, improving students' emotional competence — a key factor for adaptation in a hybrid environment. Without rethinking the teacher's role in the transformation process, these tools risk remaining merely technical supplements, failing to unlock their potential for deep personalized learning. The teacher must evolve into a facilitator and curator, integrating AI not as a replacement but as a partner that enhances the human element: empathy, critical thinking, and motivation.

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KINESIC IMAGE, VOICE AND RHETORICAL COMPETENCE IN THE STRUCTURE OF THE TRANSLATOR'S COMMUNICATIVE PERSONALITY

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Abstract: *This article addresses the problem of providing a holistic description of the translator's communicative personality. The author substantiates the necessity of overcoming the verbocentric approach in contemporary translation studies and proposes considering translation activity as a polymodal process in which kinesic (bodily), vocal-paralinguistic, and rhetorical components function in an inseparable unity. Drawing on the classical works of F. Poyatos [5, 6], the research of E. V. Alikina [1, 2, 3], and other Russian and international scholars, the author analyzes the mechanisms of synchronizing verbal and non-verbal codes in the translator's work. Special attention is paid to the concept of translational empathy as an integrative property ensuring the coherence of communicative behavior.*

Keywords: *communicative personality of the translator; kinesic image, voice, rhetoric, business rhetoric, kinesics, vocal culture, rhetorical competence, translation, interpreter, translator; verbal and non-verbal communication, competencies, empathy, communicative behavior, communication.*

Introduction

In contemporary translation studies, the limitations of a purely linguistic approach to the study of translation activity are becoming increasingly evident. For a long time, researchers were primarily interested in issues of linguistic correspondences, transformations, equivalence, and adequacy. The translator themselves remained, as it were, “behind the scenes”—an invisible operator whose personality, physicality, voice, and demeanor were considered secondary, not influencing the outcome.

However, the real practice of interpreting convincingly demonstrates that the success of communication depends not only on what the translator says but also on how they say it, how they appear, how they move, how they look, and how they engage the audience. This issue is particularly acute in situations of consecutive interpreting, on-camera simultaneous interpreting (television), escort interpreting for delegations, court interpreting, and medical interpreting, where trust in the translator directly affects trust in the information itself.

The purpose of this article is to propose an integrative model of the translator's communicative personality, uniting three fundamental dimensions: the kinesic image (bodily-gestural behavior), vocal-paralinguistic culture (voice, intonation, prosody), and rhetorical competence (the ability to persuade and build trust). The theoretical framework draws on the works of Fernando Poyatos, a classic scholar in the non-verbal semiotics of translation, as well as the contributions of Elena Vadimovna Alikina, a leading Russian specialist in the field of translation.

Main part

The foundation for studying the non-verbal aspects of translation was laid by the Spanish semiotician Fernando Poyatos. In his monograph "Nonverbal Communication and Translation", he was the first to propose viewing translation as working with a "total communicative complex," comprising three interrelated systems: language, paralinguage, and kinesics [5]. Poyatos convincingly demonstrated that in real communication, these systems are inseparable: gesture accompanies the word, intonation colors the meaning, and the pause creates tension. Ignoring non-verbal components in translation leads to impoverishment and, at times, to distortion of the original message.

In his later work, "Textual Translation and Live Translation", Poyatos extended this approach to the analysis of "live" translation — theatrical, simultaneous, consecutive — and emphasized that it is precisely in real-time situations that non-verbal components acquire particular significance, as they are perceived directly by the audience, bypassing the filter of textual analysis [6].

In Russian academia, the anthropological approach to translation is most consistently developed by Elena Vadimovna Alikina, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor, and Head of the Department of Translation and Applied Linguistics at Perm State National Research University. In her textbook "Introduction to the Theory and Practice of Consecutive Interpreting", she explicitly states: "Interpreting is not a mechanical recoding from one language to another, but a complex mental activity involving memory, attention, thinking, emotions, will, and other mental processes and personality traits of the translator" [1]. This thesis is fundamentally important: the translator is viewed not as a transmitter, but as an integral personality with all their psychological characteristics.

In her work “Psychological Model of Consecutive Interpreting», Alikina elaborates on this understanding: “Consecutive interpreting is a complex type of mental activity characterized by polyfunctionality, polymodality, and poly-subjectness. Its psychological content includes the processes of perception, memorization, comprehension, and speech production, occurring under conditions of strict time constraints” [2]. The term “polymodality” is key here. It means that the translator works simultaneously in several modalities (auditory, visual, kinesthetic) and must synchronize incoming signals with their own speech production.

In the article “Taxonomic Aspect of Interpreting”, Alikina proposes classifying types of interpreting not only by traditional parameters (simultaneous/consecutive, direct/retour) but also by more nuanced characteristics: communication conditions, the role behavior of the translator, and the degree of their involvement in the situation [3]. This opens up the possibility for analyzing how the translator “plays a role” in different contexts — and in this performance, their entire body participates.

The kinesic image is the set of visually perceived characteristics of the translator’s behavior: posture, gestures, facial expressions, direction of gaze, movement in space, and distance from interlocutors. In the Western tradition, this aspect is studied within the frameworks of kinesics and proxemics.

It would seem that the translator’s body should not attract attention — the ideal translator is “transparent,” their task being to make the audience see and hear only the speaker. But in practice, complete disappearance is impossible and, moreover, undesirable. As Alikina notes, a translator must possess “public speaking technique,” of which bodily self-regulation is a part [1]. In other words, a translator must master the basics of oratory, know how to comport themselves before an audience, control their psychophysical state, and manage the listeners’ attention [1].

What specifically constitutes the kinesic image?

Firstly, posture and stance. Slouching, rigidity, rocking from heel to toe, shifting from one foot to another — all of this is perceived by the audience as uncertainty, discomfort, and unprofessionalism. Conversely, a stable, open posture creates an impression of reliability.

Secondly, gesticulation. A complete absence of gestures makes speech unnatural, “wooden.” Excessive, chaotic gesticulation is distracting. The golden mean consists of gestures that naturally accompany speech, emphasize logical stress, and illustrate spatial relationships.

Thirdly, eye contact. In European culture, direct eye contact with the audience is a sign of sincerity and confidence. A translator who looks at the floor, the ceiling, or their notes loses trust. At the same time, it is important to remember cultural differences: in some Eastern cultures, direct eye contact may be perceived as aggression.

Even when working with recorded material, the translator relies on the visual channel no less than on the spoken word. An actor’s gesture, facial expression, or

mise-en-scène often suggests the correct translation solution more effectively than the words themselves. This is even more true in live communication, where the speaker's body is directly present.

The problem of synchronizing verbal and non-verbal channels becomes the subject of specific analysis in the work of A. Darwish and P. Orero, "Rhetorical dissonance of unsynchronized voices" [7]. The authors introduce the concept of "rhetorical dissonance"—a situation where the voice and body "say" different things. Using television translation as material, they demonstrate that if a viewer sees an announcer or translator on screen but hears a voice whose energy does not match the visible behavior, a feeling of falseness arises, and trust in the information declines [7].

Vocal Culture of the Translator: Voice as a Semantic Instrument. The translator's voice is not merely a conduit for others' words but a complex semiotic complex. Poyatos introduced the concept of "paralanguage," denoting all vocal characteristics accompanying speech: timbre, tempo, volume, rhythm, pauses, sighs, laughter, throat-clearing, etc. [5]. In interpreting, paralinguistic elements create a particular problem: should the translator imitate the speaker's vocal score?

Alikina repeatedly emphasizes the importance of vocal training for the translator in her works: "An interpreter must master the basics of oratory, as their speech is delivered publicly and must be not only grammatically correct but also aesthetically acceptable, persuasive, and appropriate to the communication situation" [1].

Let us note the phrase "aesthetically acceptable." An unpleasant timbre, monotony, tachylalia (excessively fast speech), bradylalia (excessively slow speech), unjustified pauses, filler words, unclear diction — all of this destroys perception, even if the translation is accurate in terms of meaning.

In contemporary translation studies, new concepts describing the vocal work of the translator are emerging. The term "transvocal modulation" is introduced — the translator's ability to flexibly change their vocal delivery depending on how strongly the author's position is expressed in the text. In academic translation, for example, it is important to preserve the author's epistemic caution (markers of uncertainty, supposition) while avoiding overdoing intonational uncertainty. This requires fine vocal tuning.

Rhetorical Competence of the Translator: Persuasion as a Professional Task. Rhetoric in translation is a topic that has only recently begun to be seriously discussed. Traditionally, it was believed that the translator's task was to convey information, while persuasion was the speaker's role. However, in reality, separating these functions is impossible: any utterance, even the most neutral, has an impact on the audience.

Lin Mei, in the article "Rhetorical Situation as an Effective Aspect of Studying Translation Activity», proposes viewing translation as a rhetorical act that always occurs within a specific social and cultural situation and is always aimed at persuading the addressee [4]. Translation is an interlinguacultural dialogic process that takes place in a specific situation with particular social and cultural conditions of

the target language and influences the addressee through the effective use of speech means for persuasion.

What does this mean for the translator? They must be able to analyze the rhetorical situation according to classical parameters: who is speaking (ethos), to whom (audience), for what purpose (intention), in what context (circumstances), and by what means (logos and pathos). Based on this analysis, they must adapt their speech — without altering the meaning, but by choosing appropriate means of expression.

Thus, a translator with developed rhetorical competence does not merely “transpose words” but constructs a persuasive, appropriate, and trustworthy utterance in the target language.

Empathy as an Integrative Property of the Communicative Personality. In recent years, the concept of translational empathy has been increasingly discussed in translation studies. This is the ability for emotional-cognitive resonance with the original message. A synergetic model of the translational space is emerging, within which an “energy field” is identified where emotive meanings are formed. This allows the translator to choose means of expression (verbal and non-verbal) that will create the same effect in the audience as the original.

An integrative approach to teaching interpreting presupposes not merely a sum of knowledge and skills, but the formation of a holistic translator personality capable of dialogue, understanding, and empathy. Empathy allows the translator to move beyond purely linguistic competence. It is empathy that connects kinesics, voice, and rhetoric into a living unity. If the translator feels the situation, their body and voice respond naturally and spontaneously. If they do not feel it, the result is mechanical reproduction, which the audience always perceives as false.

Conclusion

The conducted analysis allows us to draw the following conclusions:

1. The translator’s communicative personality cannot be adequately described within the framework of a verbocentric paradigm. An integrative approach is necessary, one that considers kinesic, vocal, and rhetorical components.

2. The classical works of F. Poyatos and contemporary research by E. V. Alkina provide a theoretical basis for such an approach, introducing the concepts of polymodality, paralanguage, and the psychological content of translation activity.

3. The translator’s kinesic image (bodily behavior) is a fully-fledged carrier of meaning and requires conscious formation during professional training.

4. The translator’s vocal culture includes not only diction clarity but also a fine paralinguistic attunement to the rhetorical situation, encompassing phenomena such as “transvocal modulation.”

5. The translator’s rhetorical competence ensures the communicative effect of the translation and should become a subject of specialized training.

6. Empathy serves as an integrative property, ensuring the synthesis of all components in the holistic act of translation activity.

Prospects for further research are associated with:

1. Empirical recording of the real interaction of verbal and non-verbal codes in the work of translators (audio and video recording, analysis);

2. Development of methodologies for forming polycode competence within the professional training system;

3. Cross-cultural studies of kinesic and paralinguistic norms in translation practice;

4. Studying the specific features of non-verbal communication in new formats (remote simultaneous interpreting, video conferencing).

This research allows us to see the translator as a holistic communicative personality, bodily, vocally, and rhetorically present in intercultural dialogue.

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**SOUTH KOREA:
NUCLEAR POLICY WITHOUT NUCLEAR WEAPONS (1991–2023)**

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the evolution of the Republic of Korea's (ROK) nuclear policy from 1991 to 2023 under conditions of a sustained non-nuclear status amid an immediate nuclear threat from the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK). The study examines how Seoul adapted its national security strategy to a changing military-strategic environment following the DPRK's acquisition of nuclear weapons without transitioning to an indigenous nuclear arsenal. The article reviews the principal stages of institutional consolidation of the ROK's non-nuclear course after the withdrawal of U.S. tactical nuclear weapons in 1991; the transformation of extended deterrence mechanisms and the development of the ROK's non-nuclear military capabilities in 2006-2023; and the domestic political discourse on the desirability of nuclear armament. Particular attention is paid to the "decoupling" problem affecting allied guarantees and to institutional measures aimed at strengthening confidence in extended deterrence. The article concludes that the ROK's non-nuclear status is maintained not only through international legal commitments but also through an active strategy of institutionalizing allied deterrence and minimizing the economic and political risks of a nuclear breakout. The ROK case demonstrates the relative resilience of a security model without national nuclear weapons in a context of regional confrontation and is relevant for assessing the prospects of the global nonproliferation regime.*

Keywords: *Republic of Korea; nuclear policy; non-nuclear status; extended nuclear deterrence; security dilemma; decoupling; nonproliferation regime; Korean Peninsula; DPRK.*

Introduction. The Republic of Korea's nuclear policy in 1991-2023 represents an instructive case for analyzing the resilience of the nonproliferation regime under conditions of a direct military threat. South Korea occupies a unique position: on the one hand, it possesses a developed technological and industrial base that, given a political decision, could enable a relatively rapid approach to

an indigenous nuclear capability; on the other hand, since the early 1990s it has consistently maintained a non-nuclear status despite the DPRK's transformation into a de facto nuclear-armed state. In practice, this entails continuous balancing between threat-based logic and obligations under international law, as well as reliance on external security guarantees, above all U.S. extended deterrence.

The research problem lies in the fact that the strengthening of the DPRK's nuclear and missile capabilities and the growing public support in South Korea for the idea of nuclear armament raise questions about the long-term sustainability of a security model without national nuclear weapons. The very persistence of Seoul's commitment to the Treaty on the Non-Proliferation of Nuclear Weapons (NPT) and its refusal to develop a national arsenal requires explanation not only through "allied will" or "international pressure," but also through the internal logic of strategic choice by South Korean leadership, economic constraints, political risks, and the institutions of the nonproliferation regime.

The purpose of the article is to trace the evolution of the ROK's nuclear policy in 1991-2023 and to explain how Seoul adapted its security strategy to the DPRK's acquisition of nuclear weapons without moving toward a national nuclear status. To achieve this purpose, the article addresses four tasks: (1) to identify stages in the formation and consolidation of South Korea's non-nuclear status after the withdrawal of U.S. tactical nuclear weapons and the signing of the 1992 Joint Declaration; (2) to characterize the transformation of deterrence mechanisms and alliance interaction with the United States after the DPRK's first nuclear test in 2006; (3) to analyze the domestic discussion in the ROK regarding the "nuclear option" and the factors constraining its institutionalization; and (4) to determine the place of South Korean policy within the international nonproliferation regime and to assess its significance for regional stability.

Methodologically, the study relies on the principles of historicism and a systems approach: nuclear policy is treated as the result of interaction between external challenges (threats from the DPRK, changes in allied guarantees, and great-power competition) and internal factors (political discourse, economic risks, and institutional constraints). The source base includes official documents¹ and statements², materials of international organizations and analytical publications of

¹ "Joint Declaration of the Denuclearization of the Korean Peninsula" (January 20, 1992), United Nations Peacemaker, accessed February 22, 2026, <https://peacemaker.un.org/sites/default/files/document/files/2024/05/kr20kp920120jointdeclarationdenuclearizationkoreanpeninsula.pdf>

² "Roh Declares South Korea Is Free of Nuclear Weapons," UPI, December 18, 1991, accessed February 22, 2026, <https://www.upi.com/Archives/1991/12/18/Roh-declares-South-Korea-is-free-of-nuclear-weapons/6592693032400/>

think tanks¹, as well as Russian and international scholarly literature on the Korean Peninsula, extended deterrence, and nonproliferation².

The novelty of the article lies in a comprehensive interpretation of the ROK's non-nuclear status not as a fixed "given," but as a continuously reproduced political strategy that experiences increasing pressure as threats grow while being reinforced through institutional and alliance mechanisms. The practical significance of the study is that its findings help clarify the boundaries of the nonproliferation regime's viability with respect to "threshold" states in a context of regional confrontation.

Structurally, the article includes an introduction, three analytical sections (1991-2006; 2006-2020; 2021-2023 and domestic discourse), and a conclusion summarizing the results and assessing future prospects.

Stages in the Formation of South Korea's Non-Nuclear Status (1991-2006). By the early 1990s, the Republic of Korea was already a party to the NPT and officially did not pursue nuclear weapons development (after terminating relevant efforts in the 1970s under U.S. pressure)³. A key milestone was 1991: following the end of the Cold War, the U.S. administration decided to withdraw all tactical nuclear warheads from South Korean territory. At the same time, ROK President Roh Tae-woo declared an intention to make Korea a nuclear-free zone⁴. These steps laid the foundation for the Joint Declaration on the Denuclearization of the Korean Peninsula, signed by Seoul and Pyongyang on 20 January 1992⁵. The document proclaimed that both Korean states would renounce the production, possession, and deployment of nuclear weapons and also prohibited the establishment of nuclear fuel reprocessing and uranium enrichment facilities on the Peninsula. Although the DPRK subsequently effectively abandoned compliance with this declaration, for Seoul it served as an important foreign-policy confirmation of the ROK's non-nuclear status⁶.

¹ Ildar A. Akhtamzyan, *Nuclear Nonproliferation: A University Textbook*, vol. 1 (Moscow: PIR Center, 2002).

² Anatoly V. Torkunov, Georgy D. Toloraya, and Ivan V. Dyachkov, *Modern Korea: Metamorphoses of the Turbulent Years (2008-2020)* (Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 2021).

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ "Joint Declaration of the Denuclearization of the Korean Peninsula" (January 20, 1992), United Nations Peacemaker, accessed February 20, 2026, <https://peacemaker.un.org/sites/default/files/document/files/2024/05/kr20kp920120jointdeclarationdenuclearizationkoreanpeninsula.pdf>

⁶ *Ibid.*

Throughout the 1990s, South Korea consistently adhered to nonproliferation policy, relying on diplomatic settlement of the DPRK nuclear issue in cooperation with the international community. Seoul supported negotiations between the United States and North Korea that resulted in the 1994 Agreed Framework, which envisaged freezing the DPRK's nuclear program in exchange for economic assistance¹. During this period, the ROK undertook no steps toward acquiring nuclear weapons; instead, it relied on its alliance with Washington and U.S. security guarantees. In 1996 the ROK joined the Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty (ratified in 1999)², thereby reaffirming its commitment to forgo nuclear weapons. At the same time, the country actively developed its nuclear energy program and scientific research, requiring strict compliance with IAEA arrangements. In 2004 information emerged about certain unauthorized experiments by South Korean scientists involving nuclear materials (in the early 1980s and in 2000) that had not been reported to the IAEA. The South Korean government voluntarily disclosed these facts and invited inspectors; given the small scale of the violations and Seoul's constructive cooperation, the IAEA Board of Governors did not refer the incident to the UN Security Council^{3,4}. This episode confirmed the ROK's advanced scientific and technological potential in the nuclear field, while also demonstrating its commitment to international control rules. In February 2004, an Additional Protocol to the ROK's safeguards agreement with the IAEA entered into force, further strengthening transparency in its nuclear activities.

¹ Agreement between the Republic of Korea and the United States of America Concerning Special Measures Relating to Article V of the Agreement under Article IV of the Mutual Defense Treaty between the Republic of Korea and the United States of America Regarding Facilities and Areas and the Status of United States Armed Forces in the Republic of Korea, signed November 23, 1993, entered into force January 1, 1994, United Nations Treaty Series 1771 (1994), <https://m.bigenc.ru/vault/a955f7a4e82c637336ee0a73cff7235.pdf> (accessed February 22, 2026).

² Comprehensive Nuclear-Test-Ban Treaty (CTBT), adopted September 10, 1996, United Nations General Assembly, A/RES/50/245, CTBTO Treaty Booklet (2022 edition), https://www.ctbto.org/sites/default/files/2023-10/2022_treaty_booklet_E.pdf (accessed February 22, 2026).

³ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). Implementation of the NPT Safeguards Agreement in the Republic of Korea. GOV/2004/84. November 11, 2004. <https://www.iaea.org/sites/default/files/documents/gov2004-84.pdf> (accessed February 22, 2026).

⁴ International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA). "IAEA Board Concludes Consideration of Safeguards in South Korea." November 26, 2004. <https://www.iaea.org/newscenter/news/iaea-board-concludes-consideration-safeguards-south-korea> (accessed February 22, 2026).

The end of this stage was marked by a sharp escalation of the nuclear problem on the Korean Peninsula. After the DPRK resumed previously frozen work in 2002–2003 and withdrew from the NPT, international efforts focused on the Six-Party Talks format (DPRK, ROK, United States, Russia, China, Japan). Despite the September 2005 agreement on principles of DPRK denuclearization, implementation failed. On 9 October 2006 the DPRK conducted its first nuclear test, declaring itself a nuclear state. This event created a qualitatively new security environment for South Korea, which for the first time faced the reality of a neighboring state possessing nuclear weapons. Nevertheless, even after 2006 the ROK reaffirmed its non-nuclear course: Seoul condemned Pyongyang's actions and supported UN Security Council sanctions, but did not revise its NPT commitments or other nonproliferation obligations.

Deterrence Strategy and External Challenges (2006–2020). The DPRK's acquisition of nuclear weapons fundamentally altered the military-strategic realities for Seoul. From 2006 onward, South Korean leadership faced the task of neutralizing the heightened threat while remaining within the bounds of a non-nuclear policy. The solution was found in strengthening allied cooperation with the United States and developing South Korea's own conventional deterrent capabilities. Washington publicly confirmed that "extended nuclear deterrence" applied to Seoul, i. e., that the United States would protect the ROK under its nuclear umbrella in the event of aggression from the North. Practically, this meant that the United States remained prepared, in an extreme situation, to employ nuclear weapons in defense of South Korea, even though U.S. nuclear weapons were no longer stationed on ROK territory. Bilateral defense documents and statements of the period recorded that the United States provided the ROK with a "nuclear umbrella" and all necessary deterrence means against the DPRK threat. Accordingly, the emphasis was placed on sustaining nuclear deterrence beyond the territory of South Korea itself.

In parallel, Seoul began modernizing its own defense potential. In the late 2000s and 2010s, within the "Three-Axis" defense concept, South Korea developed programs for preemptive strike (Kill Chain), missile defense (Korea Air and Missile Defense, KAMD), and massive retaliation and punishment (Korea Massive Punishment and Retaliation, KMPR). In particular, the ROK expanded its conventional precision-strike missile capabilities, enabled by the gradual relaxation of alliance restrictions on the range and payload of South Korean ballistic missiles. Whereas earlier the missile range under U.S.—ROK guidelines did not exceed 300 km, by 2020 these limitations had been removed, opening a path toward longer-range missiles capable of striking targets on and beyond DPRK territory. In addition, in 2016–2017, with U.S. support, the Terminal High Altitude Area Defense (THAAD) system was deployed in South Korea to intercept DPRK missiles at higher altitudes. The deployment provoked strong Chinese opposition and temporarily degraded Seoul–Beijing

relations, demonstrating the foreign-policy balancing challenges South Korea faces when seeking security against the DPRK threat amid major-power competition.

From 2006 to 2020, the DPRK not only refused to renounce nuclear weapons but substantially expanded its nuclear and missile capabilities through multiple tests. Following the first explosion in 2006, tests occurred in 2009, 2013, twice in 2016, and the most powerful in September 2017, when Pyongyang claimed it had tested a hydrogen bomb. The DPRK also improved delivery systems, including intercontinental ballistic missiles. As a result, by the end of the 2010s North Korea could potentially threaten not only U.S. allies in the region but also the U.S. homeland itself. This created a new strategic concern in Seoul: would Washington refrain from defending South Korea if U.S. cities faced the risk of nuclear-armed DPRK missiles? In other words, the alliance encountered the classic “decoupling” problem: nuclear umbrella guarantees become less credible when the adversary can inflict unacceptable damage on the guarantor. These concerns intensified during Donald Trump’s presidency (2017-2021), when he often expressed skepticism regarding alliance commitments to Seoul and Tokyo. Against this background, calls in South Korea for greater self-reliance in defense grew louder. Yet even at the most acute moments (for example, in 2017, when threats exchanged between Kim Jong Un and D. Trump brought the region to the brink of conflict), ROK leadership repeatedly stated that it had no plans to develop nuclear weapons or to reintroduce U.S. warheads. Instead, South Korea continued close coordination with the United States: the scope of joint military exercises expanded; bilateral consultation mechanisms on extended deterrence were established, including the Extended Deterrence Strategy and Consultation Group (created in 2010) and a renewed deterrence working group in 2018. In 2018-2019, under President Moon Jae-in, Seoul pursued détente and dialogue with the DPRK, temporarily reducing tensions (inter-Korean summits in 2018, the DPRK leader’s meetings with the U. S. President). However, by 2020 the dialogue stalled again, while the North’s nuclear and missile programs continued to advance.

Thus, in the late 2000s and the 2010s, South Korea’s nuclear policy evolved under the imperative of resolving a security dilemma: how to protect against a growing DPRK nuclear threat while not violating international commitments or provoking a regional arms race. Seoul responded through a combination of measures: reliance on the U.S. alliance (seeking as concrete as possible guarantees and joint planning for extended deterrence) and the build-up of its own conventional military capabilities. This approach strengthened deterrence without departing from the ROK’s non-nuclear status¹.

¹ Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Korea, “Korea, US Adopt Joint Declaration, Form Nuclear Consultative Group,” May 2, 2023, https://www.mofa.go.kr/eng/brd/m_5674/view.do?seq=320808 (accessed February 22, 2026).

From a theoretical perspective, South Korea's post-2006 strategy can be interpreted through the security dilemma and the "decoupling" problem in alliances, which arises when an adversary gains the ability to impose costs on the security guarantor itself. In such conditions, a technologically advanced state faces a choice between autonomous nuclear deterrence and institutional deepening of alliance mechanisms. The ROK chose the second path, seeking to formalize consultative structures, expand joint planning, and increase the transparency and credibility of extended deterrence guarantees, as reflected in the creation of the Nuclear Consultative Group in 2023¹. Thus, the non-nuclear status is maintained not by a passive renunciation of nuclear weapons, but by the active reproduction of allied deterrence mechanisms and by strengthening South Korea's own non-nuclear capabilities².

Domestic Political Discourse. Until the mid-2000s, the question of South Korea acquiring its own nuclear weapons was effectively absent from public debate and was widely viewed as closed. However, as the DPRK's nuclear capabilities expanded, a discussion gradually emerged in the ROK over the desirability of nuclear armament, balancing fear of the threat against rational assessment of the risks of such a step. Fear of DPRK military power and doubts about the reliability of external guarantees push parts of society and some politicians toward the idea of an indigenous nuclear arsenal. Public opinion polls over roughly the last 15 years show a stable majority supporting nuclear weapons development, typically ranging from 60% to more than 70%. For example, at the end of 2021 about 71% of South Koreans reportedly favored a nuclear status for their country^{3,4}. These figures reflect genuine public anxiety: many citizens doubt the United States would use nuclear weapons to defend Seoul at the cost of risking U.S. cities. Such attitudes strengthened after the DPRK demonstrated an ability to threaten the U.S. homeland, calling into question the automaticity of U.S. guarantees.

At the same time, rational calculation predominates among South Korea's political and diplomatic elites, who recognize the severe consequences of a potential nuclear breakout. For many years, the prevailing view among ROK elites

¹ Sagan S. D. Why Do States Build Nuclear Weapons? Three Models in Search of a Bomb // *International Security*.— 1996.— Vol. 21.— No. 3.— P. 54-86.

² Waltz K. The Spread of Nuclear Weapons: More May Be Better // *Adelphi Papers*.— 1981.— Vol. 21.— No. 171.

³ Kang, C. K., South Korean Public Perception of Nuclear Proliferation, April 2024, <https://wapor.org/wp-content/uploads/Kang-South-Korean-Perception-of-Nuclear-Proliferation-1.pdf> (accessed February 22, 2026).

⁴ Asan Institute for Policy Studies, "Comparing Allied Public Confidence in U.S. Extended Nuclear Deterrence," 2024, https://asaninst.org/bbs/board.php?bo_table=s1_1_eng&wr_id=184 (accessed February 22, 2026).

has been that attempting to build a nuclear arsenal would cause more harm than benefit. First, it would constitute a direct violation of the NPT, likely triggering immediate international condemnation and sanctions by the UN Security Council. As a country deeply integrated into the global economy, the ROK would face substantial losses due to disrupted relations with key partners. Analysts note that Beijing would very likely impose harsh trade restrictions in response to a South Korean nuclear move. Second, nuclearization would jeopardize the alliance with the United States: Washington would likely withdraw its extended deterrence assurances and reconsider alliance arrangements, as has occurred in other cases of nonproliferation violations. Third, obtaining nuclear weapons would not automatically resolve security problems given the DPRK's existing arsenal and the risk of a regional arms race.

Domestic debates intensified after 2016, when the DPRK conducted a series of tests indicating accelerated nuclear progress. Calls to reconsider previous taboos appeared within South Korea's conservative camp. Some lawmakers and influential right-leaning figures openly advocated the return of U.S. tactical nuclear weapons to the ROK or even the development of a national bomb. In 2017 leaders of the then-opposition Liberty Korea Party proposed renouncing non-nuclear commitments and hosting U.S. nuclear warheads to deter the North. Some public figures went further, pointing to Japan's reliance on the U.S. nuclear umbrella and drawing analogies to NATO nuclear sharing, arguing that the ROK should seek comparable arrangements or develop a national arsenal. These ideas remained marginal until the early 2020s and did not receive support from the country's leadership.

A turning point emerged in recent years as Pyongyang's nuclear coercion reached its most acute form. In 2022-2023 the nuclear status debate moved out of the shadows and began to be discussed not only by experts but also by incumbent officials. In spring 2022, after renewed DPRK missile provocations, talk resurfaced in Seoul about a possible ROK withdrawal from the NPT and the creation of national nuclear weapons. In August 2022 President Yoon Suk Yeol publicly stated that South Korea did not plan to acquire nuclear weapons¹. Although this appeared to close the issue, the very fact that the head of state considered it necessary to speak so directly was unprecedented. In 2023 several high-ranking figures publicly addressed this sensitive subject. For instance, the Mayor of Seoul, Oh Se-hoon, in March 2023 urged serious consideration of an indigenous nuclear program to counter the DPRK, even at the cost of

¹ "South Korean President Yoon Suk Yeol Says Seoul Remains Committed to the NPT," *Gazeta.ru*, January 20, 2023, <https://www.gazeta.ru/politics/news/2023/01/20/19531615.shtml> (accessed February 22, 2026).

international consequences¹. At the same time, many government and parliamentary representatives opposed this idea. The Minister of Unification Kwon Young-se described calls for acquiring a bomb as a “dangerous illusion” that could isolate South Korea internationally. Veterans of ROK diplomacy have also opposed nuclearization, emphasizing the positive role the ROK’s non-nuclear status has played in strengthening the global nonproliferation regime.

In sum, South Korea’s domestic discourse on the nuclear issue is shaped by tension between threat-driven pressures and responsibility. Fear and anger over DPRK actions fuel public support for “a bomb for Seoul.” However, rational considerations — sanctions risks, potential loss of allies, and the danger of an arms race — have thus far kept official policy within the nonproliferation framework. Most South Korean elites continue to view nuclear weapons as an extreme and undesirable step that would create more problems than it would solve. Notably, even after President Yoon in January 2023 hypothetically mentioned the possibility of nuclear armament in case of sharp deterioration, within weeks he specifically reaffirmed the ROK’s commitment to the NPT as the “only realistic and rational choice.”² This indicates that Seoul’s official line remains unchanged despite intense debate.

Conclusion. The ROK’s experience in 1991-2023 demonstrates both the possibilities and the limitations of a security policy without reliance on national nuclear weapons. After renouncing nuclear armament in the early 1990s and consolidating a non-nuclear status jointly with the DPRK, South Korea succeeded in providing for its security through a combination of external guarantees and the build-up of conventional capabilities. On the one hand, the alliance with the United States was crucial: the U.S. nuclear umbrella enabled Seoul to avoid a costly and risky nuclear arms race. On the other hand, South Korea invested significant resources in strengthening its armed forces, developing precision-strike capabilities, missile defense systems, and other deterrence instruments consistent with the nonproliferation regime. This approach largely proved effective: even in the face of repeated DPRK nuclear tests and missile launches, the ROK did not become defenseless and did not resort to fear-driven policy choices.

Nevertheless, the period studied is marked by persistent and growing pressure on the ROK’s non-nuclear policy. Whereas in the 1990s preserving a non-nuclear status appeared an unambiguous benefit (when the DPRK was not yet a nuclear state), by the 2020s the situation became far more complex. The DPRK’s real

¹ Shin, Hyonhee, “Exclusive: Seoul Mayor Calls for South Korean Nuclear Weapons to Counter Threat from North,” Reuters, March 13, 2023, <https://www.reuters.com/world/asia-pacific/seoul-mayor-calls-south-korean-nuclear-weapons-counter-threat-north-2023-03-13/> (accessed February 22, 2026).

² Ibid.

nuclear arsenal and delivery systems capable of threatening both the ROK and the United States fostered doubts among South Koreans regarding the adequacy of previous approaches. For the first time in decades, scenarios previously considered unthinkable began to be discussed seriously in Seoul — such as the return of U.S. nuclear warheads or withdrawal from the NPT to pursue national nuclear weapons. Although these ideas remain hypothetical, their emergence reflects the depth of the challenges confronting nonproliferation policy.

The domestic balance between “fear and rationality” still favors the latter: the ROK’s leadership, relying on expert analysis and international support, continues to choose a non-nuclear status as the most responsible and secure course. Recent statements reaffirming commitment to the NPT and rejecting nuclear acquisition support this assessment.

In conclusion, the ROK’s nuclear policy in 1991-2023 constitutes an important component of the historical experience of nonproliferation. South Korea has confirmed the viability of a security model without a national nuclear arsenal even under immediate nuclear threat. To a significant extent, due to its restraint, North-east Asia (with the exception of the DPRK) remained a region free of nuclear weapons for more than three decades. Preserving this situation serves global stability. The history of the ROK’s non-nuclear status shows that security guarantees grounded in alliance commitments and international law, though severely tested, can function as an alternative to nuclear proliferation. It remains crucial that the ROK — like other technologically capable states — continue to follow this course, strengthening the nonproliferation regime in the interest of international peace and security.

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SAFE SATIRE: THE TRANSFORMATION OF THE COMIC REGIME IN SOVIET ANIMATION

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Abstract. *This article examines the evolution of satirical animation in the USSR as a specific form of artistic expression situated at the intersection of asmpial strategies and state cultural policy. Late Soviet satirical animation is interpreted as a model of institutionally safe satire — a controlled form of social reflection that emerged through the transformation of the comic regime from the normative Stalinist model to the authorial animation of the Thaw period and the subsequent institutionalization of critical discourse in the 1970s-1980s. Drawing on archival materials from the Russian State Archive of Literature and Art (RGALI), studies by Russian and international scholars, and analysis of animated segments in the satirical film magazine Fitol, the article explores mechanisms through which artistic language interacted with ideological control.*

Keywords: *Soviet animation, satire, Fitol film magazine, Soviet cultural policy, auteur animation, double coding, state laughter, ideological control.*

Introduction

Soviet satirical animation occupies a distinctive place in the history of national screen culture. Unlike live-action cinema, which was perceived as a direct carrier of ideological meaning, animation was long regarded as a secondary and predominantly children-oriented medium. This institutional marginality paradoxically enabled it to become a space for more complex artistic solutions and indirect forms of social critique.

This study proposes to interpret late Soviet satirical animation as a manifestation of a specific model of the comic — *institutionally safe satire*, emerging at the intersection of authorial artistic language and mechanisms of state cultural regulation. Such satire allowed criticism of everyday social phenomena while maintaining the ideological stability of the system.

The evolution of this model is closely linked to the transformation of the functions of laughter within Soviet culture: from the normative “state laughter” of the

Stalinist era to the multilayered authorial irony of the Thaw period, and finally to an institutionalized form of social self-reflection in the 1970s.

Main Body

Researchers of Soviet culture have noted that during the Stalinist period laughter possessed a strictly normative character. The comic functioned primarily as a tool of ideological mobilization and maintenance of social hierarchy rather than as a space for doubt or criticism [1]. Analyses of the phenomenon of “state laughter” demonstrate that humor was permitted only within unambiguous frameworks — ridicule directed at external enemies, disciplinary deviations, or бытовые shortcomings that did not challenge systemic foundations [2].

For animation, this meant a limited range of satirical possibilities. Although political satire existed in early Soviet cartoons, by the postwar period it gradually gave way to a humanistic and educational narrative model. The comic became a regulated form of permitted amusement embedded within ideological discourse [3].

By the mid-1950s, however, the cultural paradigm began to change. The Thaw did not eliminate control but rather complicated artistic language. It was during this period that auteur animation emerged, characterized by visual stylization, metaphorical imagery, and multilayered meaning. N. Krivulya identifies *double coding* as a defining feature of this stage — the ability of a work to address both a mass audience and a more sophisticated level of interpretation [4]. These aesthetic changes were also linked to production processes. As G. Borodin observes, the rejection of naturalistic representation and the turn toward graphic abstraction expanded animation’s expressive possibilities [5].

International scholars likewise note that Soviet animation of the 1960s acquired traits of authorial artistic experimentation, in which movement and visual structure functioned as independent carriers of meaning [6]. Thus, a new language emerged — one that would later prove especially suitable for institutionalized satire.

The particular position of animation can be explained by its institutional status. Compared to live-action cinema, animation was perceived as a less politically significant field of culture. This underestimation created a kind of “blind spot” within systems of control, where more complex forms of irony could develop.

Western scholars have demonstrated that the conventionality of animated imagery allowed Soviet directors to address themes that would have required stricter censorship in other cinematic forms [7]. According to D. MacFadyen, animation gradually became a space for intellectual play with the viewer, where visual metaphor enabled filmmakers to avoid direct ideological declarativity [8].

By the early 1970s, satire had become an integral part of state cultural policy. Archival documents from RGALI record direct involvement of the State Committee for Cinematography (Goskino) in thematic planning of satirical content. For example, a decree issued on September 23, 1970, instructed the film magazine *Fitil* to

include critical stories addressing environmental issues [9], while Goskino Order No. 231 of June 6, 1978 mandated the systematic production of satirical materials against alcoholism, including annual animated shorts devoted to this topic [10].

Production reports from the *Soyuzmultfilm* studio for 1974 confirm the integration of animated *Fital* segments into the planned system of production and payment [11]. This demonstrates that satire ceased to be a spontaneous artistic statement and became part of an institutional structure.

Animated segments in *Fital* reveal a stable dependence of artistic decisions on the boundaries of permissible discourse. Typification of characters, schematic spatial design, and the rejection of psychological individualization shifted criticism away from concrete subjects toward abstract social phenomena. Episodes such as *Ekspونات* (1972) and *Zubik* (1974) construct humor around the absurdity of bureaucratic procedures without challenging the ideological foundations of the system [12].

The use of allegory and fairy-tale stylistics in later works further increased the distance between representation and reality, making criticism safer for institutional reception [13]. Late Soviet satirical animation thus demonstrates a paradoxical situation: the strengthening of institutional control did not eliminate satire but instead ensured its stability.

By relocating critical expression into the domain of conditional visual art, animation reduced ideological risk while allowing the system to display an image of self-correction. In this sense, Soviet animation functioned as a mechanism for redistributing symbolic risk: criticism became permissible precisely because of its artistic conventionality.

Conclusion

The evolution of Soviet satirical animation demonstrates that changes in the functions of laughter played a key role in transforming the artistic language of animation. From the normative laughter of the Stalinist era, Soviet culture moved toward the multilayered authorial irony of the Thaw and eventually toward an institutionally safe model of satire embodied in the film magazine *Fital*.

Soviet satirical animation emerged not despite the system of control but through the system's ability to institutionalize criticism. This explains why animation became a space in which social reflection could exist in forms compatible with ideological stability.

Paradoxically, the stability of this model prepared the ground for its transformation in the late 1980s, when shifts in the political environment led to a reconsideration of the very function of the comic within culture.

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FORMATION OF THE TRANSITIVITY CATEGORY OF VERBS IN SANSKRIT

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the study of the formation of the category of verb transitivity in Sanskrit in the aspect of the general trends of the evolution of Indo-European languages. In the course of the study, it was established that the category of verb transitivity in Sanskrit was formed gradually, as a result of the accretion of pure verb roots with prefixes that add additional meanings. This phenomenon is also characteristic of other Indo-European languages, resulting in the widespread use of transitive verbs and the loss of pure intransitive verb roots. In the history of Indo-European languages, the accusative case of temporal and local meanings was often used in an unprepositional form. In early Sanskrit, the unprepositional temporal accusative case was more frequently used than in classical Sanskrit. This circumstance is due to the greater degree of Sanskrit synthetism. The tendency towards analyticism, which is observed in the course of the linguistic evolution of the entire Indo-European language family, has undoubtedly led to the gradual disappearance of many prepositional case forms, including a number of Accusative case meanings. When studying this phenomenon, it is also necessary to take into account the gradual formation of the transitivity category in a number of verbs, which served as an additional reason for the loss of certain prepositional case meanings, particularly the Accusative Temporal with intransitive verbs, since the valence features of intransitive verbs practically excluded their compatibility with the Accusative case without a preposition.*

Keywords: *verb, transitivity category, Accusative case*

The category of verb transitivity is directly connected with one of the primary functions of the Accusative case in Indo-European languages — the function of the direct object. However, it should also be noted that, in addition to nominative languages, there are ergative languages whose structure does not presuppose the presence of either a subject (Nominative) or its counterpart — the object (Accusative). Furthermore, ergative linguistic systems can be regarded as more ancient

than nominative ones, since traces of a former ergative structure can be found in some languages currently classified as nominative. One of the indicators of the transition of a language system from an ergative stage to a nominative stage can be identified as the process of the formation of the category of verb transitivity. This very process is examined in the present article through the example of the Sanskrit language.

The accusative case in classical Sanskrit, as in most Indo-European nominative languages [6, p. 1736], [3, p. 251], [10, p. 2501], primarily served as the case of the direct object [2, p. 8]. However, with transitive verbs, the realization of this function became difficult. For example, in modern Russian, intransitive verbs such as “спать” (to sleep), “бежать” (to run), and others almost never combine with Accusative case forms, except in rare cases like “бежать три часа” (to run for three hours) or “проспать два дня” (to oversleep for two days). In the history of the Russian language, the situation was different: the category of verb transitivity/intransitivity was only in the process of formation and had more flexible boundaries. A similar situation can be observed in other ancient languages: “ahaṁ ča viçramjāmi *niçām imām*” [10, 64, 119] «I will rest this night.» Since this issue has been well studied in the syntax of classical languages, Latin, and Ancient Greek, in the present study we examine the features of the formation of the category of verb transitivity and the combination of intransitive verbs with adverbial forms of Sanskrit, which will allow us to identify several general features and establish multiple algorithms for translating case constructions [1, p. 7].

The purpose of the article is to identify and characterize the features of the formation of the category of transitivity in Sanskrit, to examine examples of the use of the Accusative case with temporal meaning in Sanskrit with intransitive verbs, and to conduct a comparative analysis with similar functions of the Accusative in Russian. To determine the influence of prefixation on the formation of the category of verb transitivity, and to establish the features of valency of the temporal Accusative in modern Russian.

Verb transitivity in linguistics is defined as a grammatical feature of verbs, consisting in the ability of a verb to govern a strongly controlled preposition-free form of the Accusative case (and, for verbs with negation, the form of the Genitive case) with an object meaning: to love theater — not to love theater [4, p. 307]. From this standpoint, it can be concluded that this category is characteristic of nominative, but not ergative language structures.

It should be recognized that in ancient languages the category of transitivity, largely based on additional nuances introduced into verbal meanings by means of prefixes, was still in the process of formation. This was due to the fact that most verbal roots, some of which are now no longer free (for example, the root “-nik-” in Russian), were still used without prefixes during the early stages of language

development. However, in the course of language evolution, these roots gradually acquired additional morphemes and thus expanded their syntactic valency, gaining the ability to govern the Accusative case without a preposition.

In the present study, we examine several prefixes of the Old Indic language which, when combined with simple roots, expanded the range of verbal governance, resulting in the formation of several transitive verbs in Sanskrit.

The prefixes involved in the formation of transitivity in Sanskrit include the following: “ati” ‘over, before, in front of’; “adhi” ‘over, up’; “anu” ‘after, behind’; “apa” ‘from’; “api” ‘towards, on’; “abhi” ‘at, to’; “ava” ‘from, off’; “ā” ‘at, to’; “ut” ‘up’; “upa” ‘under, to’; “ni” ‘from, with, near’; “nis” ‘out’; “pari” ‘around, about’; “pra” ‘before, over, in front of’; “prati” ‘around, about’; “vi” ‘out, apart’; “sam” ‘with, together’. In combination with these prefixes, verbs begin to convey not only the semantics of movement but also imitation “anu,” companionship “sam” — an action conditioned by various circumstances and emotional affects, for example, “as” «to be» — “atias” «to be above, to surpass,» “bhu” «to be, to become» — “anubhu” «to feel, to experience,» “lamb” «to hang» — “avalamb” «to grasp onto something» and others.

Let us provide several examples of prefixed verbs which, as a result of the addition of this morpheme, became transitive. It should be noted that sometimes it is difficult to find a transitive equivalent of a verb in translation:

“çṛīja samānān ati syāma” [5, XI, 1. 12, 21] «let us surpass all in happiness!»

“aham *patin* na ’tīçaye na ’tyaçne na ’tibhuşaye” [15. III, 14686] «I do not lie down before my husband, nor eat, nor adorn myself before him.»

“niçasv api *çmaçanam* adhiçaye” [8, 164, 12] «even at night I spend time in the cemetery (= at night I lie in the cemetery).»

“kathabhis *tam* anuçayya nitaratriḥ” [8, 184, 4] “(when) I lay down after him, I spent the night telling stories” — in this example, a gerund form of the verb “to lie down” is used; however, the formation of this form in Russian contradicts semantic principles, so in the translation we replaced it with a subordinate clause, also conveying an additional action.

“kamanusari uruşah *kaman* anuvinaçyati” [13, 4826] “a man who follows his desires (= satisfies his desires) perishes along with them.

“*viçva jatany* abhiyasi” [14, VI, 25, 5] “you overpower all beings.”

“*dhāiryam* avalambya” [9, 224] “armed with courage.”

“upatişṭhati *tişṭhantam*” [13, 5272] “fate stands beside him.”

“samavatsarasya tad *ahaḥ* pari ştha” [14, VII, 103, 7] “thus you spend that day of the year.”

Most prefixed verbs are translated into Russian as perfective verbs, although they do not always form an aspectual pair with the original verb. However, in the source language and in translation, these verbs become transitive.

It should also be noted that some verbs in Sanskrit, which remain formally intransitive, can, in certain cases, govern a direct object in the Accusative case. In such cases, this usually involves verbs of motion combined with words indicating *time* and *place*. This article examines the peculiarities of the use of the Accusative temporal with intransitive verbs.

In Sanskrit, the accusative case for temporal expressions was fairly well established. It was typically used to indicate a specific time interval during which the action of the verb occurred, such as “*ekam māsam*” «one month», “*varṣaṇam*” «one hundred years». Let us examine several examples from ancient Indian texts:

“*na kañcit suṣvāpa tām niṣām*” [15, VII, 2784] «no one slept that night».

“*viñcatim vai sahasrāṇi varṣāṇām gām apālatat*” [12, I, 44, 6] «For twenty thousand years he guarded the earth.»

“*na ṅaknomi givituṃ ṅarvarīm imām*” [12, II, 22, 7] «I cannot survive this night (any longer).»

“*duādaṅābdān vahāmj eṣa ṅirasā tava pādūke*” [11, 6, 149] «I will carry your boots on my head for twelve years.»

“*sa tasthāu katiṅid divasān*” [11, 18, 250] «he stayed for several days.

Apart from cases indicating the Accusative of time fully occupied by the verbal action, in the Sanskrit texts the temporal Accusative often depends on verbal government. Notably, these cases are most frequently observed with the verb “to go,” which is intransitive in modern Russian. Therefore, these examples generally do not pose difficulties in translation. Examples with the accusative temporal complement accompanying the verb “to go” in a figurative sense pose considerable difficulty for the translator:

“*tad dinam gaṅāma*” [16, 8, 17] “he spent that day.”

“*māsam ekam naro jātti dvāu māsaū mṅgaṅkarāu — ahir ekam dinam jati*” [9, 730] “one person (= his meat) suffices (= lasts) for one month, fawns and wild boar for two months, the snake suffices for one day.”

This manner of using the Accusative case eventually became the foundation for the formation in Sanskrit of several derived adverbs, not only with temporal meanings: “*atimātram*” ‘excessively’, “*asaṅṅajam*” ‘undoubtedly’, “*anantaram*” ‘before one’s eyes, in the presence of’, “*anudivasam*” ‘in sequence’, “*jathāpuram*” ‘as before’, “*prasabham*” ‘forcibly’, “*tuṅṅaghātam*” ‘striking with the beak’ [7, 5, 101], and others.

It should be noted that equivalents of the Accusative Temporal construction were also used in classical Sanskrit, for instance, to indicate an approximate time interval:

“*pūrvam saṅdhjām prati*” [15, IX, 411] «around the first twilight».

“*sūrjasjo ’dajanam prati*” [12, VI, 109, 20] «around sunrise».

Conclusions

The analysis presented in this article established that the category of verb transitivity in Sanskrit developed gradually through the addition of prefixes to bare verbal roots, conveying supplementary meanings. This phenomenon is also characteristic of other Indo-European languages, leading to a broader distribution of transitive verbs, while the formerly purely intransitive verbal roots became bound. The accusative case with temporal and locative meaning was often used in a prepositionless form throughout the history of Indo-European languages. It should be noted that in early Sanskrit, constructions with the prepositionless temporal Accusative case occurred more frequently than in Classical Sanskrit. This circumstance is primarily due to the higher degree of syntheticity of Sanskrit, as well as other ancient Indo-European languages. The tendency towards analyticism, observed throughout the evolution of the entire Indo-European language family, undoubtedly led to the gradual decline in the use of many case forms without prepositions, including several functions of the Accusative case. When studying this phenomenon, it is also necessary to consider the gradual development of the category of transitivity in certain verbs, which served as an additional reason for the loss of some prepositionless case functions, particularly the temporal uses of the Accusative with intransitive verbs, since the valency properties of intransitive verbs practically excluded their compatibility with the Accusative case without a preposition.

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MANIPULATION AS A WAY IMPACT ON THE MASS AUDIENCE

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Abstract. *The main features of manipulation are widespread in the media. Dominating the other methods of impact in the media, the manipulation is used to control consciousness and behavior of the recipient. The effectiveness of methods of manipulation in mass communication is that the hidden psychological effects provides the perception of information at an addressee's given standpoint.*

Key words: *addressee, impact, communication, manipulation, reception, hidden, belief.*

According to the observations of scientists, at the 21st century, manipulation of the addressee's consciousness in mass communication, especially in such forms as political and advertising activities, took on a comprehensive character (N. I. Klushina, O. L. Mikhaleva, T. I. Surikova, etc.). In post-Soviet society, this method of audience management, unlike previous direct It seems to be more effective due to the fact that in the process of implementing the pragmatic intentions set by the manipulator, as a rule, there is no psychological resistance on the part of the addressee.

The manipulative strategy of influence extends to other areas, so today we see the formation of a special, manipulative communication created by the mass media, which many researchers already consider as a manipulative system, where various methods of covert influence on the mass audience are tested and consolidated in speech practice. As A. K. believes. Mikhalskaya, at present, when the state, practically without developing civil structures, prefers a monological communicative style in communicating with the people, the media discourse, which performs the function of manipulation as the main one,

acquires the structure of manipulative discourse with a characteristic rejection of rational argumentation [1:24].

Given the current trend of language functioning in mass communication, which is widely used in influencing types of discourse as a means of programming the consciousness and, consequently, the behavior of the addressee, scientists are showing increased interest in this type of speech influence aimed at the emotional and volitional sphere of the addressee, rather than logical thinking. The problem of manipulating a person, his consciousness and behavior has repeatedly become the subject of attention of both domestic and foreign researchers (B. N. Bessonov, L. Voytasik, D. A. Volkogonov, M. L. Dotsenko, S. G. Kara-Murza, E. Kassirer, G. Schiller, E. Shostrom, and others), and it should be noted that the phenomenon of manipulation was considered in different aspects: psycholinguistic and communicative-pragmatic, related, on the one hand, to the theory of speech communication, and on the other hand, to pragmalinguistics.

The great interest in the above-mentioned problem is caused by many factors, including extralinguistic ones. Among the external reasons, first of all, the nature of the socio-psychological and political situation in Russian society should be highlighted, which largely determines the effectiveness of the impact resulting from the resort to manipulative techniques and techniques: “in modern conditions, the majority of the population cannot make a political choice based on their own interests. A significant part of society and the population of the country makes their choice not on the basis of a rational assessment of the programs of certain political movements and their leaders or their decisions and activities, but on an emotional level, based on the prevailing ratio of sympathy and antipathy, the degree of trust and distrust of specific leaders and organizations” [2:73].

In recent years, research on the problem of manipulation has intensified not only at the applied level, but also theoretically, since there are many ideas about manipulation (this term has gained popularity in various fields of linguistic science), a single definition of the concept under consideration has not yet been developed. Due to the lack of a clear definition, it is quite natural that the issue of distinguishing manipulation from other types of speech influence becomes relevant. The establishment of differential signs of the phenomenon of manipulation is also important because “a journalistic text is a complex hierarchical structure in which two tactics of persuasion are combined: open, influencing the mind of the reader, and subtext, having a direct impact on the consciousness of the addressee” [3:51]. And since the publicist uses all the means available to him to realize his intentions, in the texts of mass communication, the techniques of open persuasion are closely intertwined with manipulative techniques that provide hidden influence.

Thus, the difficulty of distinguishing the methods of influence used in the media during the implementation of the strategy of ideological subordination is largely

due to the fact that in modern newspaper practice manipulation becomes part of persuasion. Theoretically, persuasion and manipulation are contrasted as methods of influence, one of which is aimed at the intellectual sphere, and the other at the emotional, but in practice it is not always possible to distinguish persuasion from manipulation, since the prerequisites for linguistic manipulation are created by language itself with its developed system of connotative meanings and the availability of options for nominating the same phenomenon, properties or an object from the angle of view that is set by the addressee.

The issue of distinguishing between the above-mentioned phenomena is complicated by the fact that within the framework of mass media, the reader receives information selected and interpreted by the author, regardless of whether he acts as a manipulator or a rational analyst. It is no coincidence that when analyzing the texts of journalistic discourse, the secondary nature of information transmitted through media channels is often emphasized: a journalist selects certain facts, details, and details from the primary material, arranges them in the sequence he needs, while cutting off what contradicts his position. Therefore, the criterion of access to independent information, so to speak, to pure facts, which makes it possible to draw a line between manipulation and persuasion, is far from being implemented in practice in all cases, although it is referred to by many researchers studying the problems of exposure to mass media material.

While not denying the significance of this provision (manipulation is a way of influencing the addressee of speech, in which he is cut off from an independent source of information, as a result of which the information received is perceived uncritically by him), we believe that when solving the problem under consideration, we should also rely on other criteria that help reveal the essence of manipulation and show the conditions its successful application.

In the case of a close intertwining of persuasion and manipulation, it is advisable to consider the addressee's awareness/ unconsciousness in accepting the ideological model of behavior that he imposes (does not offer!) an addressee using a form of covert use of power or force. From this point of view, manipulation is understood as interference in the action of a person who is not aware of the object of influence.

Therefore, when describing this method of controlling the consciousness and behavior of a mass audience, it is necessary to emphasize that manipulation is precisely a hidden effect, the fact of which is not noticed by the addressee. A distinctive feature of the nature of manipulation is that, in parallel with an openly transmitted message, the manipulator sends an encoded signal to the object of influence, which, according to his assumptions, should have an undoubted impact on the emotional sphere. Being a method of influencing mental structures, manipulation is based not on the knowledge of the addressee, but on his ability to create certain images in his mind, thanks to which the manipulator's spiritual domination over the object of

influence becomes possible. In other words, the process of influence is carried out in the right direction for the manipulator, but in such a way that the manipulated person does not notice it, and therefore does not critically analyze it.

When considering the differential properties of manipulation, it is important to focus on the relationship of the manipulator to the recipient. Taking into account the specifics of manipulative influence, the addressee considers his communicative partner not as a person with an independent value, but as an instrument, a means for effective solution of pragmatic tasks. The weight of this criterion is quite significant, as evidenced by the definitions of manipulation known in foreign science: this method of influence is often understood as “management and control, exploitation of another, using it as an object, a thing” [4:5].

Manipulation is a type of hidden psychological influence through the introduction into the addressee’s consciousness, which is considered as a means of achieving a set goal, certain attitudes that ensure submission to the addressee’s influence. The use of manipulation techniques in mass communication ensures that the addressee perceives information from the angle set by the addressee.

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COGNITIVE STRATEGIES FOR ENCODING LOGICO-SEMANTIC RELATIONS

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Abstract. *This article presents a cognitive analysis that explicates how logico-semantic relations are encoded through coordinating conjunctions and their analogues in contemporary French. The study identifies four fundamental cognitive strategies: integrative, differentiating, prospective, and retrospective. Each strategy corresponds to a specific class of coordinating units and is grounded in unique, stable combinations of image schemas. The analysis of 9,642 contexts from the corpus Frantext reveals that the semantics of function words are systematically motivated by patterns of sensorimotor experience, establishing an ontological connection between bodily experience and abstract logical relations.*

Keywords: *cognitive strategies; logico-semantic relations; image schemas; coordinating units; French language*

Introduction

Modern cognitive linguistics seeks to explain the mechanisms underlying the formation of meaning in linguistic units, revealing their conceptual motivation. While extensive research has been devoted to coordinating conjunctions and their analogues, the question of how the meaning of these function words is motivated has typically remained open. Traditional structuralism treated conjunctions as “empty” function words (Tesnière, 1988, p. 79), while formal-logical models reduced their semantics to operations of conjunction, disjunction, and implication (Gak, 2000, p. 221). Functional approaches, although valuable, have primarily focused on recording discursive usages rather than explaining the cognitive foundations of meaning (Uryson 2011).

This study addresses this gap by proposing a cognitively grounded framework that explicates how logico-semantic relations are conceptualized and encoded through coordinating units. By *coordinating units* we refer to coordinating conjunctions and their functional analogues that serve to link syntactic elements and

encode specific types of logical relationships. In French, these include the conjunctions *et* ‘and’, *ni* ‘nor’, *ou* ‘or’, *mais* ‘but’, *donc* ‘therefore’, *car* ‘for’, as well as their analogues such as *puis* ‘then’, *ainsi que* ‘as well as’, *pourtant* ‘however’, *c’est pourquoi* ‘that is why’, *en effet* ‘indeed’, and others (Auseichyk, 2023).

The central premise is that abstract logical relations are not arbitrary linguistic conventions but are systematically motivated by patterns of sensorimotor experience. As Johnson (1987, p. xiv) argues, image schemas — recurring structures of our perceptual interactions and bodily movements — provide the foundation for meaning construction across both concrete and abstract domains.

The research aims to identify the cognitive strategies underlying the encoding of logico-semantic relations in French coordinating units and to describe the progression from embodied experience to linguistic expression through distinct levels of conceptual organization. Preliminary reflections are presented in (Auseichyk, 2025, pp. 387-392).

The research material was drawn from a segment of the Frantext sub-corpus (National Corpus of French) covering the period from 2000 to the present, with a total volume of 22,720,243 word usages. A total of 9,642 contexts containing these coordinating units were selected.

Theoretical Framework

The study integrates three complementary theoretical platforms. First, Langacker’s (1987, 1991) cognitive grammar provides the foundational distinction between profile, base, and domain. Within this framework, the meaning of a linguistic unit is understood as a profile highlighted against a cognitive base, which itself exists within broader cognitive domains constituting our experience (space, time, force, etc.). Second, image schema theory (Johnson, 1987; Lakoff, 1987; Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Evans & Green, 2006; Gibbs, 2006) offers the analytical tools for identifying the embodied structures that motivate abstract meaning. Image schemas are characterized by several properties essential for this analysis: universality and productivity (a limited set of schemas generates infinite experiential structures through combinations and transformations), amodality (information processing in a unified format regardless of input channel), and capacity for metaphorical projection (transfer from sensorimotor source domains to abstract target domains). Third, Mandler and Pagán Cánovas’s (2014) ontogenetic model provides crucial terminological precision, distinguishing between spatial primitives (basic building blocks like [path], [container], etc.), image schemas (simple spatial events combining primitives), and schematic integrations (combining spatial schemas with non-spatial elements like force, time, emotion).

The methodology proceeds through three stages: (i) identification of image schemas for each logico-semantic relations class through contextual analysis of corpus data; (ii) identification of stable combinations (patterns occurring in > 80% of

contexts and regularly reproducible across discourse types); (iii) construction of an integrative model correlating image schema combinations with cognitive domains.

Results

Application of the presented research methodology to the corpus material revealed that coordinative units function as linguistic profiles of deep cognitive operations embodying ontologically relevant strategies for structuring human experience: *integrative* (the conjunction *et* and its analogues), *differentiating* (the disjunctive conjunction *ou* and the adversative conjunction *mais* and their analogues), *prospective* (the consequential conjunction *donc* and its analogues), and *retrospective* (the causal conjunction *car* and its analogues). The meaning of each unit is formed through the activation of stable configurations of image schemas, which constitute the cognitive base for profiling the corresponding type of logico-semantic relation.

Integrative Strategy (the conjunction et and its analogues). The primary schema for the conjunction *et* and its analogues (*ni...ni* ‘neither...nor’, *ainsi que* ‘as well as’, etc.) is [container]. Elements A and B are mentally placed into a common conceptual container, creating unity and togetherness. Example (1) illustrates this: antagonistic concepts hatred and love are contained within the unified space of father’s motivation.

(1) *Par haine des “Boches” et amour de la patrie, mon père s’était brouillé peu à peu avec tous ses amis pétainistes* (B. Groult, 2008¹). / Because of hatred for the “Krauts” and love for his country, my father gradually fell out with all his Pétainist friends.

The [container] schema combines with additional schemas to structure internal organization: [container + iteration] creates temporal or logical chains (2); [container + part-whole] reveals contents of a general concept (3); [container + up-down] + [centre-periphery] profiles hierarchical relations (4); [container + intensity] creates gradational effects (5).

(2) *Alors il mimait le chêne, puis les loups, puis les tigres, puis les renards, puis les ours, puis tous les animaux du monde* (S. Chalandon, 2006). / Then he imitated the oak, then the wolves, then the tigers, then the foxes, then the bears, then all the animals in the world.

(3) *Rien ne venait perturber leur traintrain quotidien, à savoir les heures de lever, de sieste et de repas* (M. Mihami, 2018). / Nothing disturbed their daily routine, namely: getting up times, nap times, and meal times.

(4) *Tout un étrange petit monde s’agitait autour du maître d’école Platonov, une Anna Petrovna, une Sofia Egorovna, un Vengerovitch, et d’autres dont il n’avait pas même retenu le nom* (M. Bénabou, 2002). / A whole strange little world

¹ Here and in all subsequent examples, the citations are drawn from the corpus.

stirred around the schoolteacher Platonov, some Anna Petrovna, some Sofia Egorovna, some Vengerovitch, and others whose names he hadn't even remembered.

(5) *Je ne pensais pas indispensable de légiférer, dans la crainte de donner aux islamistes avides d'en découdre la facilité de présenter les jeunes exclues en victimes, voire en martyres* (M. Ozouf, 2009). / I did not consider it essential to legislate, fearing to give the eager-to-fight Islamists the opportunity to present the young excluded women as victims, or even as martyrs.

The integrative strategy thus conceptualizes connection not as simple addition but as complex spatial organization within conceptual containers.

Differentiating Strategy I: Disjunctive Unit. Disjunctive units (*ou* 'or', *soit...soit* 'either...or', *tantôt...tantôt* 'sometimes...sometimes', etc.) activate [source-path-goal] with branching [splitting path], requiring choice. The basic configuration [container + source-path-goal + splitting path] combines with additional schemas to produce distinct subtypes: [...+ in-out] yields exclusive alternation (6): binary opposition in physical space, with choice of one zone ([in]) excluding the other ([out]); [...+ merge] profiles combination of alternatives (7): formal choice offered between literal and metaphorical meanings, but response both activates schema merger, canceling choice; [...+ accumulation] underlies inclusive union (8): repetition of *ou* marks sequential addition to a common container.

(6) *En haut ou en bas? — En bas* (M. Fellag, 2007). / Upstairs or downstairs? — Downstairs.

(7) — *Au sens propre ou au figuré? — Les deux, mon général* (A. Gavalda, 2004). / — Literally or figuratively? — Both, General.

(8) *Vous en avez rien à faire de ce qui peut arriver à Clara ou à Sole... ou de ce qui va nous arriver un jour à Ana et à moi* (M. Borie, 2021). / You don't give a damn about what might happen to Clara or to Sole... or about what will happen one day to Ana and me.

When combined with [FORCE] schemas, disjunction encodes forced choice (9) or symmetric alternatives under external pressure (10). With [BALANCE], it profiles harmonious alternation (11) or temporary equilibrium between conflicting impulses (12).

(9) *Montez, ou vous êtes mort* (D. Pennac, 1989). / Get up, or you're dead.

(10) *...lorsque la colère prenait leurs voisins ou si les lois venaient à les désigner pour cibles* (A. Sabot, 2020). / ...when anger seized their neighbors or if laws came to single them out as targets.

(11) *...soit à regarder la télévision soit à écouter de la musique* (M. Alaoui, 2018). / ...either watching television or listening to music.

(12) *...hésitant entre l'éclat de rire nerveux, les larmes ou l'insulte* (B. Groult, 2008). / ...hesitating between a burst of nervous laughter, tears, or an insult.

Differentiating Strategy II: Adversative Units. Adversative units (*mais* ‘but’, *cependant* ‘however’, *pourtant* ‘yet’, *par contre* ‘on the other hand’) connect mutually exclusive elements through negation, activating [in-out] as in (13), (14). Two main combinations determine opposition type. First, [container + in-out + force] presents element B as obstacle (15), counterforce (16), or compulsion (17). Second, [container + in-out + balance] profiles compensation (18) or complex equilibrium (19).

(13) *Ce n'était pas chez nous, mais chez ma tante* (B. Groult, 2008). / It wasn't at our place, but at my aunt's.

(14) *Elle n'est plus mais son esprit demeure* (M. Palain, 2019). / She is no more, but her spirit remains.

(15) *Le Toro voulut bouger mais il avait les membres entravés* (C. Férey, 2012). / Toro wanted to move, but his limbs were bound.

(16) *Plus maigre... Mais elle était toujours belle* (J.-M. G. Le Clézio, 2003). / Thinner... But she was still beautiful.

(17) *...que le héros de la fête vous remarque, alors que vous êtes le méprisable* (M. Desplechin, 2006). / ...that the hero of the party notices you, whereas you are the contemptible one.

(18) *La durée normale... n'est que d'un mois... mais, pour obtenir une prolongation, il suffit de repasser une frontière* (M. Houellebecq, 2001). / The normal duration is only one month... but to obtain an extension, it is enough to cross a border.

(19) *J'aimais ses pleurs... mais je craignais sa colère* (Ph. Lançon, 2018). / I loved her tears... but I feared her anger.

Prospective Strategy (Consequential Units). Consequential units (*donc* ‘therefore’, *c'est pourquoi* ‘that's why’) activate [source-path-goal] visualizing causal relation as movement from cause to consequence. Three combinations emerge based on causal type. First, [source-path-goal + straight + compulsion/blockage + balance] presents consequence as indisputable conclusion (20), (21). Second, [source-path-goal + compulsion + balance + transformation] encodes moral imperative (22), (23). Third, [source-path-goal + compulsion + diversion/iteration + enablement] profiles practical solutions to changed circumstances (24), (25).

(20) *Les bois de la commune contiennent donc quatre mille huit cents chênes... Par conséquent Delphine et Marinette se sont trompées* (M. Aymé, 2002). / So, the communal woods contain four thousand eight hundred oaks... Consequently, Delphine and Marinette were mistaken.

(21) *Je n'ai rien gagné, donc je n'achèterai rien* (V. Hanf, 2013). / I earned nothing, so I will buy nothing.

(22) *Elle avait eu cette chance, mais moi je ne l'avais pas eue, alors elle voulait m'aider* (H. Guibert, 2007). / She had had that chance, but I hadn't, so she wanted to help me.

(23) *Je ne suis pas convaincu de sa culpabilité. C'est pourquoi je suis ici* (J. Dicker, 2012). / I am not convinced of his guilt. That is why I am here.

(24) *Je n'ai pas réussi à joindre Catherine Deneuve... Donc je lui ai écrit une lettre* (M. Simonet, 2010). / I couldn't reach Catherine Deneuve... So I wrote her a letter.

(25) *...puis découpe, replie, referme, lisse, appuie, enfin contemple* (N. Sarraute, 1983). / ...then cuts, folds back, closes, smooths, presses, finally contemplates.

Retrospective Strategy (Causal Units). Causal units (*car* 'for', *en effet* 'indeed') activate inverted [source-path-goal], moving from consequence ([goal]) to cause ([source]). Three combinations emerge. First, [inverted path + straight + link + compulsion] establishes objective causation (26), (27). Second, [inverted path + compulsion + balance] connects emotional manifestation to cause (28), (29). Third, combinations with [validation + matching] confirm predictions (30); with [false goal + correction path + true goal + in-out] correct errors (31); with [container + in-out + enablement + compulsion] appeal to fundamental principles (32).

(26) *...ils ne voyaient pas les étoiles car le ciel était voilé* (Al. Jenni, 2011). / ...they couldn't see the stars, for the sky was overcast.

(27) *...son époux vient d'être transporté à l'hôpital. De fait la scie est passée à deux doigts de la carotide* (M. Winock, 2003). / ...her husband has just been taken to the hospital. For the saw had passed within two fingers of the carotid artery.

(28) *Alice est horriblement anxieuse, car son domestique... n'y est pas arrivé* (J. Pouquet, 2006). / Alice is horribly anxious, for her servant... hasn't arrived.

(29) *...laisse présager une grande blessure. En effet, la seule photo de sa fille... elle l'a trouvée foulée aux pieds* (H. Castel, 2009). / ...all presage a great wound. For the only photo of her daughter... she found trampled underfoot.

(30) *Papa était très doué pour voir venir les choses. Effectivement le ciel se mit à changer de couleur* (R. Ouedraogo, 2020). / Dad was very gifted at foreseeing things. Indeed, the sky began to change color.

(31) *...elle n'est pas malade. En fait elle s'est fait agresser et violer* (M. Houellebecq, 2001). / ...she is not ill. In fact, she was attacked and raped.

(32) *Malik tâcherait d'en parler discrètement à Pierre. Après tout, c'était lui, son ami* (E. de Foucaud, 2021). / Malik would try to speak discreetly to Pierre about it. After all, he was his friend.

Discussion

The analysis reveals several fundamental principles. First, the semantics of coordinating units are systematically motivated: each logico-semantic relations class profiles meaning through a unique combination of image schemas, with one primary schema ([container], [splitting path], [in-out], [source-path-goal], [inverted path]) determining the basic relational structure, and additional schemas accounting for discursive variation. Second, the distinction between prospective and retrospective strategies in causal relations demonstrates that temporal directionality

is not merely a grammatical feature but reflects fundamental cognitive operations: consequential units conceptualize causality as forward movement along a path; causal units conceptualize it as backward searching from observed effect to hidden cause. This aligns with research on asymmetries in causal reasoning and the primacy of effect observation in everyday experience. Third, the analysis supports the embodied cognition thesis that abstract logical relations are grounded in sensorimotor experience. Concepts such as opposition, choice, consequence, and justification are not purely formal logical operations but are structured by image schemas emerging from bodily interaction with the environment: blocking forces, branching paths, containing spaces, and balanced scales. Fourth, the identification of stable combinations (patterns occurring in >80% of contexts across discourse types) demonstrates that these cognitive strategies are not ad hoc interpretations but systematic properties of linguistic semantics. The regular co-occurrence of specific schemas for each logico-semantic relations class indicates entrenched conceptual structures that motivate and constrain linguistic usage.

Conclusion

This study has demonstrated that the encoding of logico-semantic relations through French coordinating units is systematically motivated by four cognitive strategies grounded in image schema configurations. The integrative strategy conceptualizes unity through containment and structural organization; the differentiating strategy conceptualizes separation through path branching and force opposition; the prospective strategy conceptualizes causality as forward movement; the retrospective strategy conceptualizes causality as backward searching.

These findings have implications for linguistic theory, demonstrating that function words are not semantically empty but carry rich conceptual structure; for language teaching, providing a motivated basis for explaining connective usage; and for further research, opening perspectives for cross-linguistic comparison of cognitive strategies in encoding logical relations and for diachronic investigation of how these strategies emerge and change over time.

Research Materials

Frantext. National Corpus of French. <http://www.frantext.fr>

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TOOLS FOR DEVELOPING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES FOR TEACHING FRENCH

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Annotation. *This article examines the problem of digital support of the French phonetics learning process in the context of widespread universal educational platforms focused primarily on vocabulary and grammar. The typical phonetic difficulties of Russian-speaking students associated with the interfering influence of their native language are analyzed: nasal vowels, the opposition of sounds [y] and [u], the phenomenon of liaison. The functional limitations of existing digital tools are revealed: the inability to control the articulatory base, the binary nature of evaluation in speech recognition systems without diagnosing the type of error, the lack of templates for modeling coherent speech and phonetic warm-up. The zones of the French phonetic system that remain without proper digital support are determined. Based on the analysis, ways to improve digital educational resources are proposed, including the development of specialized phonetic templates, the integration of intelligent speech recognition systems, and the creation of modules for working with coherent speech.*

Keywords: *digital educational resources, phonetics of the French language, interference, pronunciation correction, speech recognition, nasal vowels, liaison, Russian-speaking students.*

The digital transformation of education has led to the emergence of an extensive array of tools for creating educational content. Platforms enabling the development of interactive modules, such as LearningApps, Quizlet, Wordwall, and others, have become an integral part of the modern educator's toolkit. Their popularity is attributable to ease of use, clarity, and the possibility of rapid assessment of knowledge acquisition. However, methodological analysis shows that the functionality of these tools in the vast majority of cases is oriented towards working with discrete units of language — words and grammatical constructions. Exercises based on the

principles of classification, comparison, or gap-filling are effective for developing lexical and grammatical skills but are poorly suited for the articulation and correction of pronunciation.

The French language has a unique and phonetically complex foundation for acquisition, which significantly differs from the phonetic system of the Russian language. Among the most challenging phenomena for Russian-speaking learners are nasal vowels, which have no analogues in the Russian language; the phenomenon of liaison, which alters the phonetic structure of a phrase; tense articulation; as well as the opposition between front and back vowels, particularly the distinction between the sounds [y] and [u]. It is precisely these aspects of pronunciation that directly influence semantic differentiation and, consequently, the effectiveness of communication. Errors in their implementation result in distortion of the meaning of the utterance or the development of a persistent foreign accent, reducing the phonetic acceptability of speech. Accordingly, a scientific and methodological problem arises: how digital tools, originally not intended for phonetic work, can be adapted to address the specific challenges of teaching French pronunciation, and which elements of the phonetic system remain unaddressed even when using specialized software. This study aims to analyze this gap and identify directions for enhancing digital educational resources within the context of teaching the phonetic aspect of the French language.

The current market of digital educational products and available online resources can be categorically divided into two main types relevant to phonetics: specialized tools (phonetic trainers, spectral analysis, and speech recognition software) and general didactic platforms, which can be used to create phonetic exercises with certain limitations[1, 2].

The first category includes resources such as Phonétique Fre, programs for working with intonograms, as well as individual modules within popular language courses (for example, Rosetta Stone with its speech recognition system). These tools possess considerable potential. Automatic speech recognition (ASR) technology enables the learner to receive feedback not on a ‘correct/incorrect’ basis but according to phonetic correspondence to the standard. The system analyzes the sound spectrum, its duration, and frequency characteristics, and provides an assessment of pronunciation quality. Such programs can signal that the sound [ɑ̃] is produced with insufficient nasalization or that the vowel [y] is too closed and retracted.

However, as practice demonstrates, these tools have limitations when addressing interference. Most ASR systems integrated into commercial products are trained on large datasets of native speaker speech and ‘ideal’ learners. They can identify the occurrence of an error but very rarely provide the learner with diagnostic information regarding the error type. For a Russian-speaking learner, it is critically important to receive the comment: ‘Your [ɑ̃] sounds like a pure vowel

[a] due to the lack of nasalization; lower the soft palate.’ Modern mass-market products generally do not provide such feedback, limiting themselves to an accuracy indicator (scale from 0 to 100 %).

The second category, which includes exercise builders (LearningApps, Quizlet, Triventy, etc.), offers the teacher the ability to independently populate templates with content. This opens opportunities for creative adaptation; however, phonetic specificity can only be reflected here indirectly. The teacher can create an exercise that requires matching a sound with its graphic representation (phonemes with graphemes), for example, grouping words with different pronunciations of the letter combination ‘oi’. Alternatively, a sound quiz can be created where the learner hears a word and selects its correct spelling, thereby training phonemic hearing. Nevertheless, the key link — articulation and muscular effort — remains beyond the control of the digital environment. The platform cannot evaluate whether the learner correctly shaped the lips to pronounce [y] or rounded them for [u]. The tasks remain at the level of sound recognition and discrimination (perceptual level), but do not address the productive level (actual speaking)[3].

To comprehend which phonetic elements remain ‘uncovered,’ it is necessary to examine in detail the nature of the interfering influence of the Russian language.

Firstly, the system of vocalism. The Russian language lacks nasal vowels. When pronouncing them, the airstream passes simultaneously through both the oral and nasal cavities. A Russian-speaking learner, lacking this habit, reproduces the French nasal vowels [ɑ̃], [ɔ̃], [ɛ̃] as the corresponding oral vowels [a], [o], [e] with a nasalized [n] or [m] sound at the end, which constitutes a significant phonetic error. Secondly, the opposition [y]–[u]. In French, these are two clearly distinct sounds: [y] — a front vowel, labialized, with the lips strongly protruded and tensed as for whistling; [u] — a back vowel, with lips protruded, but the tongue retracted. In Russian, there is the sound [y], which occupies an intermediate position; therefore, learners often confuse these two phonemes, substituting both with the Russian [y]. Thirdly, the phenomenon of liaison. It involves the appearance of an intervocalic consonant sound, which is not pronounced in an isolated word but arises in connected speech (for example, les_enfants). The rules of liaison are complex, variable, and require not only knowledge of the norm but also a well-developed phonetic ear [4]. The situation is exacerbated by the fact that the primary tool intended to provide learners with an acoustic standard — speech synthesis technologies (Text-to-Speech, TTS) embedded in electronic dictionaries and applications — often fails to correctly reproduce the described phenomena. Numerous observations of popular TTS engines (Google TTS, Amazon Polly, Acapela) record systematic failures precisely in areas vulnerable to Russian-speaking learners: during the implementation of liaison, either the obligatory linking is absent, or, conversely, it appears in prohibited contexts, which disrupts the normative sound fabric of the

French phrase. In the domain of vocalism, synthesized nasal vowels and the opposition [y]-[u] lack necessary characteristics (nasalization, tenseness), resulting in irrelevant acoustic standards for learners. The prosodic organization of the phrase in TTS is generally far from natural: the intonational contour is either excessively monotone or artificially emphasized. Thus, TTS, as the main provider of phonetic material for millions of users, paradoxically impedes rather than promotes the formation of phonetic competence, reinforcing the so-called ‘digital accent.’ This circumstance necessitates a critical reassessment of the role of synthesized speech in the educational process and consideration of this factor when analyzing the ‘uncovered’ areas of digital learning.

Let us consider how existing digital tools address these challenges. With respect to nasal vowels and the opposition [y]-[u], specialized acoustic programs (for example, the free speech analyzer Praat, which, however, is complex for an average user) enable visualization of the difference. On the spectrogram, the learner can observe that the formant structure changes during the nasal sound, and additional noise appears. However, such programs are not purely educational and require both the teacher and the learner to possess specialized knowledge in acoustic phonetics.

General didactic tools enable the creation of exercises for distinguishing pairs of words such as «vu» and «vous». For example, listening exercises with multiple-choice answers. The learner hears the phrase “Je l’ai vu” and must choose between two translation options: «I saw him» or «I saw you». This method is effective for training phonemic perception. However, at this stage, the digital environment is unable to assist the learner in correcting their own articulation. They may perfectly distinguish these sounds in the speaker’s speech, yet continue to pronounce them identically, and no digital task in LearningApps will indicate this to them. The most complex situation arises with the phenomenon of liaison. This suprasegmental phenomenon affects word boundaries and phrase prosody. Most digital exercises, especially at the initial stage, deal with isolated words. When transitioning to connected speech, learners encounter familiar words sounding differently due to the emergence of new sounds. Speech synthesis programs (Text-to-Speech), used in many online dictionaries and applications, often process liaison incorrectly. They either fail to apply liaison where it is mandatory (resulting in an incorrect auditory representation) or, conversely, apply it in prohibited contexts. Automatic speech recognition also faces difficulties analyzing connected speech, where liaison produces homographs and segmentation ambiguities in the speech stream. A digital tool very rarely explains the rule underlying any given type of liaison (mandatory, forbidden, or optional), and even less frequently can evaluate its appropriateness in a specific stylistic context[5].

The analysis reveals four key areas of French phonetics that lack adequate support from digital tools. The first area is articulatory kinesthetics. Mass digital

tools cannot monitor the position of speech organs during speech. Experimental developments using ultrasound have not extended beyond laboratories; therefore, sound formation requires the direct involvement of the instructor. The second area is the diagnosis of interference errors. Speech recognition systems operate on a binary evaluation principle, without classifying the type of error. They are unable to conduct phonetic analysis and correlate it with patterns of Russian interference. The third area is prosody and liaison in the speech flow. Existing platforms offer discrete exercises and do not model connected speech to the extent necessary for automating the skill of liaison. There are no tools for teaching the rhythm of the French phrase. The fourth area is an interactive phonetic warm-up. Universal tools do not provide templates for systematic phonetic exercises, compelling teachers to manually select materials [6, 7].

Based on the identified gaps, it is possible to outline directions for the development of digital tools adapted to the linguistic specifics of the French language.

First, a conceptual shift in the approach to templates within exercise builders is necessary. Alongside 'Find the Pair' and 'Quiz' templates, specialized phonetic templates should be introduced. For example, the 'Articulatory Trainer' template. This is a trainer presented as a video sample of articulation (video reference). A short video (10-15 seconds) can be embedded in the template of such an exercise, where the instructor or narrator clearly demonstrates the articulation of the sound, as well as the position of the lips and tongue, in close-up. The learner's task is to record their own version and visually compare themselves with the model (using the 'webcam recording' function). This is technically simple, visual, and, unlike the spectrogram, provides direct instructions for action. It is also possible to use simple wavern comparisons (visualizing volume and duration) to teach maintaining phrase rhythm without delving into complex formal structures. In any case, systems trained not only on 'clean' speech but specifically on the speech of Russian-speaking learners are required. Such a system, based on machine learning methods, could recognize not only the occurrence of an error but also its pattern: 'You pronounced the nasal sound as a combination of an oral vowel and a nasal consonant.' This would enable providing precise methodological recommendations for correction, significantly enhancing the learner's autonomy when working with phonetics[8, 9].

Thirdly, the development of modules for working with connected speech and liaison. The digital environment allows for the creation of interactive texts in which the rules of liaison are visualized (for example, letters involved in liaison are highlighted or change color when the cursor is hovered over them). A more advanced level involves listening exercises with 'noise,' in which the student must identify and graphically mark the locations where liaison has occurred. The use of karaoke technology is also promising for practicing the rhythmic and intonational structures of entire phrases, where the duration of pauses and pitch are displayed graphically.

Finally, it is necessary to integrate theoretical knowledge with practical exercises within a single digital resource. Instead of fragmented rules in the textbook and tests in the application, modules are required where a micro-lesson on the articulation of the sound [y] or linking rules is immediately reinforced by a series of interactive tasks with mandatory voice recording and automatic analysis. Only such a comprehensive approach can shift the focus of digital education in the French language from a lexico-grammatical dominance to the full development of all components of communicative competence, including phonetics[10].

The study confirms a significant gap between the didactic capabilities of modern digital tools and the requirements of teaching the phonetic system of the French language. Universal exercise builders, such as LearningApps and similar platforms, effectively address vocabulary and grammar training tasks, but due to their templated nature, they cannot provide adequate support for correcting pronunciation skills. Specialized tools, including speech recognition programs, have the necessary potential; however, their widespread implementation lacks mechanisms for diagnosing interference errors and providing tailored feedback [11, 12].

Critically, key elements essential for the French language remain unaddressed, such as the articulatory base (nasal sounds, the [y]–[u] opposition), suprasegmental phenomena (liaison, rhythm), and, most importantly, the connection between the auditory image and muscular effort. Overcoming this gap requires not the abandonment of digital tools but their qualitative advancement: the development of specialized phonetic templates in publicly accessible platforms, the integration of intelligent speech analysis systems trained to recognize typical errors of a specific language group (in this case, Russian speakers), and the creation of comprehensive interactive modules that combine theory, visual articulation visualization, and speaking practice with automatic feedback. Only under these conditions can digital educational resources become a full-fledged tool for developing phonetic competence, rather than remaining primarily a means for lexical-grammatical training.

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RATIONALITY AS THE ESSENTIAL FEATURE OF SOCIO-CULTURAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *The article argues that rationality as a quality inherent in human socio-cultural existence consists in a person's ability to discover the logic of things and follow this logic in the process of spiritual and practical development of the world. The irrational deed is the extreme limit of the proper social behavior, beyond which the instinctive biological acts are located. Actual differences in people's thoughts or ways of life are not the embodiments of multiple "rationalities", but of the same rationality as a universal, attributive characteristic of a social form of being.*

Keywords: *thinking, rationality, socio-cultural activity, irrationality, predictability.*

A history of emergence and development of man as a socio-cultural being is a history of emergence and development of a fundamental, generic, immanent feature of human socio-cultural activity, called rationality, which consists in a person's ability to discover the logic of things and follow this logic in the process of spiritual and practical development of the world. The process of formation of consciousness as a specifically human, socio-historical form of reflection of reality is inextricably linked with the process of formation of rationality as the ability to operate with concepts, i.e. to think.

Consciousness itself arises simultaneously with the emergence of thinking, in which alone the specificity of consciousness can be discovered in comparison with the psyche of animals. Thinking cannot be replaced by imagination, fantasy, feelings, emotions, or will, since all other mental processes in humans as a socio-cultural rather than biological being arise only on the basis of and in inseparable connection with thinking. Where there is consciousness, there is thinking, because it is thinking, as a specific form of consciousness, that begins with the act of distinguishing between I/we and non-I/non-we. Until this distinction occurs, there is no thinking, imagination, or memory as processes of conscious mental activity that characterize humans as opposed to animals.

When we talk about a person as a reasonable, rationally, meaningfully acting subject, we mean that this subject: 1) is conscious, i.e. knows about his own

existence, different from the existence of the surrounding world; 2) pursues a specific goal that exists in his mind in the form of an ideal image of the desired; 3) measures the chosen means of achieving the goal with the result obtained, i.e. is capable of choosing adequate means of achieving the goal.

The rational thinking differs from other forms of mental reflection, first of all, by the non-randomness of the properties of reality reflected with its help. The fact that essence and phenomenon as attributes of reality do not coincide with each other generates the objective need for the formation of thinking as a special ability of the human psyche to distinguish between these dialectically interrelated forms of being. Without the ability to identify the essential relationships between phenomena, to separate the necessary from the accidental, the emergence not only of specialized forms of knowledge (scientific, philosophical, humanitarian), but also of all those practical transformations that underlie the development of human civilization would be impossible.

The ability to think rationally, cognizing the essential properties of the surrounding world, lies at the heart of human cultural activity. Therefore, it would be wrong to characterize even primitive thinking as exclusively associative, unable to identify essential connections and relationships between phenomena, taking the accidental and insignificant for essential. Thanks to thinking, which reveals the essential properties and connections between the phenomena of reality already at the level of everyday consciousness, in everyday practical activities, people have learned how to make fire, create and improve tools, tame animals, cultivate the land, build a dwelling and much more. It would be impossible to spiritually master, understand, and comprehend the world without thinking based on the distinction between the visible and the invisible, the given and the hidden, the effect and the cause that gave rise to it.

Any comprehension as a process of spiritual transformation, subjective appropriation of the object's content, is impossible without mediation by already available spiritual products. That is why no sensory perception of the subject of cognition is direct. And no sensory perception can be theoretically described as immediate, since absolute phenomenological reduction is impossible in principle. Therefore, when M. K. Mamardashvili wrote that "... we see hooks and planks, but we know that these are skates and skis. And sometimes knowing what we see undoubtedly prevents us from seeing the visible" [4, p. 44], he did not take into account that the fact of seeing hooks and planks is possible only simultaneously with the fact of realizing that these are hooks and planks, and not anything else. In order to see hooks and planks, but not skates and skis, you need to know that these are hooks and planks. Just because we know something, we see it. Replacing skates and skis with hooks and planks does not change anything in the essence of the perception process. Otherwise, we would have to say that we do not see anything, or we see something, but we do not know what it is.

This example only demonstrates that direct perception is possible only at the level of instinctive existence, which never rises to the level of awareness. Any conscious perception is a perception mediated by certain ideal products. But it is precisely for this reason that no kind of understanding of reality, neither ordinary, nor mythological, nor religious, can be considered as absolutely direct, unrelated to rational thinking, which is the difference between the conscious activity of a cultural subject and the psyche of animals.

From a metaphysical point of view, rationality as a quality inherent in human socio-cultural existence is contrasted with irrationality as literally none-existence of rationality. The irrational deed is the extreme limit of the proper social behavior, beyond which the instinctive biological acts are located [3]. To take away reason is to turn a socio-cultural subject into an animal.

However, from the thesis that rationality is an attribute of a social form of existence and characterizes thinking as such, it does not follow at all that a person is always, everywhere and in everything equally rational or that irrationality is not inherent in him in principle.

It should be remembered that when analyzing human behavior, predictability is often considered as the measure of rationality, and everything that cannot be predicted is considered as irrational. Meanwhile, predictability acts more as a measure of the complexity of an object of cognition for the cognizing subject, rather than as a characteristic of the subject's own properties and reasonable grounds for activity.

In its most general and abstract form, the thesis of human unpredictability is false. Everyday experience testifies not only to the fundamental predictability of the behavior of most people in standard situations, but also to the ability of every sane person, based on their life experience, to predict the behavior of others with a high degree of probability, which, in fact, ensures the normal functioning of society.

If we are talking about non-standard, special situations, then it is necessary to clarify each time: in what sense, to what extent, and in what ways is a person unpredictable? Ignorance of a situation does not mean unpredictability of behavior, just as lack of predictability of behavior does not indicate its irrationality. Moreover, can anyone be considered a human being who is really unpredictable about the ultimate goals of his existence? Would not this unpredictability be an expression of an animal-like state, a lack of self-determination as a social being?

If a person retains a value orientation, then at least in this respect he is completely predictable. A decent person is just as predictable as a dishonest one in the main thing that makes it possible to call them that. At the same time, the lack of a moral assessment of any act, or the lack of guarantees that, even with the best intentions, a person will not commit an immoral act as a result, indicate not the irrationality of human behavior, but the real complexity and diversity of social relations, the emergence, development, and maintenance of which require adequate complexity and diversity of reasonable, rational activity.

It should be borne in mind that in the context of “our own/someone else’s”, the terms “rational”/ “irrational” always mark (and at least partially mask) elementary value judgments: “This is good (because we like it), so it is rational”, “This is bad (because we do not like it), so it is irrational”. In any case, the use of the terms “rational/irrational” to evaluate any set of ideas, actions, or holistic ways of life is an indirect confirmation that it is rationality as an attributive quality of sociality that serves as the basis for making an assessment.

Obviously, the definition of “irrational” in relation to philosophy is either meaningless (an oxymoron) or metaphorical: philosophy, by definition, is the territory of free reason, the territory on which sovereign reflection is carried out. But philosophy can make the subject of its own reflection various aspects of human existence, including those in which the manifestations of reason, and therefore sociality and culture, will be minimal, close to the limit [1].

However, a real, rather than imaginary, deviation from rationality turns out to be so threatening to human existence itself, both as a socio-cultural and even as a biological being, that it happens extremely rarely (on the scale of the human race as a whole, of course). In the real life of a cultural subject, transitions from rationality to irrationality occur only when thinking ceases to be adequate to its object, no matter what the nature of the object may be: whether this object is a scientific problem, a practical task, or emotional stress.

In addition, it should be emphasized that there are no “special types of reason” or “local types of rationality” in human culture [2], but there is a single human mind that historically develops and solves practical, cognitive and any other problems by methods and means appropriate to the nature of these problems. Actual differences in people’s thoughts or ways of life are not the embodiments of multiple “rationalities”, but of the same rationality as a universal, attributive characteristic of a social form of being.

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